

GREAT PrEPARATIONS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF THE EXPERIENCE OF
GAY, BISEXUAL AND OTHER MEN WHO HAVE SEX WITH MEN LIVING IN
AREAS OF HIGH DEPRIVATION IN THE WEST OF SCOTLAND
WHO ARE TAKING PRE-EXPOSURE PROPHYLAXIS TO HIV MEDICATION
(PrEP)

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Abstract

Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP) to Human Immuno-Deficiency Virus (HIV) is HIV medication being taken for prevention instead of for treatment. Gay, Bisexual and other Men who have Sex with Men (GBMSM) bear a disproportionate burden of HIV in Scotland and PrEP reduces transmission of HIV via sexual risk. In 2017 Scotland became the first UK country to provide free PrEP nationally via the NHS.

Concerns exist around widening health inequalities and PrEP uptake amongst GBMSM, disproportionately benefitting those better educated and/or from more affluent backgrounds. There is currently limited evidence regarding socioeconomic status and PrEP uptake.

Aim: To understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking PrEP.

Methodology

Purposive sample (n=12) of GBMSM living in SIMD quintiles one and two taking NHS PrEP. Data were collected utilising individual semi-structured telephone interviews. Data were analysed by Thematic Analysis informed by Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.

Findings: PrEP has successfully improved sexual wellbeing amongst GBMSM by effective HIV prevention and reducing the anxiety of acquiring HIV. Indeed, PrEP is now becoming normalised amongst GBMSM and appears to have replaced condoms for HIV prevention for many. Cultural competence amongst sexual health staff has been a significant factor in successful PrEP provision and uptake. However, PrEP has been linked to reduced condom use and an increase in sexual health risk taking behaviours. Furthermore, the lack of promotion of PrEP has led to problems around awareness; and physical and economic barriers to PrEP have been identified for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. Groups such as younger and bisexual GBMSM are less likely access sexual health services and PrEP, indicating a requirement to address gaps in sex education and HIV literacy.

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Author's declaration

The work in this thesis is the sole work of the candidate. This work has not previously been submitted for award at any other institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published by another person except where due reference is made in the thesis itself.

Abbreviations

AAAQ	Availability, Accessibility, Acceptability and Quality
AIDS	Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome
BASHH	British Association of Sexual Health and Human Immunodeficiency Virus
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CD	Cluster of Differentiation
DNA	Deoxyribo Nucleic Acid
EBD	Event Based Dosing
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GP	General Practitioner
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HSPC	Health and Social Care Partnership
IPA	Interpretative phenomenological analysis
GBMSM	Gay, Bisexual and other Men who have Sex with Men
NHS	National Health Service
NICE	National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence
NMC	Nursing and Midwifery Council
PrEP	Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis to HIV
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses
PHS	Public Health Scotland
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RNA	Ribo Nucleic Acid
STIs	Sexually Transmitted Infections
SIGN	Scottish Intercollegiate Guidelines Network
SIMD	Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation
SIV	Simian Immunodeficiency Virus
UK	United Kingdom
US(A)	United States (of America)
WHO	World Health Organisation

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Personal Integrative Statement

My journey in sexual health began in the early 1990s whilst working as a Centre Manager at a third sector sexual health clinic in a London hospital. Moving forward, I qualified as a registered nurse in Scotland in 1998 and worked in sexual health clinics for 19 years. During that time I gained a significant amount of clinical experience but less involvement with research; therefore was keen to progress my research knowledge and skills to strengthen my practice and gain new in-depth perspectives in sexual health. In 2011, I completed an MSc in Advanced Practice, which had a technocratic remit fitting well with increasing the scope of my role as a nurse managing complex patients. My MSc dissertation topic explored the experiences of GBMSM in the West of Scotland with regard to religion as a potential barrier to attending sexual health services. In 2017, the offer of funding of the first year of a Professional Doctorate at UWS allowed me the opportunity to further my studies. In the same year, PrEP was launched in sexual health services in Scotland and as a new intervention I felt it was an ideal topic for my Doctoral study. I was working in at least one PrEP clinic per week whilst studying, allowing me to compare the continually emergent body of knowledge of PrEP with my real-world experience in clinical practice (see 4.2).

During the PrEP clinics, I started to reflect on the characteristics of service users who were not attending sexual health services rather than those who were. In clinical practice I noticed a number of traditionally 'working class' GBMSM who were not part of the 'gay scene' and did not attend sexual health services very often. Many lived away from the city centre in traditionally more deprived areas and found transport to the clinics a barrier, particularly if they faced other pressures such as caring responsibilities. In my experience they only attended if sent by a GP or for treatment requiring attendance at a sexual health clinic. At the PrEP clinics I felt I tended to see knowledgeable traditionally 'middle class' GBMSM who were very engaged in their healthcare; however there were few vulnerable individuals or those facing barriers to healthcare due to aspects of deprivation. In light of this, together with current structural and systemic factors such as governmental austerity policies and the cost of living crisis augmenting financial hardship (Institute of Health Equity, 2020), I chose to focus on GBMSM taking PrEP who are living in areas of high deprivation for this study.

Chapter one: Background to the study

1.1 Introduction

This thesis will explore the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in the West of Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP medication to investigate how health inequalities may impact on the uptake of PrEP. PrEP is medication for HIV prevention used by people who are at high risk of HIV via sex. This first chapter introduces the thesis and gives the context in which the research is situated. The chapter starts by briefly introducing the pathophysiology of HIV; portraying the incidence/prevalence and establishing it as a defining public health issue. HIV stigma, activism, policy and treatment initiatives are then considered, leading to the context and development of PrEP. Finally, barriers surrounding PrEP acceptability, accessibility and deprivation are addressed.

1.2 HIV pathophysiology and AIDS

HIV is thought to have spread undetected to the USA in the mid 1960s and around the world in the 1970s (Huet *et al.*, 1990). The first reported cases of AIDS related illnesses were documented in 1981 in the USA when 121 young homosexual men suddenly died of pneumonia, weight loss and the rare skin disease, Kaposi's Sarcoma. In 1982 the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) established that these immune system disorders were due to an infection; however, as the route of transmission had not yet been identified, testing and treatment had not been developed. The prevalence disproportionately affected GBMSM, injecting drug users, haemophiliacs and Haitians due to specific behavioural and population risk factors (CDC, 1981). The HIV virus was identified in 1983 by Dr. Françoise Barré-Sinoussi and Prof. Luc Montagnier at the Pasteur Institute in Paris (Barre-Sinoussi *et al.*, 1983).

HIV is a retrovirus, consisting of Ribo Nucleic Acid (RNA) genetic material. HIV infects and destroys CD4 T-lymphocyte cells, which are part of the human immune reaction (Adler *et al.*, 2012, p.6). CD4 T-lymphocyte cells are responsible for helping other cells identify, destruct, and produce antibodies against foreign organisms such as viruses. If left untreated, HIV can develop into Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS),

which is diagnosed as a CD4 cell count lower than 200 cells/ml (Adler *et al.*, 2012, p.21). This low CD4 cell count compromises the human immune system, increasing the risk of opportunistic infections where otherwise harmless common viruses, fungi, bacteria or parasites cause disease. Examples include cancer, encephalopathy, chronic herpes simplex, Kaposi's sarcoma, recurrent pneumonia, toxoplasmosis, tuberculosis and weight loss (Adler *et al.*, 2012, p.21).

1.3 HIV incidence and prevalence

Since the 1980s, the incidence and prevalence of HIV had increased to substantial levels, becoming a significant public health issue due to scale, severity, transmission and treatment requirements (UNAIDS, 2017). Table 1.1 below shows the incidence and mortality of HIV and AIDS diagnoses and deaths over time globally, in the UK and in Scotland. As can be seen, the HIV epidemic rose sharply from the late 1980s until recent years. AIDS diagnosis and deaths subsequently fell in the mid-1990s and early 2000s as testing and treatment options improved.

Table 1.1: New HIV and AIDS diagnoses and deaths, by year of diagnosis, year of death and gender: all years to 2017

YEAR	GLOBAL			UK			SCOTLAND		
	HIV diagnoses	AIDS diagnoses	AIDS deaths	HIV	AIDS	AIDS deaths	HIV	AIDS	AIDS deaths
1988	No data	No data	No data	1,953	596	512	151	63	35
1989	No data	142,000	No data	2,181	650	778	122	63	53
1990	8,300,000	307,000	290,000	2,597	751	933	125	61	73
1995	19,100,000	1,000,000	820,000	2,934	806	1,716	141	50	169
2000	27,400 000	No data	1,500,000	3,989	624	481	138	30	49
2005	30,100,000	No data	1,900,000	7,865	737	587	311	40	52
2010	32,400,000	2,240,000	1,400,000	6,327	518	718	265	41	46
2015	36,700,000	2,200,000	1,000,000	6,043	335	527	263	9	46
2017	36,900,000	2,140,000	940,000	4,363	230	428	186	0	28

(UNAIDS, 2017 and Public Health England, 2020)

In the UK, around 101,600 of the total population, or 170 people per 100,000, have been diagnosed HIV positive. Today, 37 million people are living with HIV globally. Of these, 5,256 live in Scotland, which equates to 97 per 100,000 of the population (Public Health Scotland, 2019). In Scotland, GBMSM had accounted for 70% of cases of HIV reported since 2004; however, by 2019 only 47% of people with HIV in Scotland were GBMSM, with 39% heterosexual and 10% injecting drug users (Public Health Scotland, 2019). The mortality rate of HIV remains stable at roughly 631 per 100,000 of the population (Public Health England, 2020). Akinyemi, Omokhodion, Fasokun, *et al.*, (2023) suggested a link between HIV prevalence and deprivation in the USA where lack of access to healthcare, poor housing and drug use contribute to HIV transmission. However, as English and Scottish HIV incidence and prevalence epidemiological data is not collected by category or measure of deprivation, it is not possible to determine the same link in the UK at present (Public Health England, 2020; Public Health Scotland, 2019).

1.4 HIV stigma, power, inequality and activism

This section examines the theoretical underpinning of social norms, stigma and self-concept in relation to HIV. Becker (1963, p.8) defined stigma as people who are perceived as different to the social norm being seen as 'outsiders' from 'mainstream society'. Goffman (1963, p.12) explained how this led to a disapproving societal attitude towards the individual, reducing them to a tainted and discounted person. Stigmatised individuals internalise this to view themselves as discredited or undesirable, damaging their identity. Self-concept being determined by the perceived judgements of others is known as the Looking Glass Theory (Cooley, 1998, p. 20). Discrimination ensues because of stigma (Bem, 1967), which was evident in terms of the fatal AIDS epidemic of the 1980s, where it became clear that sections of society disapproved of homosexuality, infidelity, sex work and drug use (US Department of Health and Human Services, 2022). Applying moral judgement allowed the rationalisation that the person was at fault for contracting HIV/AIDS due to their irresponsible behaviour and therefore undeserving of empathy (Mbonu, van den Bourne, De Vries, 2009). For example, ministers in the USA preached sermons containing viewpoints such as 'AIDS is a lethal judgment of God...for endorsing this

vulgar, perverted and reprobate lifestyle' (Jonsen and Stryker, 1993) and 'retribution for a repulsive vice' (France, 2016, p.218). This American moral standpoint was reflected in the UK in terms of stigma in the media of the time, for example the UK Mail on Sunday newspaper reported 'Britain threatened by gay virus plague' in 1985 (Martin, Hilton and McDaid, 2013). It is likely that the issues around HIV stigma highlighted here were compounded and reinforced by the Sexual Offences Act which made homosexuality illegal in England until 1967 and in Scotland until legislation came into effect in 1981. Furthermore, thousands of UK gay men were convicted for offences such as 'gross indecency' after 1967 and the promotion of homosexuality was still criminalised until 2000 in Scotland and 2003 in England (Tatchell, 2017).

Stigma and discrimination can be broadened in relation to power, domination and control, where some groups such as the lower working class are excluded from certain settings leading to social inequality (Addison, 2023; Marmot, 2018; Parker and Aggleton, 2003). For example, UCAS (2021 p.17) explained how HIV stigma can affect education for UK GBMSM, with 42% of LGBT school pupils having been bullied and 47% university students targeted by others due to their sexuality. Similarly, Stonewall (2018, p.10) found that in the workplace, 18% of LGBT people were discriminated against when in and looking for employment due to their sexuality. Low levels of education and employment opportunity in high deprivation areas is a precursor to life chances and health (Audit Scotland, 2012). The benefits to health of higher levels of education are achieved via not only a higher income and better standard of living, but also increased health literacy and health seeking behaviours, leading to fewer co-morbidities and longer life expectancy (Public Health England, 2021). Consequently, HIV stigma and discrimination can exacerbate deprivation, poor education and other inequalities, affecting the availability, accessibility and uptake of PrEP for GBMSM (Dalrymple *et al.*, 2019; Coia *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, HIV stigma together with racism are barriers to PrEP for black African and Caribbean women in the UK, who have a low uptake of PrEP despite representing 42% of all new HIV infections among heterosexuals (Nakasone *et al.*, 2020). Stigma can also affect sexual health behaviours for GBMSM. Closson *et al.* (2018) found an association between lower socio-economic status, lower levels of education and risky sexual

health behaviours including condomless sex amongst GBMSM due to power imbalances, poor sexual health literacy and economic dependence.

Foucault considered the concepts of biopower, or governmental/societal power to control populations, for example, health promotion or risk regulation; and biopolitics, or how this power regulates individuals, such as politics and law (Adams, 2017). Foucault described social control to be exercised by social conformity rather than governmental control (Nutland, 2016; Parker and Aggleton, 2003; Sumartojo, 2000). However, Brisson, Ravitsky and Williams-Jones (2019) warned that this perception of individuals as 'docile bodies' frames GBMSM as passive and disempowered instruments of processes and ignores their agency and autonomy. In fact, GBMSM as a community in the 1980s commenced a wave of organised activism calling for a political response to the AIDS epidemic and mobilising health care staff and researchers to support and empower people with AIDS, spreading ideas for social change worldwide (Wright, 2013). Protests such as civil disobedience, marches and publications led to the idea of safe sex, improved funding for research and drug development and medicines regulation so that with treatment, people were able to live with HIV (Brown *et al.*, 1996). Nevertheless, HIV stigma still exists today. Beichler, Kutalek and Dorner (2023) documented experiences of rejection and fear of contagion affecting GBMSM with HIV. Similarly, Liboro *et al.* (2021) note that HIV stigma has consequences for HIV positive GBMSMs regarding their confidentiality, employment, elderly care and access to health care.

1.5 HIV policy initiatives

1.5.1 Global

To address the AIDS epidemic, the Joint United Nations Programme on AIDS (UNAIDS) was founded in 1996 to coordinate the response to HIV/AIDS globally by uniting the resources and actions of other UN organisations (WHO, 1997). Furthermore, the World Health Organisation (WHO) launched the Global Programme on AIDS in 1987 to assist with raising awareness, policy making and providing research and financial support to lower income countries (WHO, 1997). In 2001, the UN worked with the WHO to agree the Doha Declaration, allowing generic drug

manufacturers to produce HIV medication for developing countries at discounted cost as the price of anti-viral medication had remained high. Despite these initiatives, 2003 saw the greatest number of people infected with HIV in one year worldwide; consequently, the WHO announced the '3 by 5' initiative to bring HIV treatment to 3 million people by 2005 in developing countries (United Nations, 2018). This target was not reached as by December 2005 only 1.3 million people were receiving HIV treatment in these countries due to delays in funding and management issues. Nevertheless, the establishment of antiretroviral treatment worldwide in 2013 led to a comparative reduction in AIDS-related deaths (UNAIDS, 2015). In 2014, UNAIDS introduced the '90-90-90' worldwide targets which aimed for 90% of people living with HIV to be diagnosed, 90% to be accessing antiretroviral treatment and 90% of those to achieve viral suppression by 2020. These targets have been met in the UK (UNAIDS, 2017).

1.5.2 England

Public Health England and the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) have reported a recent decline of HIV diagnoses in some populations in England (Public Health England, 2020; NICE, 2016). However, they have recommended an increase in HIV screening at general practices and hospitals amongst disadvantaged populations of prisoners and injecting drug users to reduce the risk of undiagnosed HIV infection (Public Health England, 2020; NICE, 2016). The Kings Fund (Baylis *et al.*, 2017) contended that HIV prevention in England is hampered by budget cuts and the responsibilities for HIV treatment and services lack co-ordination by being divided across many organisations. Furthermore, in 2016/17 the UK government had cut spending on HIV prevention by 6.25% to £2.25 million (National AIDS Trust, 2016). In 2016, the NHS in England had declined to pay for a national programme of PrEP, arguing that it was a preventative therapy only. However, this decision was overturned in court when the National AIDS Trust successfully sued the NHS (Nash *et al.*, 2017). Consequently in 2017, a three-year trial of PrEP prescriptions was commenced across 200 sexual health clinics in England to 10,000 people at high risk of HIV. Later, in April 2021 PrEP became available for free in England from the NHS. The recent Towards Zero HIV action plan aims to

improve access to PrEP for groups of people experiencing health disparities and reduce new HIV infections in England by 80% by 2025 (Department of Health and Social Care, 2021).

1.5.3 Scotland

Local HIV policy in parts of Scotland had initially focused on law and social disorder involving injecting drug users rather than addressing vulnerabilities and public health strategies. For example, in 1983 the closure of a legal retailer of needles and syringes in Edinburgh and a subsequent unofficial prohibition of these items by pharmacists led to 51% of injecting drug users being found to be HIV positive (Robertson *et al.*, 1986). After being dubbed ‘The AIDS capital of Europe’ by the Sunday Times (McCarthy and Welsby, 2003), new health policy supplied oral methadone to replace street heroin, negating the need to inject and limiting HIV transmission (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland), 2021).

Currently, the Scottish Government’s Reset and Rebuild strategy post COVID-19 (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland), 2021) aims to improve prevention and treatment for HIV and other Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs) and empower people to take control of their own sexual health with appropriate, accessible services. The Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC) approved PrEP in April 2017 and it became available from Scottish NHS sexual health clinics in July 2017 without a pilot trial. Although Wales followed with NHS PrEP soon afterwards, Scotland was the first country in the UK to provide PrEP nationally and free of charge (Brady *et al.*, 2019). In November 2017, NHS Scotland was able to successfully commission generic PrEP medication rather than branded at significant cost savings with prices dropping from £355 to under £50 per month (Public Health Scotland, 2019). Appendix 1 outlines the eligibility criteria for the prescribing of NHS-funded PrEP in Scotland, which is based on the British Association of Sexual Health and HIV (BASHH) guidelines (Brady *et al.*, 2019). BASHH is a UK wide specialist professional organisation who provide best practice evidence-based research and guidelines for sexual health. To obtain PrEP from NHS Scotland, an individual must attend the clinic every three months for a sexual health screen and monitoring and be at high risk of contracting HIV which is

determined by their sexual risk behaviours. In practice individuals in Scotland eligible for PrEP are mostly GBMSM but also include very small numbers of injecting drug users and heterosexual men and women who have partners with untreated HIV (Brady *et al.*, 2019).

1.6 HIV treatment

Antiretroviral treatments inhibit or stop different parts of the life cycle of HIV (Adler *et al.*, 2012, p.97). Early diagnosis of HIV and significant improvements in antiretroviral treatments over recent times have led to HIV infection having very little impact on life expectancy in the UK (Ong *et al.*, 2019). Nevertheless, the Kings Fund (Baylis *et al.*, 2017) noted that as people living with HIV age they are likely to experience additional co-morbidities. McGettigan *et al.* (2022) found that from 2008 to 2015, the percentage of HIV positive people in England living in areas of high deprivation increased remarkably from 12.4% to 52.6%. It was thought that as people living with HIV age and co-morbidities increase, employment opportunities and economic status suffer. Socio-economic disadvantage had also been associated with higher morbidity for people with living with COVID-19 (Bhaskaran *et al.*, 2021).

HIV treatments are estimated to cost between £70,000 and £200,000 per person per lifetime depending on if the medication is generic as opposed to named brands, which tend to be more expensive (Ong *et al.*, 2019). Appendix 2 provides a brief overview of HIV testing and treatments over time demonstrating how HIV prevention and patient outcomes have progressed. Advances in HIV treatments and the discovery that people with HIV who are virally suppressed are not able to sexually transmit the virus to others has been ground-breaking in terms of their personal lives and influencing wider public opinion (Calabrese and Mayer, 2019).

Recent substantial increases in HIV screening have also led to a drop in undiagnosed infection and faster treatment at diagnosis has also reduced onwards transmission of HIV (Palfreeman *et al.*, 2020; Brown *et al.*, 2017). Previous and current HIV prevention strategies and programs in the UK had focussed on behaviour change such as condom use, serosorting (using HIV status of partner to decide sexual behaviour) and

regular HIV testing for early diagnosis (Young, Flowers and McDaid, 2015). Many GBMSMs also utilise strategies such as avoiding partners who 'appear' to have HIV or not taking part in 'risky' sexual practices, suggesting that HIV risk perception may be affected by HIV stigma (Young, Flowers and McDaid, 2015). However, Nutland (2016) added that some GBMSM demonstrate a flawed risk analysis of their chance of HIV acquisition.

1.6.1 Establishment of PrEP

Despite these HIV prevention strategies, condomless sex between GBMSM continued to be the main way in which new HIV infections are acquired in the UK (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland), 2021). Multiple reasons as to why GBMSM may have condomless sex have been identified in the literature. Jacobs, Kane and Ownby (2012) found that sensation seeking, Viagra use, 'safe sex' fatigue/reduced concern about HIV and alcohol/drugs are reasons for condomless sex. Furthermore, Stack *et al.* (2016) observed that having unplanned unprotected sex is more likely in a monogamous relationship, at a younger age, lower educational level, or if engaging in group sex or sex for money. Nevertheless, Lim, *et al.* (2012) observed that these reasons can be confounded by other variables such as the need to feel physically attractive and social marginalisation within the gay community. Jacobs, Kane and Ownby (2012) concurred, suggesting that mainstream gay culture emphasizes youth, and some older men can feel unattractive and under pressure to have unprotected sex as an alternative to rejection by potential partners. Coia *et al.* (2014) added that GBMSM who report low self-esteem and loneliness often lacked the confidence, skills or assertiveness to negotiate what they wanted from sexual encounters and define their own boundaries.

The development of PrEP extends to preceding research by Henderson and Gerberding (1989) who had learned that antiretroviral medication can block the HIV virus from infecting immune system cells. Cardo *et al.* (1997) showed that prompt antiretroviral treatment provided an 81% reduction in the risk of HIV transmission amongst healthcare workers with needlestick injuries in the USA. Consequently, antiretroviral treatment known as Post-Exposure Prophylaxis to Sexual Exposure of

HIV (PEPSE) became available in the UK in the early 2000s (Brady *et al.*, 2019). Following on from this, it was suggested that HIV medication may also be able to reduce the incidence of HIV transmission before risk exposure as well as afterwards. Molina *et al.* (2015) and McCormack *et al.* (2016) randomised controlled trials (RCTs) suggested the current formulation of two antiretroviral drugs, Emtricitabine and Tenofovir (PrEP), were 86% effective in the prevention of HIV transmission. These RCTs together with a cost benefit analysis informed the SMC decision to provide a public health program of NHS PrEP in Scotland to be rolled out fully without the requirement for an initial trial or pilot (SMC, 2017). PrEP can be taken either as a continuous daily dose or 'event-based' regimen; or the more flexible option of taking it only at the time of a planned sexual risk (Molina *et al.*, 2015).

Today, Public Health Scotland (2023) have indicated that PrEP prescribing has exceeded estimates of 1000 people per year to an average of 190 per month. 93% of those prescribed PrEP were GBMSM and most were eligible for PrEP due to reporting unprotected anal sex with multiple partners. Efficacy has been high, with the risk of HIV for Scottish GBMSM being reduced by 75% for those prescribed PrEP at least once and 32% lower for those not prescribed PrEP, suggesting a contribution to the population-level reduction in HIV incidence (Estcourt *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, Public Health Scotland (2019, p.14) stated that the PrEP eligibility criteria has 'the potential to widen inequalities in health and the intervention, for example, might disproportionately benefit those GBMSM who were better educated and/or from more affluent backgrounds'. This statement substantiates the rationale for this study.

1.6.2 Clinical organisational change, the nurse role and PrEP

The organisational alterations to sexual health services that were required to deliver the additional PrEP services in Scotland were a challenge, and included staff training, new protocols, leaflets and updates to technological systems and reporting (Public Health Scotland, 2019). Sexual health services were already facing increasing rates of STIs and economic challenges; however financial resources were not provided for these additional service costs. The standard appointment time of 20 minutes was found to be insufficient to address PrEP assessment, health promotion and sexual

health needs whilst maintaining patient care. The high number of individuals starting PrEP combined with those already taking it led to an exacerbation of pressure on services (Public Health Scotland, 2019).

PrEP is prescribed in clinic by doctors and nurses. Patient assessment, decision making and prescribing medications are skills that used to be the responsibility of medical staff rather than nurses (Baid *et al.*, 2009 and Legare *et al.*, 2011). Policies and guidelines such as Modernising Nursing Careers (Department of Health, 2006), the Nursing and Midwifery Strategy: 2011-2014 (NHS Education for Scotland, 2011) and the Nursing 2030 Vision (Chief Nursing Officer Directorate, 2017) resulted in expansion of the role of the nurse in the UK. Nurses and midwives in the UK are regulated by the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC), who set the standards of education, training, performance and conduct to maintain their registration (NMC, 2018). Nurse prescribing of PrEP fits with the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) Code (2018) in terms of meeting patient needs, evidence-based practice, preventing ill-health and patient safety. Nurse prescribing provides an equivalent level of care to doctors at less cost (Chief Nursing Officer Directorate, 2017). However, despite increasing the scope of their role, research by Scheffer *et al.* (2019) suggested that nurses in the UK do not consequently feel able to address health inequalities or impact on population health for patients living in poverty.

1.7 Barriers to accessing sexual health services

Flowers, Duncan and Knussen (2003) had identified a wide range of barriers to accessing sexual health services for GBMSM including concerns about discrimination at clinics, stigma, young age, perceptions of HIV risk and not testing for HIV before. Flowers, *et al.* (2013) found ten years later that although more men were testing for HIV, barriers remained such as fear of a positive result, accessibility of clinics and attitudes to HIV positive men. Testing for STIs was also impeded by concerns around confidentiality, disclosing sexuality (Mimiaga *et al.*, 2007) and assuming that infections were symptomatic (Schmidt and Marcus, 2011). Barriers to the accessibility of clinic services included inconvenient opening hours, conflicts with work schedules, travel distance and the time required to attend which included the financial cost of attending

clinics (Lea *et al.*, 2019). Facilitators to accessing sexual health services were a higher level of education and social marketing campaigns (Flowers, *et al.*, 2013). Frankis *et al.* (2016) concurred that higher levels of education, frequent HIV testing and proximity to health promotion initiatives are linked to better sexual health literacy.

Similar barriers to HIV testing for younger Scottish GBMSM have also been identified, with additional concerns such as missing school, depending on parents for transport, assumptions of heterosexuality by clinic staff and limited knowledge of STIs (Dalrymple *et al.*, 2019; Cassidy *et al.*, 2018; Bender and Fulbright, 2013). Young GBMSM tended to gain their sexual health knowledge from the internet, pornography, friends and their own experiences, rather than from sex education in schools (Coia *et al.*, 2014). Patterson *et al.* (2020) argued that sex education in Scottish schools is often inadequate as it remains bounded by social class, power and politics, with schools tending to explain outcomes of risky sexual behaviours without imparting the practical facts and advice necessary to mitigate these risks. Sexual issues, communication and emotions are often not discussed openly, leading to stigma, anxiety and perceptions of sex as 'taboo' (Coia, *et al.*, 2014). A moralistic negative culture around sexual health is reinforced with sex between men being shameful, disgusting or unmanly (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Consequently, younger Scottish GBMSM were often poorly informed about HIV risk and unprepared for positive relationships, leading to risky sexual health behaviours with less likelihood of attending sexual health services (Coia *et al.*, 2014). Ezhova *et al.* (2020) added that this stigma toward sexual orientation was one of the largest barriers to acceptability of sexual health services in older age too, with older GBMSM representing a hidden population who are absent from government policies and sexual health promotions.

Cultural barriers to the acceptability and accessibility of sexual health services also exist for GBMSM. For example, Kaczowski and Swartout (2019) found that young refugees, particularly men, had limited or incorrect knowledge of STIs and sexual health clinics and felt shame and embarrassment when talking about sexual health. Lack of money, transport and confidentiality were also specific concerns (Kaczowski and Swartout, 2019). Sometimes GBMSM from other cultures retreat from cultural norms, for example in Asian cultures GBMSM can experience difficulties around

religions and the expectation of marriage to a female partner (Hart *et al.*, 2023). Similar findings can also be seen in the Black community as families sometimes follow a very conservative form of Protestantism (Lassiter, Brewer and Wilton, 2019). Additionally, Scottish gay, lesbian and bisexual people experience poorer mental and physical health than the heterosexual population; and are more likely to smoke, drink alcohol and take drugs (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Unstable or no employment and poverty can be both causes and consequences of mental health problems (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Added vulnerabilities for adults can increase the risk of poor self-care, not prioritising sexual health and present challenges to accessing health services (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). For example, drug use and insecure housing deplete the financial and emotional resources people need to physically attend clinics (Edelman *et al.*, 2013).

Social categories such as deprivation, ethnic background, culture and sexuality are described in the concept of intersectionality (Scottish Government, 2022). Here, the interaction of two or more of these social categories where systems are connected within structures of power (e.g., government, policy, law) cause power and structural inequalities reflected as relative disadvantage. Although the application of intersectionality to policymaking and analysis can identify barriers to accessing health services, an intersectional approach is rarely taken and there is a lack of intersectional data on outcomes in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2022).

1.8 Deprivation and the Inverse Care Law

The Scottish Government recognises the ongoing problem of widening health inequalities between the least and most educated, wealthy and housed in Scotland (Scottish Government National Statistics, 2021). Deprivation has been found to be the one key determinant of health inequalities (Audit Scotland, 2012). Causes of deprivation have been identified as low income and economic disadvantage, low educational attainment, poor housing, poor transport links and industrial decline affecting work and environment (Scottish Government National Statistics, 2021). The area chosen for this study, the West of Scotland and its surrounding areas, has the highest level of deprivation in Scotland (Scottish Government National Statistics,

2021). People from more deprived areas tend to have poorer access to health services and poorer health outcomes (Scottish Parliament Health and Sport Committee, 2015). This is known as the 'Inverse Care Law', where the availability of good medical care varies conversely with population need (Watt, 2002). Current employment patterns of temporary work, zero-hours contracts or low paid, low-status work together with current welfare reform is reducing the income available to the most vulnerable and poorest families and individuals (Buck *et al.*, 2018; Population Health Directorate (Scotland), 2017). Austerity has adversely affected the social determinants that impact on health such as a decline in funding for education, a rise in homelessness and foodbanks and a housing affordability crisis (Institute of Health Equity, 2020). Furthermore, lesbian, gay and bisexual people in Scotland experience higher unemployment than their heterosexual counterparts (Stonewall, 2018, p.10).

Sexual health outcomes are not discrete from these patterns of general health in Scotland. The Population Health Directorate (Scotland) (2021) notes that deprivation has a particularly negative influence on the diagnosis of STIs, risk-taking behaviours and positive sexual wellbeing. GBMSM are particularly at risk of negative outcomes such as STIs where there is evidence of stigma, discrimination and low uptake/late access to services (Official Statistics (Scotland) (2017). Furthermore, McDaid *et al.* (2019) and Lorimer *et al.* (2018) confirmed links between low socio-economic status, poor sexual health and high-risk sexual behaviours in Scotland, where deprivation is a factor of disadvantage.

1.9 Rationale for the study and research aim

This chapter demonstrates how deprivation, defined as an unequal distribution of income, power and wealth is a driver of poverty and, together with the current cost of living crisis and inverse care law, can negatively affect health outcomes (Population Health Directorate (Scotland), 2017). Living in areas of high deprivation exacerbates the effects of insecure employment, poor education and health inequalities such as vulnerabilities for Scottish GBMSM (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Scottish GBMSM also face barriers to PrEP accessibility and acceptability including engaging with sexual health services (Flowers *et al.*, 2013). Factors such as inadequate sex

education in schools can inhibit HIV literacy (Patterson *et al.*, 2019) and economic insecurity has been shown to affect medications adherence and sexual health behaviours (Closson *et al.*, 2018). Morgan *et al.* (2018) explained how people with higher socio economic status are likely to have more resources to be informed of and access new health technologies such as PrEP; and this corresponds to the author's experience of working as an advanced practitioner in PrEP clinics in Scotland.

The efficacy and success of PrEP for HIV prevention is well established (Estcourt *et al.*, 2021), nevertheless inequalities in the social determinants of health are threats to the right to health for GBMSM (Public Health Scotland, 2019). Little is known about the relationship between deprivation and uptake of PrEP for Scottish GBMSM, therefore this doctoral study will explore the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation to assess the realisation of PrEP for this population. WHO (2017) stated that health services should be available, accessible, acceptable to all and of good quality to address inequalities, which corresponds to the Scottish Government ambition for available accessible healthcare (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland), 2021). Furthermore, healthcare does not involve one aspect of care but should be considered in terms of the entire sequence of events that a person experiences when accessing services, treatments and interventions (WHO, 2017). These elements reflect the PrEP 'Care Continuum', or steps that the service user moves through to be aware of, commence and adhere to PrEP (Nunn, *et al.*, 2017). Hence the research aim for this study is to understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP.

1.10 Structure of the thesis

Chapter one has provided a chronological background to the HIV and AIDS epidemic; including stigma, subsequent HIV activism and policy and treatment initiatives. Context to the introduction of PrEP medication to healthcare is established. Deprivation and the rationale for the study are addressed and the research aim outlined.

Chapter two; the literature review defines the literature search, demonstrating a critical overview of the current evidence on the principal concepts of PrEP provision. The effects of health inequalities on the acceptability, accessibility and continuation of PrEP are explored, concluding with an overview of current research and the aim and objectives of this study.

Chapter three, the conceptual framework, demonstrates the relationship between the concepts related to PrEP provision and uptake utilising a rights to healthcare approach.

Chapter four establishes the design and methodology used in the study; detailing the evaluation and appraisal of research methods and why the approach employed was deemed to be the most appropriate. Ethical considerations, rigour and trustworthiness are addressed.

Chapter five presents the qualitative key findings and themes of this study, exploring the GBMSM participants lived experience of accessing and taking PrEP medication.

Chapter six explores and classifies these key findings in dialogue with the wider literature, identifying emergent and developing themes and revisiting the conceptual framework.

Chapter seven discusses the strengths and limitations of the study, followed by recommendations for policy and further research. Finally, the conclusions are presented.

Chapter two: Literature review

2.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses the evidence base to determine what is known about the topic to lay a foundation for new study (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.91; Polit and Beck, 2020, p.170). The aim of this literature review is determined by the research aim which is to understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. This will include awareness, availability, access, acceptability, uptake and continuation of PREP together with outcomes such as changes to sexual behaviours. This chapter will outline the literature search and provide an objective, systematic summary and critical analysis of the available literature pertaining to the topic (Hart, 2018, p.3). Key studies, debates, findings and gaps in the knowledge will be identified to inform the development of the research aim and objectives (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.28; Polit and Beck, 2020, p.170) and plan the study framework and methodology (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.94).

2.2 Hierarchy of evidence and critical appraisal

Sackett *et al.* (1996) proposed that evidence-based practice is obtained by the best external evidence from systematic research together with clinical expertise. 'Hierarchies of evidence' are often used to assess the strength and quality/precision of research, with systematic reviews ranked uppermost, followed by individual randomised controlled trials (RCTs), quasi-experiments, observational studies and finally expert opinions (Rees, Beecroft and Booth, 2015, p.108; Gao Smith *et al.*, 2006). However, the hierarchical approach has been criticised for not considering the quality of the studies and consensus is difficult due to issues such as conflicting findings or varying sampling methods (Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.108, Parahoo, 2014, p. 226).

Systematic reviews are seen as a superior form of research particularly in medicine as they use precision, leave an audit trail and are deemed to be objective (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.39; Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.100). Systematic reviews are considered the most transparent, precise and least biased way to summarise the

largest amount of qualitative research, using narrative integration rather than statistical methods to identify, synthesise and appraise findings from individual studies (Rees, Beecroft and Booth, 2015, p.115; Dixon-Woods *et al.*, 2006; Moynihan, 2004). Rigorous methodological standards, explicit search and inclusion criteria and formal evaluation instruments aim to screen out studies of low quality (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.39; Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.115; Moynihan, 2004). However, the merit of the review relies on the quality of the studies contained within and similar research questions and consistency of evidence are required to avoid bias (Mueller *et al.*, 2013; Merlin, Weston and Tooher, 2009).

Much of the evidence available regarding PrEP has been undertaken using individual deductive RCTs with measured numerical data and cause and effect. RCTs reduce selection and observer bias and often have larger sample sizes or powering, which adds rigour and trustworthiness (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.226). However, there may be limitations and bias within RCT designs and true experiments are not always practical in healthcare due to ethical, clinical or organisational reasons (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.118). Observational studies such as cohort, cross-sectional and case controls have been assigned a lower quality grading in the hierarchy of evidence as they lack experimental rigour, however they can be elevated in rank if the treatment effect is significant and the results not explained by other potential biases (Guyatt *et al.*, 2008).

Qualitative studies are included to provide depth and breadth around the topic of the patient experience of taking PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. Qualitative research fits with the research aim in this study as it is widely agreed in the literature that qualitative research explores individual interactions, experiences and meanings (Polgar, 2019, p.12; Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.3; Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.104).

Critical appraisal tools were used to analyse and evaluate the quality of the evidence in the studies identified in this literature search (Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.105; Kattrak *et al.*, 2004). NHS Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP; NICE, 2020) tools were chosen as they are specifically designed for evidence in healthcare (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.52; Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.109). The CASP tool

provides a standardised, explicit means of assessing internal and external validity which addresses aspects such as reliability, validity, bias and generalisability (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.52; Rees, Beecroft, and Booth, 2015, p.109). The specific CASP tool was applied to each study after all were obtained to preclude bias and each study was scored as to whether it met the criteria in the tool. For each criterion, the study was evaluated and rated by answering “yes”, “no” or “can’t tell”. If the study met the criterion (denoting “yes”) it scored 1, if the criterion was not met (denoting “no”) the study scored 0 and if there was uncertainty or only some relevance to the criterion (denoting “can’t tell”) the study scored 0.5 (Smith *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, qualitative studies scored from 1-10, cohort studies from 0-12 and RCTs from 0-11. This appraisal highlighted methodological issues in each study, leading to the classification of studies as “weak” (score <5), “fair” (score 5-8) or “good” (score >8) (Long, French and Brooks, 2020). No articles were classed as “weak”. A quality assessment of the evidence included in this thesis is presented in Appendix 6.

2.3 Literature review

Polit and Beck (2020, p.170) explained how approaches to literature reviews vary, with grounded theory researchers collecting data before the literature review in contrast to phenomenologists and ethnographers who conduct the literature review first to inform the study. Robson and McCartan (2016, p.56) and Cresswell and Cresswell (2018, p.28) described different types of literature reviews such as methodological, historical or mixed methods. Systematic reviews provide the most comprehensive surveys of the literature with the least systemic error; however, they require funding, a team of researchers and are time consuming (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.93), and so outside the scope of this doctorate. Traditional literature reviews are generally narrative, comparing recent and current research and integrating both quantitative and qualitative evidence (Smith and Noble, 2016). A narrative literature review provides an agenda for further research by considering an extensive range of key sources and providing critique, leading to a detailed view of the topic (Dekkers, Carey and Langhorne, 2022, p.38). Narrative reviews that are systematic in approach fit with an interpretivist paradigm and are useful for exploring topics that are under-researched

or complex, requiring nuanced description and interpretation (Sukhera, 2022). Therefore, a systematic narrative review was considered suitable for this study as diverse sources of information will be useful to address the research aim of understanding the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP and the PrEP 'care continuum' (Nunn *et al.*, 2017). Narrative literature reviews have been criticised for being incomplete or not explicit regarding search criteria (David and Sutton, 2011, p.64); nevertheless, the diversity contained within the construction of narrative reviews can provide a good comparison between the outcomes of similar studies (Sukhera, 2022). Therefore, this review aims to replicate a systematic structured approach to searching and critiquing the literature by utilising the principles and guidelines of a systematic review for thoroughness and reduction of inclination to bias (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.173). Literature reviews can be organised utilising various principals, such as chronological, methodological or by transferability (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.79). However, a thematic organisation was chosen for this literature review as this approach lends itself to consider the varied range of subject areas relevant to PrEP, integrating both quantitative and qualitative evidence (Smith and Noble, 2016).

2.4 Search strategy

Electronic online bibliographic databases are the preferred option for accessing the literature as they are reliable, accurate and provide the largest number of abstracts, journal articles and books (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.96). EBSCOhost databases CINAHL, MEDLINE and Nursing Academic Edition were searched as it is widely acknowledged that they contain the best available evidence regarding nursing and medicine (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.100; Beecroft, Booth and Rees, 2015, p.90; Polit and Beck, 2020, p.175). Additionally, Science Direct, Pubmed, Taylor and Francis Online, Wiley Online Library, SpringerLink, Sage Journals and Web of Science were searched to capture the varied range of subject areas relevant to PrEP (Kamitani *et al.*, 2019).

To launch the search, the keywords were identified by inputting the core search terms into the Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) database (David and Sutton, 2011, p.62;

Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.54). As the aim of this literature review is to understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP and the PrEP 'care continuum', the search formula consisted of the core search terms/keywords of 'Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis' 'GBMSM' and 'Deprivation'. Keywords to identify PrEP medication were 'PrEP', 'Pre-exposure prophylaxis', 'Pre exposure prophylaxis' and 'Preexposure prophylaxis'. Keywords to identify GBMSM were 'GBMSM', 'MSM', 'men who have sex with men', 'homosexual', 'gay', 'bisexual' and 'LGBT'. Keywords to identify deprivation were 'deprivation', 'deprived', 'socio economic', 'low income', 'poor', 'poverty' and 'inequality'. The Boolean operator 'OR' widened the search so that all keywords were included then 'AND' narrowed the search so that at least one keyword relating to PrEP, GBMSM and deprivation was present in the material searched as part of the systematic approach (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.175; Beecroft, Booth and Rees, 2015, p.96; David and Sutton, 2011, p.60). Truncation was used for keywords with the same root but a potentially different ending, therefore wildcard characters to stand in for an unknown character were not required (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.175). See Appendix 3 for detail of keywords, delineators and truncation used. The search was originally undertaken in August 2019 and updated in May 2023 to include subsequent research. Inclusion criteria required research articles to be available in English and be published from 2007 to the present day (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.177; Beecroft, Booth and Rees, 2015, p.99). Studies prior to 2007 were excluded because Emtricitabine and Tenofovir disoproxil had not been established as a preventative treatment for HIV before this time (Karim *et al.*, 2010) (see section 1.6.1). Details of the search strategy are outlined in Appendix 4 using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) checklist (Page *et al.*, 2021).

Following the database searches, all titles were screened and abstracts of each article, book or report were evaluated to identify the population, aim and intervention (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.183; Beecroft, Booth and Rees, 2015, p.101). Screening titles could potentially miss relevant materials so the abstract was also read if the title was ambiguous. Inclusion criteria for screening were studies regarding HIV PrEP medication specifically and studies regarding the population of GBMSM; hence studies regarding non-GBMSM populations were excluded. Inclusion criteria for screening

also required studies to be related to deprivation, poverty or inequality (Population Health Directorate (Scotland), 2017). To define deprivation, the Scottish Government criteria of income, employment, education, health, access to services, crime and housing was used (Public Health Scotland, 2020). Therefore, at least one these inclusion criteria were required for screening to denote socio-economic status (see Chapter one, sections 1.7 and 1.8). Screening included articles where a subsection of the research related to the inclusion criteria and the findings could be extracted separately. To complete the screening, the remaining studies were read in full to assess for eligibility for inclusion in the literature review. To further increase the precision and sensitivity of this literature search, the articles identified were hand searched by examining the citations of key papers on the Web of Science database and checking their reference lists (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.54). Finally, Google Scholar was checked with the keywords identified above to ensure that no articles had been missed. No new articles were revealed.

After the removal of duplicate records, 1189 articles around PrEP, GBMSM and deprivation were retrieved and screened. Reasons for exclusion were studies of non-GBMSM populations, studies not regarding PrEP or deprivation and studies in locations where free PrEP had not been introduced in contrast to NHS services. 38 articles fitted the inclusion criteria and 11 articles were included in the literature review as they specifically addressed GBMSMs living in areas of deprivation who were taking free PrEP. The 11 original papers reported on individual studies, which from a hierarchical perspective included one RCT, two qualitative and the remainder quantitative cross sectional studies. Two took place in England however the majority originated in the USA. Characteristics of the studies included in the literature review are provided in Appendix 5.

2.5 Narrative literature review

The themes for this narrative literature review derived from the research aim, PrEP 'care continuum' (Nunn *et al.*, 2017) and the volume of evidence found for each theme. The selected papers were thematically analysed for similarities and differences and grouped into topics. Themes were GBMSM experience of deprivation and uptake of PrEP in terms of poverty and education, barriers and facilitators to uptake, adherence and continuation of PrEP and sexual risk compensation. Psychosocial perspectives for each theme were also identified. These themes informed development of the research objectives.

2.5.1 GBMSM experiences of socio-economic status, poverty and uptake of PrEP

The USA was the first country to approve Emtricitabine/Tenofovir for use as PrEP in 2012; therefore much of the study around PrEP has taken place there. Reyniers *et al.* (2017) discovered that groups at greatest risk of HIV in the USA were underrepresented largely due to health inequalities and access issues. Consequently, PrEP has been criticised as a 'boutique intervention' where people who can afford to pay for PrEP are receiving it yet vulnerable populations at high risk of HIV are not; reflecting the Inverse Care Law discussed in section 1.8 (Auerbach and Hoppe, 2015). It has been established in chapter one that deprivation is a key social driver that impacts on health inequality (see section 1.8), however, research on the uptake of PrEP outside of trial settings remains limited (Young, Flowers and McDaid, 2015).

Dehlin *et al.* (2019) research used a quantitative cross sectional design to study 150 young Black GBMSM in Chicago using neighbourhood poverty levels to measure socio-economic status. Area level income is also one of the criteria for measurement of deprivation in Scotland (Public Health Scotland, 2020) (see section 1.8). Multivariate analysis of the sample in Dehlin *et al.* (2019) determined which demographic variables were significantly associated with making an appointment for PrEP via the PrEPline telephone support programme but not actually initiating it. Many of the sample were referred internally, which could introduce sample bias towards successfully initiating PrEP (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.187).

Nevertheless, Dehlin *et al.* (2019) found that GBMSM were less likely to initiate free PrEP if they lived in areas where over 30% of the community were below the US poverty level in comparison to areas with less poverty. The neighbourhoods with higher poverty were in the West side of Chicago, where historical racial segregation and systemic housing discrimination had exacerbated inequalities for young Black GBMSM, who have a disproportionately high risk of HIV yet a low uptake of PrEP. Dehlin, *et al.* (2019) were able to demonstrate that living in a low income neighbourhood was a structural barrier to access to PrEP for Black GBMSM who experienced racism, lack of access to healthcare, few providers of PrEP and lack of awareness/financial resources.

Similar results were demonstrated in Burns *et al.* (2021) quantitative cross sectional research, which also focussed on neighbourhood level poverty as a structural barrier to uptake of PrEP for Black GBMSM in the USA south. The purposive sample of 142 was recruited from a larger HIV prevention intervention in Mississippi, which has a high incidence of HIV particularly amongst Black GBMSM. Burns *et al.* (2021) used the Andersen Model of Health Utilisation to provide a framework to identify social and structural factors potentially affecting PrEP uptake, which included environmental factors such as poverty, socio-demographic factors and individual resources. A computer survey and multi-level logistic regression were used to analyse the results at individual and neighbourhood levels, although careful purposive sampling is required to ensure the sample is representative of the population to reduce bias (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.312). The results demonstrated that older Black GBMSM in insecure housing were less likely to use PrEP, as were participants experiencing homelessness in the last year, suggesting that housing is a structural barrier to PrEP. Burns *et al.* (2021) concurred with Dehlin *et al.* (2019) in that poverty rates specifically influenced PrEP uptake on a neighbourhood level. Burns *et al.* (2021) summarised that geographic concentrations of poverty contribute to neighbourhood structural disadvantage which negatively impacts on PrEP uptake for Black GBMSM in the USA south. Racism, lack of employment and disparities in health services exacerbate an unequal distribution of power relations and resources for this population (Burns *et al.*, 2021).

Burns *et al.* (2021) also found that improved HIV literacy and recent incarceration increased the likelihood of PrEP uptake. The suggestion in Burns *et al.* (2021) that incarceration as an adverse life experience may be a motivation to use HIV prevention is contrary to that in other studies such as Ransome *et al.* (2020) where incarceration is negatively associated with the uptake of PrEP. Yang, Matthews and Shoff (2011) suggested that the prevalence of issues such as discrimination or incarceration rates within a given area can generate community norms such as distrust of governmental organisations and healthcare, which may in turn diminish acceptability of free PrEP.

Individual income levels are also linked to health inequalities (Buck, *et al.*, 2018). Blashill *et al.* (2019) investigated individual income level as one of a number of social, cultural and health factors as potential barriers to the PrEP Care Cascade amongst 151 Latino GBMSM in California. Latino GBMSM in the USA are also at disproportionately high risk of HIV together with a low uptake of PrEP. Blashill *et al.* (2019) quantitative cross sectional survey analysed structural and psychological variables separately as predictors for the stages of PrEP awareness, willingness, uptake and adherence using logistic regression models. Blashill *et al.* (2019) found that each structural factor/variable of income, housing, incarceration and the psychosocial factors of depression, alcohol/drug use, violence and past sexual abuse were all associated with lower PrEP awareness and use. When analysed for effect, structural barriers such as housing impaired awareness of PrEP but not willingness to use it; however once the participant had started to take PrEP, psychosocial indicators such as drug use negatively affected adherence to PrEP. This is a cross sectional study of a population at a particular point in time and cannot measure change so cannot sustain causal analysis (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.267). Nevertheless, this study provides further evidence that GBMSM experiences of wider structural factors such as income, housing and incarceration are impacting on their access to and utilisation of PrEP, which is significant regarding the research aim in this study.

2.5.2 GBMSM experiences of socio-economic status, education and uptake of PrEP

Garcia and Saw (2019) explored whether individual income and education levels were barriers to PrEP uptake for Latino GBMSM in Texas. A convenience sample of 154 Latino GBMSM were recruited to a quantitative cross-sectional online survey with multiple regression data analyses. Results demonstrated that participants with higher education levels and income were more likely to be aware of and take PrEP. Participants with less education and income were less likely to take PrEP, reporting concerns about side effects and medication safety due to mistrust of the state and healthcare (Garcia and Saw, 2019). Mistrust of healthcare providers regarding PrEP has been found in the wider literature (Ransome *et al.* 2020). Garcia and Saw (2019) suggested that Latino GBMSM with lower income and education had less access to health insurance and healthcare. Nunn *et al.* (2017) explained that to obtain PrEP in the USA, individuals require a medical provider who prescribes PrEP and their health insurance may not cover the costs of associated medications, provider fees or laboratory tests. Additionally, GBMSM in Texas are not protected by law and may face lower socio-economic status and health disparities due to stigma and discrimination. Garcia and Saw (2019) may not be generalisable to GBMSM in the UK who have access to free NHS healthcare and are protected by law from discrimination due to their sexuality (Tatchell, 2017). Nevertheless, the experiences of GBMSM in Garcia and Saw (2019) demonstrated again that structural factors such as stigma and discrimination and individual income and education impact on the accessibility and uptake of PrEP for this population.

Inequalities around the intersectionality of race, ethnicity, sexuality and deprivation experienced by the Black and Latino American GBMSM in the USA studies above are unlikely to be experienced in the same way compared to the majority white population of Scottish GBMSM; thus affecting generalisability (Edwards *et al.*, 2017). As the influence of race in these American studies is not separate from that of deprivation, the effect of inequality due to deprivation alone on PrEP uptake has not been identified (Nakasone *et al.*, 2020). Accordingly, Jaspal *et al.* (2019) study was a cross-sectional survey of 191 GBMSM in the UK to determine whether individuals with lower individual

income and lesser educational qualifications would have less HIV knowledge, therefore being less aware of their risk of HIV and consequently less likely to access PrEP. Jaspal *et al.* (2019) chose a sample from Leicester due to double the national average of HIV diagnoses. Participants were recruited from a social networking application to an online survey about sexual health risk taking with Kruskal–Wallis tests used for data analysis where demographic data was the independent variable and HIV knowledge and PrEP acceptability were dependent variables. Results demonstrated that respondents educated to the level of General Certificate of Secondary Education had statistically significantly less understanding of HIV than those educated to postgraduate level. Similarly, respondents with an annual income of below £10,000 demonstrated statistically significantly less knowledge of HIV and frequency of testing than higher income groups. A structural equation model demonstrated that socio-economic inequalities impacted negatively on HIV knowledge and HIV testing, and consequently on PrEP acceptability (Jaspal *et al.*, 2019). Jaspal *et al.* (2019) used a non-probability opportunity sample which Polit and Beck (2020, p.319) describe as ‘weak’ as the sample may not be representative of the population and Kruskal-Wallis testing relies on samples being random and independent (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.660). Nevertheless, other studies such as Holloway *et al.* (2017) in the USA have found supplemental results in their research suggesting that PrEP use may be associated with a higher income amongst GBMSM, and Wang *et al.* (2022) in the Netherlands suggest PrEP acceptability and uptake is linked to higher education.

Further barriers and facilitators to PrEP awareness, acceptability, accessibility and uptake for GBMSM have been identified in the literature. Golub *et al.* (2013) carried out a quantitative cross-sectional survey aiming to identify barriers and facilitators to PrEP acceptability, accessibility and motivations for adherence for 177 GBMSM in New York who were at risk of HIV. The association between perceived barriers and facilitators to PrEP was quantified by multivariable logistic regression and linear regression was used to test and predict the value of the effect of PrEP acceptability on adherence (Seale, 1999; Nelson, Dumville and Torgerson, 2015, p.260 and Lathlean, 2015). Results from Golub *et al.* (2013) found PrEP acceptable particularly if the medication was free and HIV testing and sexual health care were available

without going to a regular doctor. Key barriers to PrEP acceptability were concerns about condom use, long-term health and side effects, efficacy and HIV resistance. Awareness of PrEP was lower amongst GBMSM who were less highly educated and mistrust of healthcare providers was again shown to be an issue affecting acceptability of PrEP. Understandably, barriers and facilitators to PrEP accessibility had a subsequent effect on adherence motivation. Golub *et al.* (2013) research utilised snowball sampling, which can restrict the sample to a small network of acquaintances, introducing bias (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.319). However, Sowicz *et al.* (2014) in a literature review also identified accessibility, ease of use, efficacy and safety of PrEP as facilitators to uptake. Golub *et al.* (2013) concurred with Franks *et al.* (2017) in finding a negative stigma around PrEP acceptability in the USA, where family and partners of people taking PrEP interpreted its' use as an indication of being promiscuous and at high risk of HIV or being HIV positive. Conversely, Auerbach and Hoppe (2015) and Ellorin *et al.* (2017) suggested that being 'HIV negative and on PrEP' is now seen as being desirable as the person taking PrEP was acting responsibly and HIV negative.

2.6 GBMSM experiences of adherence to PrEP

Adherence to PrEP medication in this literature review is defined as dose taking behaviour compared to taking the medication prescribed (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.199). Levels of adherence to PrEP in the literature vary greatly, for example, Guest *et al.* (2010) reported a high level of adherence to PrEP of 82% and Montgomery *et al.* (2016) 90%; whereas Hosek *et al.* (2013) demonstrated as low as 20% adherence to PrEP in their study. Much of the literature around adherence to PrEP for GBMSM did not study deprivation or socio-economic status specifically; instead focussing on health and access to services which are domains of deprivation (Public Health Scotland, 2020).

Taylor *et al.* (2014) in the USA conducted a qualitative study of 39 GBMSM utilising focus groups and a descriptive design to identify issues around PrEP adherence. Findings identified the rationale for GBMSM taking PrEP as the reduced risk of contracting HIV and the idea of not passing on HIV to the wider community.

Facilitators to PrEP adherence included taking other medications regularly, keeping pills in different places, anticipating changes in schedules, reminders such as texts, emails, phone calls and alarms and a good relationship with the health care provider. Barriers to PrEP adherence and continuation were anxiety, insomnia, drugs, alcohol and side effects. However, there is consensus in the literature that under 10% of PrEP users experience adverse side effects (Spinner *et al.*, 2016; Pool, Youssef and Fisher, 2015; De Man *et al.*, 2013). Further barriers to PrEP adherence in Taylor *et al.* (2014) were depression, stigma and health care providers being poorly informed. Focus groups do not provide confidentiality and can be biased by participants avoiding conflict or conforming to expectations of their peers or dominant opinions within the group (Goodman and Evans, 2015, p.406; David and Sutton, 2011, p.136). However, Sowicz *et al.* (2014) in a literature review similarly found that running out of medication, being busy, being away, variations to routine and alcohol/drugs were barriers to adherence to PrEP. Further barriers to PrEP adherence in Molina *et al.* (2015) RCT were identified as being wrongly branded as HIV positive, unintended disclosure of homosexual identity and partner conflicts. Moreover, the patients' perception of their HIV risk may be different to their actual risk; and an individual comfortable with a certain level of risk could regard missed doses of PrEP more favourably (De Man *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, HIV literacy and realisation of HIV risk is vital to not only uptake of PrEP but also adherence (Harberer, 2016; Young and McDaid, 2014).

2.6.1 Psychosocial factors affecting GBMSM experiences of adherence to PrEP

As outlined in the previous chapter (section 1.7) GBMSM experience poorer mental and physical health than the heterosexual population and are more likely to smoke, drink alcohol and take drugs (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Shuper *et al.* (2020) noted that alcohol/drug use and mental health problems are significantly associated with poorer adherence to anti-retroviral therapy for people living with HIV and investigated if adherence to PrEP is affected in the same way. Results demonstrated that harmful drinkers of alcohol were over six times more likely to be nonadherent to PrEP than those GBMSM who were low-risk drinkers and moderate/high cocaine users were over three times more likely not to adhere to PrEP than low-risk users (Shuper *et al.*, 2020). This study informed Shuper *et al.* (2022) to investigate these

results further with a qualitative study recruiting 35 GBMSM from two PrEP clinics in Toronto to take part in five focus groups. Discussions focused on adherence to PrEP with an emphasis on alcohol, drug use and mental health and the findings developed utilising thematic analysis. Participants reported that again, significant alcohol or drug use was a barrier to remembering to take PrEP as the person was intoxicated; additionally people who were dependent on alcohol/drugs tended to neglect their health in general. Alcohol and cocaine use can impair neurocognitive function and cause lifestyle disruptions, preventing GBMSM from taking their PrEP on schedule (Shuper *et al.*, 2022). With regard to mental health, participants reported that the severity of the illness affected adherence. Illnesses such as depression diminished the motivation for GBMSM to take care of their health, particularly if the person was less sexually active at the time (Shuper *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, the literature suggests that barriers to adherence to PrEP of alcohol/drug use and mental health issues for GBMSM are counteracted by individual motivation for self-care.

Adherence to medication can be challenging to measure in studies as construct validity is introduced if the instrument is not accurate (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.199). Pill counts are often used in PrEP studies but cannot measure whether the medication was actually taken; therefore drug levels in plasma are more reliable (Anghel, Farcas and Oprean, 2019; Sidebottom, Ekstrom and Stromdahl, 2018). Alternatively, self-reporting data can be affected by participant bias where adherence may have been overestimated due to reasons such as social desirability or poor recall (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.250). Therefore, Anghel, Farcas and Oprean (2019) and Harberer (2016) recommended combining at least two methods for accuracy.

2.7 GBMSM experiences of risk compensation and PrEP continuation

Risk compensation is a particularly significant issue in regard to continuation of PrEP as commencing, continuing with or stopping PrEP will be dependent on the individual's perceived risk analysis of acquiring HIV, which may be flawed (Young and McDaid, 2014). A brief explanation of why GBMSM may not use condoms and take part in sexual behaviours which put them at risk of HIV has been outlined in chapter one, section 1.6.1. Much of the literature around changes to health behaviours and continuation of PrEP for GBMSM related to deprivation focussed on health inequalities and vulnerabilities.

A qualitative study by Hughes *et al.* (2018) utilised grounded theory with individual semi-structured telephone interviews to explore the role of PrEP on the sexual behaviours of 32 GBMSM in the USA. Findings included a low incidence of HIV, high incidence of other STIs and that indicators of sexual risk-taking behaviours declined or remained stable when taking PrEP. Hughes *et al.* (2018) research found that some participants directly attributed PrEP use to condomless sex as the quality of PrEP provided 'a salvation' from the risk of HIV, allowing them to enjoy sex and intimacy and lessening HIV stigma. Other participants reported that changes in sexual behaviour were partially due to PrEP use but also due to their psychological needs at the time, such as being single or in a new relationship or experiencing erectile dysfunction. Some participants who had ceased to use condoms had subsequently contracted other STIs so started to use condoms again. Grounded theory methods have been criticised for not taking into account the influence of social structures and culture on human interaction and for being too prescriptive and limited in terms of providing an explanation (Holloway and Galvin, 2015, p.193; David and Sutton, 2011, p.201). However, Hosek *et al.* (2017) and McCormack *et al.* (2016) also concurred that sexual risk taking behaviours did not increase when GBMSM were taking PrEP.

McCormack *et al.* (2016) was a particularly relevant RCT regarding PrEP provision in the UK as it recruited a pilot sample of 545 as part of a larger sample of 5000 GBMSM from sexual health clinics in England. Polit and Beck (2020, p.245) explained how highly powered studies such as this increase the external validity and reliability of the

RCT. The aim of McCormack *et al.* (2016) RCT was to assess the quality and efficacy of PrEP in a real-life setting and whether taking PrEP would affect participants' sexual risk-taking behaviour. McCormack *et al.* (2016) RCT reported that 21% of participants in the immediate PrEP arm had had condomless sex with ten or more partners compared to 12% in the control arm. No significant difference was found between the two groups regarding bacterial STIs, and the authors suggest that this indicates a negligible difference in condom use between the trial and control arms of the study. Reasons for not using condoms were given as sex is more enjoyable without them, participants or their partners didn't like condoms, they weren't discussed, participants were under the influence of drugs/alcohol, didn't consider themselves at risk of HIV or that they didn't use condoms with their regular partners but did with others. Nevertheless, the wider literature is conflicted as to whether taking PrEP affects risk compensation in terms of condom use and consequently, STI rates for GBMSM taking PrEP living in areas of high deprivation. For example, Oldenburg *et al.* (2017) discovered that individuals felt more protected from HIV following PrEP initiation and found a statistically significant increase in the number of partners and condomless sex as a consequence. Similarly, Chen *et al.* (2016) found that condom use had decreased by more than half from 2004 to 2014 with a sharp increase in unprotected sex amongst partners assumed to be HIV-negative due to PrEP. Traeger *et al.* (2018) found an increased diagnosis of STI's amongst GBMSM taking PrEP which suggests an increase in condomless sex and refutes the findings in McCormack *et al.* (2016). However, a lack of control data in observational studies makes it difficult to attribute changes in sexual behaviour to PrEP use alone as unmeasured or unanalysed confounders potentially affect results (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.51).

2.7.1 Psychosocial factors affecting GBMSM experiences of PrEP and risk compensation

Miltz *et al.* (2019a) further analysed the data in McCormack *et al.* (2016) to find that GBMSM who were taking PrEP also experienced a very high lifetime prevalence of intimate partner violence. This was strongly associated with sexualised drug use, internalised homophobia and depression. Further inequalities such as income and education between partners could also establish power dynamics in relationships and increase the risk of controlling behaviour and abuse from a partner (Miltz *et al.*, 2019a).

Miltz *et al.* (2019b) also analysed data from McCormack *et al.* (2016) to explore the prevalence of depression over time for GBMSM taking PrEP as mental health and wellbeing are often strongly linked to sexual health behaviours (Achterbergh *et al.*, 2020). Findings noted that GBMSM taking PrEP face a significant amount of stress in terms of HIV stigma, drug use, intimate partner violence and depression. The findings also emphasised the link between socioeconomic disadvantage and poor mental health, where the GBMSM taking PrEP in McCormack *et al.* (2016) RCT reported increasing levels of depression over time. This was thought to be due to underreporting at baseline and increasing socioeconomic hardship and financial instability rather than associations with PrEP (Miltz *et al.*, 2019b). The proportions of GBMSM who are at high risk of HIV and taking PrEP who experience depression and intimate partner violence are unexpectedly high in comparison to GBMSM at low risk of HIV and do not require PrEP. The findings suggest that PrEP itself does not appear to influence these comorbidities; however, as outlined in the previous sections 1.7, 1.8 and 2.8, health inequalities such as these can negatively impact on uptake and adherence to PrEP.

2.7.2 GBMSM experiences of PrEP continuation

Identifying populations with low engagement of PrEP is an important outcome measure in evaluating the success of PrEP as programmes should not increase health inequity amongst at-risk populations. Rogers *et al.* (2023) carried out a qualitative study interviewing 49 GBMSM recruited from three PrEP clinics in the USA exploring why they had missed PrEP appointments. Findings were presented in themes of structural factors, social, clinical and behavioural factors. Structural factors included financial costs and problems with getting to the clinic such as not owning a car, poor public transport and reliance on others for transport. Social factors included seeing false or negative information in the media about PrEP and suspicions around safety from friends and family. The frequency of medical appointments was another barrier, particularly when asking for time away from hourly or low-paid work, and finally, participants attributing physical problems to side effects of PrEP. Improving PrEP literacy, culturally competent healthcare staff, flexible appointment times and support were thought to be facilitators to continuation of PrEP.

2.8 Narrative literature review summary

To summarise, it is important to return to the purpose of this literature review, the PrEP Care Cascade and the aim and objectives of this study. The literature around GBMSM and PrEP is quite extensive; however little relates specifically to GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation and the studies identified in this literature review tended to originate from the USA rather than the UK. The first research objective in this study relates to the rationale and experiences of taking PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. No studies were found which related to deprivation specifically, however findings in general were that PrEP facilitated less anxiety around contracting HIV, reduced HIV stigma and increased pleasure during sex for GBMSM (Hughes *et al.*, 2018). It is therefore presumed that GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation would also commence PrEP for the same reasons, although their specific experiences remain unknown in the literature.

The second research objective in this study explores barriers and facilitators to the uptake and adherence of PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. This review found that the characterisation of deprivation in the literature reflected that specified by the Scottish government and included finance, housing, health, access to services, education, incarceration and employment (Public Health Scotland, 2020). Five studies identified in the review regarding this theme concurred that deprivation in terms of low income both individually and at area level was a barrier to the uptake of PrEP for GBMSM (Dehlin *et al.*, 2019; Burns *et al.*, 2020; Blashill *et al.*, 2019; Garcia and Saw, 2019; Jaspal *et al.*, 2019). Understandably, a lack of employment was identified as one of the many causes of individuals low income, where a lack of financial resources prevented getting transport to PrEP clinics and associated costs of PrEP such as prescriptions (Dehlin *et al.*, 2019; Garcia and Saw, 2019; Jaspal *et al.*, 2019). Individuals with a low income often did not own a car and relied on others for transport because public transport services were limited. Even if the person was working, they were often in hourly or low-paid insecure employment where getting time away from work for the frequent PrEP clinic appointments required was a challenge (Rogers *et al.*, 2023). In terms of structural barriers to PrEP and lack of income/financial resources, this lack of access to healthcare was compounded by an

inadequate provision of PrEP clinics (Dehlin *et al.*, 2019; Garcia and Saw, 2019; Jaspal *et al.*, 2019). Poor housing was identified as another barrier to uptake of PrEP and understandably homeless individuals faced challenges to making and attending healthcare appointments (Dehlin *et al.*, 2019; Blashill *et al.*, 2019; Burns *et al.* 2021). Areas with higher levels of poverty and deprivation also tended to have higher levels of incarceration (Blashill *et al.*, 2019; Burns *et al.*, 2021). Burns *et al.* (2021) explained how these factors of deprivation act together on a neighbourhood level to form geographic concentrations of poverty; contributing to structural disadvantage which negatively impacts on PrEP uptake for the GBMSM living in those areas. The intersectionality of these factors together with disparities in health services exacerbates an unequal distribution of resources for GBMSM who are at risk of HIV. Furthermore, poor education increased mistrust of health care providers and impacted on HIV literacy, therefore awareness and uptake of PrEP where individuals who are unaware that they are at high risk of HIV are also unlikely to be aware of PrEP (Jaspal *et al.*, 2019; Garcia and Saw, 2019; Golub *et al.*, 2013). Mistrust of healthcare providers is likely to extend to mistrust of PrEP itself, particularly in light of concerns about side effects and negative PrEP stigma (Golub *et al.*, 2013). Experiences of violence, alcohol, drugs or depression were additional health disparities which were barriers to uptake of PrEP (Blashill *et al.*, 2019), as were issues with attending sexual health services and the stress of HIV stigma and discrimination (Garcia and Saw, 2019; Golub *et al.*, 2013).

Facilitators to uptake of PrEP in the literature for GBMSM with low socio-economic status tended to be the reverse of the barriers identified above; where better housing, better health, higher income and employment with good terms and conditions provided the individual with the social and economic opportunities to access healthcare and attend PrEP clinics. Better education was found to be linked to increased health and HIV literacy and increased uptake of PrEP, furthermore support and counselling in sexual health provided individuals with more information and therefore agency regarding their decision making and sexual health (Garcia and Saw, 2019; Jaspal *et al.*, 2019; Golub *et al.*, 2013).

Adherence to PrEP is important to consider as the medication will not be effective if it is not taken as indicated (Harberer, 2016). The literature in terms of deprivation for GBMSM and adherence to PrEP tended to focus only on health and access to services specifically and other characteristics of deprivation were not studied. Health issues included addictions such as alcohol and drugs and mental health problems such as depression and anxiety. GBMSM experience poorer mental and physical health than the heterosexual population and are more likely to smoke, drink alcohol and take drugs (Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017). Shuper *et al.* (2022) found that significant alcohol and/or cocaine use were barriers to adherence to PrEP. Individuals were either intoxicated or tended to be less likely to look after their health, causing them to not take their PrEP at the correct times or forget it altogether. Both substances, particularly in larger amounts, can affect cognition and function and can lead to chaotic lifestyles. Shuper *et al.* (2022) also studied mental health and adherence to PrEP in terms of depression, anxiety and adverse childhood experiences (ACE). Associations between depression and adherence to PrEP were inconclusive, nevertheless, it was found that other mental health conditions such as anxiety and experience of ACE impacted negatively on adherence to PrEP, with the severity of the condition being a factor (Shuper *et al.*, 2022;2020). Mental illnesses can affect mood and motivation for self-care, particularly if the individual is less sexually active due to their mood and may feel the requirement for PrEP is lessened (Shuper *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, this literature review identifies that health problems in terms of alcohol, drugs, mental health conditions and ACE are barriers to PrEP adherence for GBMSM. However these studies do not focus on GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation specifically, or take account other characteristics of deprivation such as income, education, employment, etc. Further barriers to adherence to PrEP identified in the wider literature were side effects, HIV stigma, poor HIV literacy, variations to routine, being busy and poor relationships with healthcare providers (Taylor *et al.*, 2014; Sowicz *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, facilitators to PrEP adherence such as external reminders, good relationships with healthcare providers and motivation to take PrEP to protect oneself and others will be applicable to GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation (Taylor *et al.*, 2014).

The third research objective in this study is to gain insight into sexual health behaviours in the light of PrEP amongst GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. Again, the literature identified in this review tended to be in terms of health and alcohol, drug use and mental health conditions with less study addressing other characteristics of deprivation. Miltz *et al.* (2019a; 2019b) explored GBMSM who are taking PrEP experiences of intimate partner violence and depression. It was found that GBMSM who are at high risk of HIV and so eligible for PrEP have experienced particularly high lifetime prevalences of intimate partner violence, depression and drug use which were linked to poorer health outcomes. This was thought in part to be due to the high levels of stress faced by GBMSM at a high risk of HIV due to HIV stigma. Those with less income and education faced further inequalities due to the risk of power relationships and coercion in relationships (Miltz *et al.*, 2019a). Furthermore, the stress of financial instability and socio-economic hardship was thought to increase the risk of stress and depression for GBMSM taking PrEP (Miltz *et al.*, 2019b). Interestingly, Hughes *et al.* (2018) found PrEP itself to have a positive effect on health, where participants reported a much lower anxiety about acquiring HIV. Findings in Hughes *et al.* (2018) noted that PrEP and risk compensation was often conditional on wider individual, social and historical factors. The wider literature regarding HIV risk compensation in terms of condom use and numbers of partners suggests that PrEP is linked to reduced condom use and potential increase in risk-taking behaviours and STIs (Oldenbrug *et al.*, 2017; Traeger *et al.*, 2018). Understandably, the barriers identified in this literature review to uptake of PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation such as financial considerations, lack of transport and insecure employment were also barriers to continuation of PrEP (Rogers *et al.*, 2023). However, Rogers *et al.* (2023) were able to identify that increasing awareness of HIV prevention and PrEP, knowledgeable and culturally sensitive healthcare providers, flexible clinic times and healthcare support were all facilitators to PrEP continuation for GBMSM.

2.9 Current research and key themes

Other current studies regarding PrEP in Scotland include a PhD studentship examining opportunities for online PrEP provision and another exploring the use of PrEP by women of colour in Chicago, London and Scotland. Further current research includes a qualitative study on the role of HIV activism and collaborations between community members and practitioners. Finally, another study explores perspectives on PrEP for people who inject drugs involving potential service users and providers (Public Health Scotland, 2019).

With regard to PrEP availability overseas, France has temporarily commenced a national program of PrEP in 2016 with subsidised costs and Norway has proposed plans to provide free PrEP (WHO, 2015). Other European countries are taking initial steps to instigate national programs of PrEP but out with Scotland many people are buying it online as it is not available from community or health services. Many internet sites do not require proof of a negative HIV test, a renal function result or a prescription. The European Medicines Agency has approved Tenofovir and Emtricitabine as PrEP; however every EU country must review individual price negotiations and intellectual property legislation to financially plan for prospective PrEP programs (Coleman and Prins, 2017).

2.10 Chapter two summary, rationale for study and aim and objectives

This literature review has established that there is scanty evidence around the impact of inequalities on the uptake of PrEP in Scotland amongst GBMSM. The introduction of PrEP in the UK has been within the last few years and the demand has been substantial. However, this literature review has demonstrated that deprivation in terms of income, education, health, education and income may adversely affect acceptability and accessibility of PrEP for GBMSM and impact on their right to health (WHO, 2017). To date there is a dearth of published study regarding GBMSM, deprivation and PrEP and whether GBMSM with a lower socio-economic status have poorer sexual health outcomes with regard to PrEP. The gaps in the literature outlined in the previous section provide justification for the topic selection and research need and have enabled development of the research aim and objectives that will determine the overall direction, scope and depth of the study (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.185). The aim and objectives are provided below:

Aim

To understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP.

Objectives

1. To explore the rationale for and experiences of (a) accessing and (b) utilising NHS PrEP among GBMSM living in SIMD quintiles one and two.
2. To understand the barriers and facilitators to (a) the uptake of and (b) adherence to PrEP among the above population.
3. To gain insight into sexual health behaviours among the above population in the light of PrEP.

Chapter three: Conceptual framework

3.1 Introduction

Many models and theories regarding uptake of healthcare exist but for this chapter the researcher will devise, present and focus on a specific conceptual framework for this study. This reflects the research aim and objectives of this study and context as the social phenomena regarding PrEP are complex and a multidisciplinary approach provides a better understanding of the occurrence in the real world (Parahoo, 2014, p. 71; Jabareen, 2009).

3.2 Theories, models and conceptual framework

A model can be defined as a schematic representation of a reality, whereas a theory explains how and why the phenomenon occurs (Parahoo, 2014, p.144). Jabareen (2009) distinguished between a theoretical framework, or research supported by a theory, and a conceptual framework, which utilises concepts from theories, models and research findings to underpin and guide a study. Theories such as Normalisation Process Theory (NPT) can be applicable to the aim of this study to explain how health inequalities can be mitigated if deprivation is taken into account during the implementation of PrEP as a health intervention (Chng *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, psychosocial healthcare models such as the Health Belief Model can be drawn upon to apply to sexual health decision making and uptake of PrEP, where HIV literacy and belief in the efficacy of PrEP are required before consideration of a potential cue to action (Llewellyn *et al.*, 2019, p.114). Another pertinent model which addresses alternative sources of health information is the Martin Word of Mouth communication Model where patients draw on health information from others such as friends (Pauli, Martin and Greiling, 2022).

The Health Belief and Word of Mouth Models and NPT are useful to draw upon from an individual and collective-level perspective in guiding understanding of HIV prevention behaviours by considering modifying factors, individual beliefs, and actions intrinsic to the individual (May *et al.*, 2018). However, the wider concept of intersectionality is also applicable to this study by demonstrating that the interaction

between social categories interconnected with power inequalities lead to structural inequalities, or relative disadvantage and privilege (Scottish government, 2022) (see section 1.7). Consequently, for GBMSM accessing PrEP, the social categories of sexuality and deprivation interacting within the power structure of law, health policy and government can cause structural inequalities affecting their human rights (Scottish Government, 2022).

3.3 Development of conceptual framework

Jabareen (2009), supported by Parahoo (2014, p.144), defined a conceptual framework as a 'network, or a 'plane,' of interlinked concepts that together provide a comprehensive understanding of a phenomena'; although qualifies that the term is often used imprecisely. Here, the author as a researcher with sexual health expertise has utilised an inductive approach where their own interpretation of the concepts are combined with the ideas that have emerged from the literature and their competencies. For the purposes of this thesis, a conceptual framework is devised and presented which includes not only GBMSM management of their sexual health regarding the multifaceted intervention of PrEP but also the wider contexts of structural and social level factors and the impacts of these on their sexual health.

To initiate the development of a new conceptual framework for this study, two existing conceptual frameworks for PrEP were identified and considered. Many PrEP models have proposed a number of individual steps within a linear PrEP 'Care Cascade' or 'Care Continuum' which aimed to quantify PrEP implementation programmes (Kelley *et al.*, 2015). PrEP Care Cascade/Continuum models and frameworks depict the patient journey by capturing the patient moving from initially becoming aware of PrEP to stages through to finally being actively engaged in taking it. During this journey, patients are in contact with the health service at a consecutive series of 'touch points'. These encompass both the physical and emotional aspects of the patient experience as they journey through the stages, where the patient is at the centre of the model and behaviour, feelings, motivations and attitudes are captured across episodes of care rather than at one visit (Davies *et al.*, 2022). In concordance with this, Nunn *et al.* (2017) developed the Kelley *et al.* (2015) PrEP Care Continuum to generate a

framework of nine stages within three categories for assessing PrEP implementation programs. The first category is awareness of PrEP; and includes identifying individuals at high risk for HIV and increasing their awareness of their risk of HIV and PrEP. The second category, uptake of PrEP, includes facilitating access to PrEP, linking to PrEP care and prescribing and initiating PrEP. The third and final category is adherence and retention in PrEP care:

Figure 3.1 PrEP Care Continuum Framework

(Nunn *et al.*, 2017)

Nunn *et al.* (2017) described how the steps in their framework conceptualise the barriers to PrEP effectiveness and uptake by highlighting additional opportunities for interventions to improve PrEP programmes and provide insight into how patients engage in PrEP care. In consideration of a conceptual framework for this study, it was felt that the concepts of HIV literacy, awareness of, access to and adherence to PrEP in Nunn *et al.* (2017) were key steps in the PrEP patient journey and therefore should be included in the framework for this study. However, the second category in Nunn *et al.* (2017), PrEP uptake, included considerations around the cost of clinical care, health insurance and finding a care provider which are specific to the USA and in contrast to the UK where PrEP is prescribed for free by the NHS. Retention in care is also difficult to quantify for a medication which is used as required. It can also be argued that the classifications of factors relevant to uptake of PrEP are narrow and

many political and economic social-level and structural-level factors relating to deprivation are not addressed in depth in this framework (Ezennia, Geter and Smith, 2019). The research aim of this study is to understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. Factors such as employment and health (Public Health Scotland, 2020) and the effect of political and social conditions relating to deprivation are likely to affect accessibility and acceptability of PrEP for GBMSM. Broader sociological or psychological considerations and structural level variables which impact on GBMSM seeking PrEP should be considered when addressing inequalities (Nutland, 2016).

Poundstone, Strathdee and Celentano (2004) explained how the determinants around HIV can be conceptualised at three levels: individual, social, and structural. Individual level influences include those such as behavioural or demographic risk factors that may influence the patients' risk of HIV infection. Social-level factors address how individuals are networked and linked to society such as by culture, social networks, neighbourhoods or social capital. Structural-level factors include economic and social factors, policies and laws which affect the differential distribution of HIV. Diez-Roux (1998) and Sumartojo (2000) argued that structural or macro-level variables affect individuals directly and constrain their choices and therefore multilevel or contextual analysis is required to understand social inequalities in health. Brisson, Ravitsky and Williams-Jones (2019) and Nutland (2016) concurred that the majority of PrEP studies have explored the acceptability of PrEP utilising the concepts of risk-taking behaviours, side effects, adherence and efficacy rather than addressing broader sociological or psychological considerations as outlined in chapter two. Chapter one demonstrates that PrEP encompasses a complex interlocking of political, biomedical, social and cultural forces with diverse meanings and values. It is important that the new conceptual framework for this study incorporates each of the associated individual-level concepts and social and structural factors.

One such conceptual framework which moved outside of the linear approach described above to extend PrEP conceptual frameworks further was Lau, Hung and Lee (2020), who introduced a conceptual healthcare accessibility framework for the Asia-Pacific region based on a modified version of the Levesque, Harris and Russell (2013) access to healthcare framework. Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) claimed that their framework is particularly appropriate for PrEP as it understands healthcare access from multiple levels rather than defining it by population and system characteristics or supply and demand factors.

Figure 3.2: Lau modified conceptual framework of healthcare accessibility for PrEP

(Lau, Hung and Lee, 2020)

The Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) conceptual framework specified five constructs with regard to the concepts involved in the uptake of PrEP. The first is approachability, where awareness of PrEP is necessary before it can be accessed. Awareness of PrEP in the Asia-Pacific region remained low, which reflects marginalised populations in Scotland (Estcourt *et al.*, 2021). Next, acceptability includes cultural and social factors such as concerns about confidentiality or PrEP-related social stigma. Community involvement was found to be important to analyse barriers to accessing

services and address discrimination to provide inclusive, non-judgmental and welcoming sexual health services (Lau, Hung and Lee, 2020). Thirdly, appropriateness focusses on the fit between the service and patient need. The fourth construct, availability, ensures that enough healthcare services provide PrEP that can be physically accessed, with convenient appointment times and competent staffing. Interestingly, successful programs involved nurses undertaking tasks that had previously been performed by doctors, which corresponds to PrEP provision in Scotland (see section 1.6.2). Finally, affordability relates to the cost of PrEP to the patient. Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) maintained that their healthcare accessibility construct framework is useful for identifying complex facilitators and structural barriers to PrEP implementation and community engagement and can assess best practice as it includes the perspectives of both healthcare client and provider. Therefore, it was felt that Lau, Hung and Lee (202) would form a basis for the conceptual framework for this study to aid understanding of PrEP as a complex intervention. However, further development was required to add multi-level concepts to fully encompass the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP.

Public Health Scotland (2021) explained how the fundamental human right of good health is dependent on Scottish public healthcare services and social determinants of health meeting the AAAQ standards (WHO, 2017). The AAAQ framework is useful in identifying health inequalities and barriers to accessing healthcare such as deprivation (Public Health Scotland, 2021). It was noted that the five constructs in the Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) framework aligned with the WHO (2017) Essential Standards of Healthcare Services which are availability, accessibility, acceptability and quality (AAAQ) overleaf:

Table 3:2 WHO AAAQ Framework

<p>Availability Medication or service sufficient in terms of quantity and type</p>	<p>Acceptability Inclusivity of service, confidentiality, cultural competence of staff</p>
<p>Accessibility Physical (location, appointment times/types) Economic (cost to access e.g., transport) Non-discrimination (for all people including vulnerable, no stigma) Information (promotion of service)</p>	<p>Quality Scientifically and medically appropriate (medication standards, staff training)</p>

(WHO, 2017)

Therefore, it was decided that it was important to modify the Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) framework to reflect the four constructs of the WHO (2017) AAAQ framework. Availability replaces approachability and refers to the actual PrEP service provision and promotion of the same which will be linked to awareness of PrEP. Acceptability remains constant in both frameworks, referring to the cultural and social acceptability of the medication and sexual health services for GBMSM. Accessibility has been divided into two constructs, the physical in terms of location/cost to get to the clinic, and non-discrimination/information accessibility, which refers to the PrEP service and health information being accessible to all including vulnerable populations. Finally, quality replaces appropriateness, and refers to the quality and utility of PrEP medication and the services surrounding provision. This allows for the inclusion of PrEP medication itself to the framework, and the addition of GBMSM motivations and influences on the continuation of PrEP which are fundamental but are absent in other frameworks. Affordability has been removed from this framework as PrEP medication is provided free from the NHS in Scotland.

The final consideration for the conceptual framework for this study concerned the inclusion of components to address barriers to PrEP and inequalities that had been identified in the framework. To do this, the author considered it appropriate to move outside of healthcare and towards business models as it was felt the objective of customer service would fit with addressing the needs of service users, good relationships with healthcare providers and retention in care. It was found that the constructs in Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) conceptual framework and WHO (2017) AAAQ framework for healthcare standards also fitted with those in the 'marketing mix', which is a tool featuring key considerations for review when successfully marketing a product or service (Groucutt, Leadley and Forsyth, 2004, p.250). The 'marketing mix', or 'five Ps' are product, place, price, promotion, and people. This range of factors or concepts incorporate the product PrEP, or the quality of the physical item that serves the needs of patients (customer demand), the price or cost, the place or location, promotion and advertising and finally people including staff and patients (or customers) and their behaviours and psychosocial considerations. For the purposes of the conceptual framework in this study, price is less relevant here as PrEP is free from the NHS, therefore it has been replaced by the consideration packaging, or the quality and utility of the service around PrEP provision (Constantinides, 2006, p.207).

In summary, the new conceptual framework for this study is derived by the researcher in the main from the development of the Nunn et al. (2017) PrEP Care Continuum and the Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) PrEP healthcare accessibility frameworks. To realise the Scottish Government aim of the right to health, the AAAQ standards of healthcare is reflected in the framework (Public Health Scotland, 2021; WHO, 2017) and the marketing mix is also integrated to improve PrEP service provision (Groucutt, Leadley and Forsyth, 2004, p.250). The framework contains the determinants around HIV conceptualised at individual, social and structural levels (Poundstone, Strathdee and Celentano, 2004). The constructs of Availability, Accessibility, Acceptability and Quality comprehensively capture the experiences of the GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation who are taking NHS PrEP:

Figure 3.3: New PrEP patient journey conceptual framework devised for this study

The arrows indicate the patient journey from PrEP availability and initial patient awareness of PrEP to the decision to acquire it, to attending sexual health services, the PrEP consultation and finally PrEP uptake and continuation. The addition of the ‘marketing mix’ tool provides useful wider considerations that can be addressed to influence demand for PrEP from patients who are at risk of HIV. The ‘marketing mix’ directs focus to whether PrEP services meet or fail to meet patient need, how PrEP is perceived by patients and how PrEP healthcare services interact with patients. The inclusion of structural, intermediate/social and individual levels to each of the steps rather than a linear approach allows incorporation of the economic, political, cultural and social determinants of health applicable to PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. Patient journey frameworks such as the new conceptual framework above devised for this study can enable understanding of the dynamic patient relationship with the health service and in particular the lived experience of stigmatised or disadvantaged populations who may face additional barriers to accessing and engaging with health services (Davies *et al.*, 2022). This new conceptual framework was utilised to underpin this study as demonstrated in the theme generation in the findings chapter five and section 6.8 with the addition of the key conceptual findings.

3.4 Chapter three summary

The new conceptual framework for this study developed by the researcher is derived from consideration of the Nunn *et al.* (2017) PrEP 'care continuum' and the Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) PrEP conceptual frameworks, also incorporating Scottish government policy for public health services (Public Health Scotland, 2021). The need for a multi-level healthcare accessibility conceptual framework to underpin this study which includes individual/social/structural determinants of health is justified to allow for the inclusion of the economic and social factors, policies and laws which affect the social inequalities in health for GBMSM taking PrEP.

Chapter four: Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will provide a clear account of the procedures followed to implement this study. Firstly, the key philosophical issues in the context of this research are presented, then the underlying theory related to the research design and the process and rationale for the research approach adopted. The next section provides the justification for participant selection, recruitment and data collection techniques and details how they were executed in the study. Next, the choice of framework for data analysis is examined together with the decisions taken to arrive at the final themes. Ethical approval is addressed and finally, the means of ensuring rigour and trustworthiness of the data are outlined.

4.2 Ontological and epistemological perspectives

Guba and Lincoln (1994, p.108) explained that the perspective towards the proposed research, or paradigm, is presented in terms of ontology (nature of reality), which gives rise to epistemology (theory of knowledge and evidence) and subsequently methodology (how to gain evidence). All scientific research rests on ontological and epistemological assumptions and principles (Neuman, 2014, p.70).

Ontology can be defined as an area of philosophy describing the nature of reality; of what exists and the nature of being (Neuman, 2014, p.72; David and Sutton, 2011, p.39). Clear ontological assumptions are necessary to define what is to be studied and its place in the world during the research process. Within the ontological perspective there are two diverse basic positions: the realist and the nominalist. Realists view the world as being organised into pre-existing categories which can be captured easily to produce objective knowledge. Often the reality is measurable scientifically, with the assumption that it exists without outside influence, independently of humans and their interpretations of it (Neuman, 2014, p.98). Conversely, nominalists assume that humans never experience reality directly as their understanding of the 'real world' occurs through a lens of subconscious interpretations and inner subjectivity. As biography, cultural worldview and subjective-cultural beliefs

vary between individuals, there are multiple perceptions of reality; hence the acquisition of objective knowledge is problematical (Neuman 2014, p.99).

Philosophically, researchers must have an epistemological viewpoint, or theory of knowledge, which is grounded in their ontological assumptions of what it is to be human. Epistemology is concerned with ways of researching, or what is to be done to produce valid scientific knowledge (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.33). Epistemological principles and rules include two types of reasoning: firstly, deductive methods from the realist approach where a hypothesis is tested to form a theory and conclusion formed by logical steps from a premise (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.130). Conversely, inductive methods involve the study of individual cases leading to a conclusion or generalisation and abstract thinking evolving from empirical evidence (Neuman, 2014, p.102). Epistemological assumptions also tend towards two broad positions: positivism and interpretivism (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.6). The positivist approach is considered to be comparable to the natural sciences' method of enquiry regarding empirical evidence where discrete concepts such as numerical data are obtained. Knowledge is acquired using a deductive process and statistical analysis of empirical evidence using formal instruments are used to test a theory proposed by the researcher by examining the relationship amongst variables (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.7). This quantitative, deterministic approach assumes a fixed orderly reality that can be objectively studied and reduced to a probable law or prediction (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.21). Objectivity is important so the researcher is independent from the research participants (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.110). Alternatively, interpretivism embodies the proposition that social reality is changing constantly and it is not possible to arrive at understanding by means of precise measurements (Bryman, 2015, p.26). The voices of and interaction between researchers and participants are central to the understanding of the phenomenon and knowledge is obtained using an inductive process (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.17). The focus is on emerging subjectivity of values and beliefs of the participants' mental framework; often a central tenet of qualitative research (Neuman, 2014, p.103).

The aim of this study was informed and shaped by the researcher's personal ontological worldview of historic materialism, where the economic and social conditions faced by GBMSM in Scotland drive history, and history is made as a result of the struggle between different social classes rooted in the underlying economic base (Kenny *et al.*, 2010, p.771). Historical materialism reflects my personal view as it seeks to explain and critique social inequalities through capitalism and economics and also to formulate a transformative agenda toward a more equitable future. Problems faced by GBMSM such as health inequalities related to HIV are not experienced in a vacuum but are influenced by additional structural, social and individual factors (see Personal integrative statement). Reflection of my clinical practice in sexual health informed my epistemological approach to this study. Experiencing the complex interaction of each service users' individual history, emotions, circumstances and beliefs drew me to IPA as the idiographic nature captured the integrity of each part of the participant's experience without having to subsume their findings into someone else's story (Smith, 2017).

4.2.1 Paradigm

Cresswell and Cresswell (2018, p.5) explained how a paradigm is defined as the set of philosophical assumptions that guide the approach to inquiry, or worldview. The paradigm and theoretical lens of this research has been underpinned by the literature review to facilitate the exploration of the nature of knowledge (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.106). The philosophical worldview of the lead researcher regarding this study has been shaped by their discipline and past research experience and complemented by the shared beliefs and values of other health professionals with expertise in both research and sexual health (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.6; Gerrish, 2015, p.8). Various paradigms were considered as to which provides the best theoretical underpinning to answer the research aim and objectives. In nursing it has been suggested that the dominant paradigm is constructivism (Seale, 1999), which was deemed appropriate and useful in terms of PrEP being a new medication in healthcare (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.27). However, positivism cannot be discounted as PrEP research lends itself to RCTs involving well developed concepts with an existing body of literature, usually explained in quantitative terms.

The approach to empirical research chosen for this study was one of a social constructionist paradigm utilising qualitative research due to the topic of interest involving fluid social constructions as opposed to firm facts. Patient experience is a social construction in how individuals perceive and identify the circumstances around taking PrEP. The ontology of constructionism views the world by emphasising the meanings shared between individuals who are self-directed and logical (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.24). Ransome *et al.* (2020) argued that HIV risk is a social construct as it upraised the debate between individual rights and public health, with the government of individual sexual practices demonstrating that societal normalisation of sexuality is an instrument of power. Social discourse defines the rules of sexuality with HIV becoming synonymous with moral decadence and promiscuity, enabling stigmatisation of the disease process and encouraging blame, prejudice and discrimination as outlined in section 1.4 (Huber and Gillaspy, 1998). Similarly, poverty and social exclusion are social constructs, involving shame and dispossession (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland) 2017).

The epistemological underpinning for the researcher is in their ability to recreate and impart the sense and belief of that social life (David and Sutton, 2011, p.78). Neuman (2014, p.104) added that reality exists as people experience it and assign meanings to it, for example relying on untested assumptions and taken-for-granted knowledge. The philosophical tenets of the social constructivist paradigm are underpinned by qualitative research to enable comprehension of the various social constructions using data collection techniques such as interviews (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.25). Knowledge is the outcome of human activity as the researcher utilises inductive reasoning to integrate information from the specific to the general to develop theory (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.18). Social constructionism fits with research where context is key as there is not one tangible reality shared by all participants (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.25). However, critics of the interpretivist tradition, including critical theorists such as Habermas, reject the view that 'cultures can only be understood in terms of their own internal system of values and beliefs' and claim that the meaningful understandings of one lifeworld can be explained to another (David and Sutton, 2011 p. 36).

4.2.2 Strategy of inquiry

Cresswell and Cresswell (2018, p.3) described how research topics 'tend' towards quantitative or qualitative contrasting methods of research. As this study explores the interactions, experiences and meanings of individuals in a community rather than measuring quantities or frequencies, it tends toward qualitative research and the interpretivist paradigm (Polgar, 2019, p.12; Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.104). Qualitative research is often used for investigating hard to reach groups (such as GBMSM) or for discussing sensitive subjects (such as sexual health) (Topping, 2015, p.166). Trust and insight are provided by the empathic professional relationship built up between the researcher and participant (Polgar, 2019, p.13). Qualitative research methods are often used in nursing, partly because the small sample sizes involved are more practical but also because it is more in keeping with the patient observation and interaction involved in nursing (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.6). Given that human beings, societies and cultures are different, qualitative research does not provide one single interpretation of meaning hence does not provide the generalisability of quantitative research (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.159).

Several principal qualitative strategies of inquiry (or procedures associated with the approach to the study) were considered. Firstly, ethnographic study involves investigation by the researcher of a cultural group immersed in their natural setting over a prolonged period of time, analysing observational and interview data (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.13). Ethnography aims to grasp the social interactions and lived realities of a culture (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.181); however, this approach is inapplicable to this study as the researcher cannot be integrated into the research setting because the sexual aspect of participants' lives are not open to routine observation (David and Sutton, 2011, p.150). Grounded theory methods comprise of data being simultaneously collected and analysed, allowing for a theory development to identify interrelationships with the aim of accounting for peoples' actions (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.269; Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.161). True grounded theory informs researchers should guard against preconceived ideas and thoughts and enter the research field as a 'tabular rasa' or blank slate, however, Robson and McCartan (2016, p.171) informed that this is challenging. Grounded

theory has been criticised because theory is formed from the best account of a small dataset which may not have exhausted all explanations and may provide categories without any explanatory potential (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.602). Grounded theory was deemed inappropriate for this study as the research aim is not investigating the symbolic interactions between people (Holloway and Galvin, 2015, p.188).

Further strategies of inquiry included critical theory which focusses on the needs of groups or individuals in society who may be marginalised or disenfranchised; thus, involving a critique of society (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.9). Similarly, feminist research focusses on gender domination and discrimination within patriarchal societies to understand how women's lives have been shaped and facilitate transformative change (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.274). Action research seeks to improve practice by studying the effects of an action taken in one particular health care setting where the researcher collaborates with the participants (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.163). However, critical realism seeks to explain deeper mechanisms beneath social and economic relationships, which is outside the scope of this doctorate (David and Sutton, 2011, p.77); feminist theory was thought less appropriate for a study regarding men (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, p.109) and this study does not address the progressive problem solving involved in action research. Historical research and case studies were also discounted due to the lack of existing data as PrEP is a new medication.

4.2.3 Phenomenology

Phenomenology is a research tradition built on the view that philosophy is based on human experience and that the view from the persons' perspective is required for a comprehensive understanding of human behaviour (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.159). The phenomenological approach was originally founded by Husserl, who assumed that physical objects exist as perceptual phenomena, or an 'essence' of subjective phenomena (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.212). Husserl proposed that the way an experience is directed towards an object, or intuition, provides intentional experience and meaning which Husserl described as Realist Phenomenology

(Husserl and Moran, 2002, p.xxxi). Hence, phenomenology is the study of conscious experience, describing psychological acts rather than causal explanations. Husserl also defined the practice of 'bracketing' where the observer identifies and suspends their ego and predetermined beliefs and viewpoints about the phenomena being studied so that they remain open to the meanings attributed by the participants (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.212). This bracketing process also sits within the positivist approach to research (Nelson, Dumville and Torgerson, 2015, p.239).

Husserl's approach to phenomenology was expanded and amended by Heidegger, who examined it not as a scientific discipline but rather as the nature of existence (Kenny, 2010, p.819). Central to this is the notion that phenomenology should include unconscious or semi-conscious habits, and that people were not just 'essences' but were 'becoming' (Horrigan-Kelly, Millar and Dowling, 2016). Contrary to Husserl's stance, Heidegger acknowledged that bracketing in phenomenology is not possible as the researcher is in the world so cannot be separate from it. Heidegger denied the existence of human nature, instead believing in individual choice and responsibility and has been described as the originator of existentialism (Kenny, 2010, p.821). He understood that language influences experiences of reality and later concentrated on hermeneutics, or the study of language and interpretation; and conceived the hermeneutic circle where text and context interchange (Horrigan-Kelly, Millar and Dowling, 2016). The existentialist Jean-Paul Sartre expanded on Heidegger's work, agreeing with the philosophy of free will, however proposing that because individuals can think of ways of dealing with situations they did not choose to be in, consciousness occurs as intentionality (Kenny, 2010, p.822). Following on from these earlier works, Gadamer defined the concept of hermeneutical phenomenological interpretation as incorporating aspects such as 'experiential happenings', where the researcher assembles the common themes and understandings of the participant. An 'essential structure' brings the themes together as they are generalised beyond the study participants in an understandable way to form a new perspective, or 'fusion of horizons'. Thus, findings are shaped by context, analysed and understood 'whilst capturing the unique' (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.216).

An outline of phenomenological ontology suggests that humans are conscious beings, and this awareness shapes personal reality (David and Sutton, 2011, p.89). The researcher gathers and reflects on the participant's experiences, or 'lifeworld' descriptions to develop understandings which can be applied further to other populations and groups (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.218). The phenomenological approach to research investigates the individual's fundamental truth of their reality based on their lived experience so was deemed the appropriate strategy of inquiry for this study.

The strengths of a phenomenological approach are that it can provide rigour to a study in encapsulating and portraying the meanings of significant human experiences, providing deeper insight and humanising understanding with recognition by the reader. However, limitations exist around variances between the different phenomenological approaches regarding issues such as bracketing, suggesting that the pursuit of phenomenology is an essentially contested concept (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.221). Descriptive phenomenology has also been criticised for being 'sealed from the world outside'; being incomplete by not taking account of how the participants' circumstances affect their meaning, such as in the power relationship between a health care professional and patient (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.21).

4.2.4 Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis

The theory of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is underpinned by the concept of individual experience above personal theory from Husserl and the analysis of participant and researcher from Heidegger (Smith, 2017). The IPA approach is becoming prevalent in nursing as it offers detailed understanding of individual patient experience, exploring personal meanings and facilitating empathy for teaching and patient care (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.121). IPA shares philosophical assumptions with critical realism and it has been portrayed as being situated in the middle of the realist-relativist ontological continuum (Shinebourne, 2011). Therefore, IPA fits with the aim of this study as it is in congruence with the social constructive paradigm (Smith, 2017) exploring and understanding each participant's subjective viewpoint of the world rather than describing objective accounts of reality (Smith,

Flowers, and Larkin, 2022, p.33). It is useful for contemporary topics where little is known such as GBMSM experience of PrEP (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.267).

IPA is also grounded in hermeneutical phenomenology; using a 'double hermeneutic'; where the researcher makes sense of the participant making sense (Brown *et al.*, 2018). This ensures that the interpretive analysis remains true to the participant's account to reveal their reflections and perceived experiences of taking PrEP (Brown *et al.*, 2018; Smith, 2017). The IPA approach also accounts for past and present social, economic and biochemical factors that can influence the individual participant's experience (Brown *et al.*, 2018). An additional advantage of IPA is idiography, or the incorporation of divergent participant experiences rather than looking only for similarities amongst participants, which are tenets of other strategies of inquiry such as thematic analysis (Brown *et al.*, 2018). IPA is useful for examining cultural practices and experience within culture, hence is in keeping with the study of populations such as GBMSM (Smith, Flowers and Larkin 2022, p.194). Speirs and Riley (2018) noted that thematic analysis and IPA work well together as methods to draw out multiple elements of a larger qualitative datasets, therefore, it was decided that the approach to this study would follow the central tenets of IPA to facilitate data analysis and utilise IPA-informed thematic analysis.

4.3 Methodological process

Key to the philosophical discussions is the need to demonstrate a thread to the process of the research. This section explains the gathering of qualitative data, encompassing the associated ethical issues, the nature of the sample and data analysis, before moving on to consider rigour in the study.

4.3.1 Population/sample

Nieswiadomy and Bailey (2018, p.170) explained how it is not possible to collect information about an entire population for a study. Parahoo (2014, p.262) identified two main types of sampling strategy as probability and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling is the random selection of components from a population and is generally used in quantitative research such as RCTs to draw robust statistical

generalisations from the sample to the population (Polgar, 2019, p.36). This is not appropriate for this study as generalisability is not an aim. Non-probability sampling is more commonly associated with qualitative research and is not random, aiming for transferability rather than the generalisability of quantitative research (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.175). Non-probability sampling is widely used in nursing research as it is appropriate for smaller studies and uses participants who volunteer so is useful for hard-to-reach groups such as GBMSM (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.280). Rigour relies on ensuring that the sample is reflective of the study population (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.172). The use of non-probability sampling for this study identified participants who could provide depth of knowledge and richness of meaning to maximise the understanding of the phenomenon (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.309).

Several principal strategies of non-probability sampling exist. Firstly, convenience sampling consists of choosing the nearest or most accessible individuals, which saves time and money so may be useful for novices or a pilot study (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.182; Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.280). However, the potential for bias and a less representative sample limits transferability and the ability to analyse the data, hence this method was thought unsatisfactory for this study (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.281). Snowball sampling involves study participants identifying other individuals who may qualify for inclusion to the study (David and Sutton, 2011, p.232). This type of sampling is useful for hard to reach or to identify new populations or where the topic may be sensitive, such as sexuality (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.281) and breaks down the power relationship between researcher and participant, for example nurse researchers with patient respondents (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.159; Johnson and Long, 2015, p.34). However, snowball sampling was discounted for this study as bias is almost inevitable where isolated social networks of individuals are over sampled or excluded by the initial contact and the researcher is unable to judge how reflective of the population the sample is (David and Sutton, 2011, p.232). Theoretical sampling is a feature of grounded theory. Sampling is not generally defined beforehand but directed by emerging theory whilst using constant comparison until no modifications are made to the theory (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.161). Theoretical sampling involves ongoing a posteriori knowledge used in addition to a priori knowledge for sampling decisions to develop or

integrate conceptual categories within the research (Gentles *et al.*, 2015), hence is not applicable to this study as data collection is not ongoing.

Purposive sampling seeks out and selects a subset of people from the target population for information-rich sources (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.312). Purposive sampling requires definitive information about each available sampling unit and the criteria to be used for selection (Gentles *et al.*, 2015). Purposive sampling is generally used in phenomenological research and particularly IPA as to provide a personal account and context the participant must have experienced the phenomena (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.217). Consequently, purposive sampling was chosen for this study so that the participants will be GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation who are taking NHS PrEP, facilitating focus on the relevant range of specific and distinctive issues and circumstances (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.156). Nevertheless, purposive sampling may introduce sample bias as the viewpoints of people not included in the sample are not represented and individuals of note to the researcher can be over-represented (Hunt and Lathlean, 2015, p.177; Parahoo, 2014, p.382). However, Parahoo (2014, p.269) explained how purposive sampling aims for 'naturalistic generalisation', where the findings of one study can aid understanding in similar situations by portraying the 'typical'.

Sampling used by traditional phenomenological approaches can deliberately select cases with a wide variety of interest, or maximum variation sampling (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.320). However, IPA uses homogenous purposive sampling to find a closely defined group who are significant in regard to the research aim and topic under investigation (Smith and Osborn, 2007). For this study the sample were GBMSM in the West of Scotland taking NHS PrEP living in SIMD quintiles one and two. Despite the IPA approach of reporting in detail on one group, there was some variation amongst participants in this study sample in terms of relationship status, education, area, occupation, age and the length of time taking PrEP.

A range of optimal sample sizes has been proposed for qualitative research. Typically, studies in phenomenology use small numbers such as ten participants to provide in-depth reflections (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.323; Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.218).

Smith and Osborn (2007) suggested that the optimum sample size for IPA ranges from one to over 15; and Gentles *et al.* (2015) suggested 12 participants. Thus, it was determined that the sample size should be twelve participants to provide a detailed analysis of each case (Smith and Osborn, 2007) and if not, the researcher would return to the sampling frame to recruit more participants. At twelve participants, many of the themes related similarly between participants, suggesting wider applicability (Smith and Osborn, 2007).

4.3.2 Inclusion/exclusion criteria

The sampling frame of the population of interest were identified as participants living in the West of Scotland region. The population of interest and inclusion criteria for the sample were English speaking GBMSM aged 18 and over who had access to a telephone, lived in SIMD quintile areas one and two of the city hence potentially lower socio-economic status who had been prescribed PrEP medication by NHS sexual health services. [The five SIMD quintiles define the extent of deprivation of an area by consideration of seven domains: crime, access to services, health, housing, education, employment and income (Public Health Scotland, 2020)]. Exclusion criteria were GBMSM not taking PrEP, heterosexual men, people without a phone, people requiring interpreters, women, people aged under 18 and people living outside the sampling frame area. A major Scottish city health board was chosen as it includes the majority of PrEP recipients in Scotland (41%, Public Health Scotland, 2019). In other health board areas patients access PrEP services in alternate ways and prescriptions may not be on their electronic patient record. Additionally, this Scottish city NHS health board was chosen as a higher number of people live in the lower SIMD quintile areas compared to the higher SIMD, more affluent areas (Scottish Government National Statistics, 2021). Health Board areas in Scotland vary in terms of population density and demographics so the results of this study may be transferable to other urban areas but perhaps less so to rural areas where GBMSM are less aware of PrEP (Frankis *et al.*, 2016). Patients living in SIMD quintile areas three, four and five were excluded as they are the least deprived. The inclusion and exclusion criteria fit with the research aim and objectives of this study (see chapter two).

4.3.3 Ethical considerations

This study adheres to the principles of the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki and the code of ethics at the University of the West of Scotland (Gelling, 2015, p.144 and 155). Firstly, local informal management approval was granted by the Clinical Director, who has overall responsibility for the sexual health service (Appendix 7). The lead researcher then completed a local research enquiry process form (Appendix 8) and formal management approval was granted at the local clinic research governance group meeting on 15/4/20 (Appendix 9). Favourable ethical opinion was granted by the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee on 29/7/20 (Appendix 10). Favourable ethical opinion had also been granted by Essex East of England NHS Research ethics committee on 23/12/20 before patients were recruited into this study (Appendix 11).

Informed consent was required for this study. Participants were asked if they had any questions from the participant information sheet (Appendix 12) which were answered by the lead researcher to ensure they were fully informed about the research, comprehended their role, potential risks and were free from coercion (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.127; NMC, 2018). If participants lacked the capacity to consent, they were excluded from the study as per Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act (2000). Participants were informed that they could decline to answer questions or withdraw from the study at any time up to a week after the interview without giving a reason. If a participant had withdrawn, their interview data would have been deleted immediately and another participant recruited to the study.

To ensure confidentiality, participants were not identified (NMC, 2018). All data are kept securely either on paper in locked cabinets in a locked room or in electronic form on a secure (password protected) computer in adherence with the Data Protection Act (2018), UWS policy and ethics committee decisions (Johnson and Long, 2015, p.36). Only the lead researcher and supervisors have access to the data. Potential participants were also assured that the lead researcher would only use their first name, phone number and SIMD quintile from their online patient record for identification so would be unable to identify them outside of the research interview. Names and phone numbers were deleted immediately after interview transcription and substituted by a

code that only the lead researcher had access to. This was kept separately to other data to break the link between data and participant and preserve anonymity. Quotations were identified by pseudonym only, chosen by the lead researcher (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.213). Participants did not include those known to the lead researcher or others in a dependent relationship to prevent coercion. However, it is acknowledged that the lead researcher for this study was also employed as an advanced nurse practitioner at the clinic although acting as a student researcher in this role. There was the potential for participants to recognise their voice on the phone so to mitigate this the sample was recruited from a different clinic site. However, as the researcher and participant do not see each other during telephone interviews there is less chance of recognition if the participant attended the clinic in future (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.213).

Participants are often encouraged to 'share confidences' in qualitative research, and the research aim addressing the participant's sexual health in this study is of a sensitive nature (Parahoo, 2014, p.57). To mitigate any potential risk to the participant, if they had become distressed on the phone the lead researcher would stop the interview and depending on the patient's wishes provide support and signpost them to professional help. Participants were also advised of the potential long-term benefits to others of the research (Johnson and Long, 2015, p.37). If requested, the findings could be shared with the participants although IPA is unlike other qualitative research methodologies in that respondent validation is not a requirement. Participants may exhibit bias such as changing their mind about what they have said (Flick, 2018, p.558; Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.171).

4.3.4 Recruitment

A gatekeeper was identified at the sexual health clinic to monitor recruitment and assess potential risk (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.79). The study was advertised to clinic staff during a presentation given at a routine monthly internal staff training session, which is a standard format for all research projects in the workplace of the lead researcher. Potential respondents were identified beforehand as living in SIMD quintiles one and two using the address added to their electronic patient record

when their appointment was made. At the clinic appointment, clinic staff asked potential participants if they were interested in participating in the study. Patients wishing further information or to participate were provided with a Participant Information Sheet (See Appendix 12), a Stamped Addressed Envelope (SAE) and two consent forms (See Appendix 13); one for the participant and one for the lead researcher. They were also invited to provide permission for the clinician to pass on their contact details of first name, phone number and/or email address to the lead researcher. At least 24 hours later (arbitrary cooling off period), the lead researcher contacted the participant to assess their interest in participating in the study (Wilson, Draper and Ives, 2008). At recruitment, 38 respondents informed that they would be interested in this study and of these, 12 respondents agreed to participate. Next, the lead researcher arranged a convenient date and time for a single telephone interview. Once informed consent was obtained, participants were requested to complete the consent forms, keep one and post the other back to the lead researcher using the SAE.

4.3.5 Data collection tools

Data collection organises information into structure and meaning for interpretation and explanation. There are numerous methods of data collection in qualitative research with observational methods, interviews, and focus groups employed in the main utilising audio/video recording, transcripts, texts and field notes (Bryman, 2015, p.352). Focus groups are a group interview which uses the interaction between the members of the group to generate discussion and provide more detail than a one-to-one interview (David and Sutton, 2011, p.135). This group dynamic generates a large amount of data; hence they are useful for identifying complex problems and areas for further exploration (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.300; Goodman and Evans, 2015, p.409). However, one or two members may dominate the group with less vocal members of the group speaking less or acquiescing to the views of what they think the others want to hear, affecting reliability (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.214). By nature, focus groups lack confidentiality, which David and Sutton (2011, p.136) suggested reduces the disclosure of sensitive data, leading to a weakening of in-depth validity. Consequently, focus groups were discounted for this study given the sensitive

nature of sexual health. Observation involves researchers watching and recording the behaviour and activities of people in a specific environment to enable understanding of the culture (Bryman 2015, p.392; Flick, 2018, p.313). The researcher is able to see and hear how people act directly instead of relying on their descriptions, increasing reliability (Booth, 2015, p.427). The disadvantages of observation include potential observer bias such as selective memory, selective data entry or researcher inference (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.213). Observational data collection methods were deemed inapplicable for the nature of this study as the sexual aspect of participants' lives were not open to routine observation by the researcher (David and Sutton, 2011, p.159).

4.3.6 Interviews

Traditionally, phenomenological research used face to face interviews for data collection to yield semantic knowledge, focus exploration and identify concepts (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.236; Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.218). Interviews in IPA will allow the interviewer to concentrate on the complexity of the individual participant experience of PrEP, providing rich data (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.56; Polit and Beck, 2020, p.295). Interviews tend to generate data covering many subjects and enable exploration of subjects where little is already known such as PrEP, allowing for unexpected answers (Tod, 2015, p.388). Accordingly, interviews were chosen for this study over questionnaires as they have the advantage of greater depth and focus on human interaction. Interviews also enable flexibility as the researcher can explore contexts whilst allowing for more complex questions and clarification of responses and misunderstandings (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.236). The disadvantages of interviews are that they tend not to be standardised, so the interviewer has less control and not all of the same information is collected for each respondent; neither do they capture measurable phenomenon (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.504; Forbes, 2008). Interviews are a social encounter with various socio-cultural influences with the potential for researcher or participant bias where the participant may not trust or be influenced by characteristics of the interviewer and amend their answers to be socially acceptable (Nieswiadomy and Bailey, 2018, p.214). Reflexivity was important to address potential researcher

bias. An example was feedback from the pilot interview where I was required to make a concerted effort not to respond positively or negatively to what the respondent was saying. During the participant interviews I found the differences between a clinical consultation and research interviews a challenge in terms of not hurrying the interview to fit it into a 30 minute appointment timeslot, not interrupting the participant and the use of silence to allow time for the participant to consider their answer.

Qualitative interviews are unstructured, semi-structured or structured depending on the purpose and research approach selected (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.178; Parahoo, 2014, p.308). Unstructured interviews use open-ended questions to test the limits of the respondent's knowledge and allow for unexpected answers, providing in depth investigation and eliciting a larger amount of data (Polgar, 2019, p.216; Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.288). Alternatively, structured interviews involve the researcher asking a set of pre-determined, often closed, questions using the same wording as specified in an interview schedule. Semi-structured interviews are prevalent in nursing research as they involve the same number and types of question for all respondents but include flexibility with less variation, allowing for comparison between respondents in the same study and transferability to similar settings (Tod, 2015, p.391; Parahoo, 2014, p.319).

Semi-structured qualitative interviews were chosen for data collection in this study as they fit with the IPA approach, providing more depth, complexity and rich data than other tools and allowing for the explanation of relationships (Smith and Osborn, 2007). Semi structured interviews consist of specific questions and topic guides, which are outlines or guides of key issues and areas to be covered where the exact order of questions and wording can be varied (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.341). For this study, the interview questions and topic guide were informed by the research aim of understanding the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. The questions and prompts followed the research objectives and PrEP patient journey conceptual framework (section 3.3) exploring initial awareness of PrEP and 1) experience of acceptability/rationale for deciding to take it, 2) experience of clinic accessibility and adherence to PrEP and barriers/facilitators and 3) inquiry about changes to sexual behaviours and

continuation of PrEP. As IPA is idiographic, the topics and perceptions were 'funnelled' into the iterative as opposed to prescriptive topic guide (Smith, 2017) and the order of the questions depended on the course set by the individual participant. Furthermore, as the lead researcher is part of the researched world, they are knowledgeable about the subject matter and have the relevant expertise to conduct the interview in an informed manner to facilitate further meaning (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017 p.422).

For the purposes of this study, telephone interviews were chosen as virtually all of the GBMSM accessing PrEP in the West of Scotland have provided a phone number for their patient record so have access to a phone. In contrast to face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews are convenient for respondents in terms of costs, travel and time; potentially improving response rates from hard-to-reach populations (Tod, 2015, p.391). They offer safety to the researcher, provide uniformity and the comfortable location for the participant of being at home and feeling of detachment from the interviewer can enhance the response rate and sensitivity of data disclosed, which is a strength for this study investigating the sensitive nature of sexual health (Smith and Osborn, 2007). Nevertheless, the participant could hang up or experience technological difficulties or some participants may be distracted or concerned about confidentiality (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.440). Non-verbal communication is absent with telephone interviewing and participants may be less motivated to spend time concentrating on comprehensive answers (Smith and Osborn, 2007). Therefore, the date and time of the interview date was chosen by the participant in an attempt to mitigate these issues and if the participant had been distracted the interview would have been stopped and restarted at a later date. Data collection involved telephoning the participants' mobile phone device from a private room. All interviews were recorded using an audio device and interviews took fifty minutes on average to complete.

4.3.7 Pilot interview

A draft of the interview topic guide questions and prompts based on the research aim and objectives was composed by the lead researcher (See Appendix 14), (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.341; Polgar, 2019, p.85). This a priori strategy follows phenomenological study (Gentles *et al.*, 2015). Initially, socio-demographic data were collected then the respondent was requested to provide a full description of what the experience was like for them including factual details, meanings, feelings, attitudes and examples (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.218). At the end of the interview the participant was asked if there was anything else that they would like to add for thoroughness (Tod, 2015, p.393). During transcription IPA requires each interview to include non-linguistic utterances such as laughter and semantic communication such as false starts (Polgar, 2019, p.97).

The telephone interview was piloted with two colleagues who have expertise in research methods to assess the relevance and meaning of each question as it was read out (protocol analysis) (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p.268). Piloting can suggest how long the interview may take and identify problems such as misconceptions or missed questions (Tod, 2015, p.395). Peer debriefing also adds to the rigour of the study by acting as an audit mechanism to eliminate unviable questions, resolving unintended bias and allowing the researcher to reflect on their development of the interview in practice (David and Sutton, 2011, p.123). After the pilot interview a question about the risk of STIs other than HIV was added to the topic guide.

4.3.8 IPA informed thematic analysis

Initially, IPA data analysis was chosen to contextualise the interviews and develop the analysis in this study (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.73). However, it was found during the interviews that some participants were brief in their answers and despite prompting tended towards short answers and descriptions of events with less information offered about their feelings and emotions. This has been observed in other studies utilising semi-structured interviews with male participants who have been laconic, unforthcoming or terse (Affleck, Glass and MacDonald, 2012). Consequently,

the data analysis tended towards the descriptive with less linguistic and conceptual interpretation. Initial noting in the data analysis process of IPA involves three discrete focusses. Descriptive comments describe the content and subject of what the participant has said, linguistic comments focus on their specific use of language and conceptual comments refer to interpretations by the researcher (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, P.88). Nevertheless, Smith, Flowers and Larkin, (2022, p.84) explained that IPA does not have a clear right way to analyse data and the three ways of initial noting are not prescriptive but rather useful tools which the researcher could employ. The IPA approach requires flexibility and conceptual thinking to be wary of 'methodolatry' (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.40). Therefore, although the data analysis followed the same steps as IPA, it was thought that IPA-informed thematic analysis was more appropriate for this study. IPA and IPA informed thematic analysis have both been proven to be effective in healthcare settings such as comparable study of gay men's attitudes to sex and sexuality (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.135) and distress amongst General Practitioners (Spiers and Riley, 2018) respectively.

IPA emphasises and focusses on the participants' attempt to make sense of their experiences from beliefs and constructs that are made manifest in the interview (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.79). IPA suggests that the meaning participants give to their experience, in essence, becomes the experience itself because people are 'sense-making beings' (Smith, Flowers, & Larkin, 2022, p.26). Different interpretative stances are possible for the researcher and IPA combines an empathic with a questioning hermeneutic. Smith and Osborn (2007) added that qualitative analysis is a personal process for the researcher, involving dependence on and complication by the researcher's own conceptions. Hence, due to researcher preconception, IPA acknowledges that it is impossible to realise the exact personal world of the participant, however the intention is to attain an account and explanation that is as 'close' to the participant's view as possible.

In summary, the stages include:

Table 4.3: Data Analysis in IPA

1	Reading and rereading of the interview transcripts
2	Initial noting in left hand margin expressing meanings
3	Development of emerging themes. Add to right hand margin
4	Searching for connections amongst emergent themes
5	Moving to the next case
6	Looking for patterns across cases
7	Illustrate themes in detail including quotes
8	Produce narrative account to highlight meaning across cases

(Smith and Osborn, 2007)

Firstly, the interviews were immediately transcribed by the lead researcher to allow for immersion in the data. As IPA is ideographic and focusses on each participant's unique experience, interviews were analysed individually before cross case analysis (Smith, 2017). Data and 'text' was 'read' back and forth between particular details and expressions to establish the meaning as a whole and be 'in dialogue' with the literature (Galvin and Holloway, 2015, p.219) and initial comments added to the left-hand margin of each transcript (Smith and Osborn, 2007). The exploratory comments made by the researcher for each participant were initially descriptive. Here, the descriptions, assumptions, emotional responses and sayings were recorded to provide their relationship to the participant and to stay close to the participants' meaning (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.88). An example was Franks' quote 'anybody seen anywhere near the place was beelin' (section 5.5.2) to describe the embarrassment of being seen by others at a sexual health clinic. Next, interpretation of these comments was required to help understand context and how and why the participant held their view. Development of the comments and notes involved linguistic analysis, where the researcher explored the use of the participants' language to uncover abstract meanings (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.83). Linguistic comments included laughter, pronouns where participants discussed other GBMSM and repetition of certain words. Participants tended to use many filler words and sounds when

reflecting on how to respond to questions throughout the interviews (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.88).

Development of the interpretative conceptual comments was more complex and took reflection by the researcher to analyse the text through the lens of their own experience and knowledge (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.92). Parts of the text and the whole text were interpreted in relation to each other as an iterative process, which is the hermeneutic circle (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.92 and 116; Polit and Beck, 2020, p.464). The iteration of the researcher reflecting upon their own and the participant's experiences led to double hermeneutics and new interpretations of the text where the researcher made sense of the participants' making sense (Horrigan-Kelly, Millar and Dowling, 2016; Smith and Osborne, 2007). The transcripts in this study were informed by concepts such as GBMSMs experiences over their lifetimes, in comparison to other groups such as heterosexual men and emotionally. An example of this was the development of the superordinate theme regarding the PrEP clinic consultations. When Logan and Stewie described the nurses as 'fantastic', (section 5.3.1) they were potentially talking about myself, and I reflected on what this meant as I was striving to be a 'fantastic' nurse and felt satisfaction and pride when I thought I may have managed it. The sense of the meaning for myself and I believe the participant was that practitioner knowledge of sexual health through training and experience and a non-judgemental attitude, together with a familiarity and understanding of issues faced by GBMSM led to shared decision making, agency and ownership of their own healthcare for GBMSM.

Development of exploratory comments is illustrated further in table 4.4 below for a specific quote:

Table 4.4: Example of analysis of exploratory comments

Quote section 5.3.2	<i>'Every other mainstream drug it (PrEP) would have helped all these people, it should have came with a huge fanfare that everything else got and it just feels like shove it in the back door'. (Logan, p.8, line 17)</i>
Descriptive comments	Logan is describing how PrEP is comparable to other established medications as it is effective for HIV prevention, however it was not promoted and advertised in the usual/same way
Linguistic comments	The use of metaphor adds emphasis here. The word "shove" implies a rough forceful push rather than careful placing. The use of "back door" rather than front door implies PrEP being furtively hidden away and neglected as opposed to the front door which is public, formal, open to the street on display and official. Doors are also opportunities in metaphors as a way in or out of something (eg. Foot in the door) so PrEP can be seen an opportunity too
Conceptual comments	<u>Here, the treatment of PrEP reflects how GBMSM have been treated in society where stigma is used to hide them and "other" them from "mainstream" society (often noted in IPA). Hiding GBMSM and PrEP away avoids controversy in the homophobic media for example but is a continuation of discrimination for GBMSM in the present day</u>

Emergent concepts in IPA differ from traditional phenomenological analysis in that they are not demarcated as 'meaning units', or concepts of text that require an individual comment. Rather, the researcher in IPA aims to understand the content and complexity of these meanings instead of measuring their frequency as some parts of the transcript may require further attention and depiction as they offer richer data (David and Sutton, 2011, p.340). Titles of the themes were added to the right-hand margin of the transcripts (Smith and Osborn, 2007).

For the next stage of data analysis emergent data were organised into clusters and patterns to generate super-ordinate themes by methods such as abstraction, numeration, polarisation (oppositional relationships) and consideration of context and

function (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.97). A super-ordinate theme is one which usually applies to each participant but not necessarily in the same way (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.166). Examples included the use of contextualisation and the hermeneutic circle within the super-ordinate theme of Stigma, discrimination and awareness of PrEP (5.3.2), where participants had discussed how they felt discriminated against as GBMSM as PrEP had not been promoted in the same way as other 'mainstream' medications (see table 4.4). This fitted with their other experiences of HIV stigma and being treated differently to and 'othered' from the heterosexual population as described in the supporting sub themes 5.4.2 and 5.5.3. The idiographic tenet of IPA is to focus on the individual to "capture the unique" and was ensured by the inclusion of individual participants' analysis which was divergent to the other participants. Examples include Logan being the only participant who did not prefer men only clinic waiting rooms, where finding them socially awkward and uncoordinated (section 5.5.2). Similarly, all participants were confident in the efficacy of PrEP, apart from Tom who had read of a man becoming HIV positive despite good concordance (section 5.5.4).

Next, the themes were then added to a table and scrutinised on a case-by-case basis with the connections between cases examined (Smith, 2017; Smith and Osborn, 2007). Themes were counted as recurrent if they were present in over half of the sample (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.97). An example of this would be the super-ordinate theme of PrEP replacing condoms for HIV prevention (5.3.3) which involved numeration where all participants ceased or reduced their condom use due to PrEP. The subordinate group themes jointly informed and supported the super-ordinate themes but were dependent on the main concepts for their meaning.. Within the subordinate themes are sub-themes which demonstrate further the differences and similarities in the experiences between participants. Lastly, a narrative account was produced with quotations used to illustrate the themes in more detail (Lathlean, 2015, p.482; Smith and Osborn, 2007). Three superordinate and four subordinate themes were identified (see table 4.5). Appendix 15 provides an example of category and theme generation from the data. The themes/findings were confirmed by university supervisors (see Appendix 16).

Table 4.5 Table of super-ordinate and subordinate themes

Super-ordinate themes	Subordinate themes	Subordinate sub themes
Cultural competence and the role of the clinician	Socioeconomic status: health inequalities and PrEP	1: Health inequalities, vulnerabilities, culture and access to PrEP 2: Health inequalities, education, information provision and access to PrEP 3: Health inequalities and organisational/clinic barriers to accessing PrEP medication
Stigma, discrimination and awareness of PrEP	Benefits and barriers to PrEP access	1: PrEP face-to-face appointments versus telephone and postal clinic appointments 2: Sexual health service stigma and help seeking 3: HIV stigma and generational differences 4: GBMSM Rationale for PrEP uptake and use
PrEP replacing condoms for HIV prevention	GBMSM experience of taking PrEP medication	1: Dosing schedules of PrEP medication 2 Adherence and concordance to PrEP medication
	Risk Compensation: GBMSM's perceptions of PrEP and health outcomes/safety	1: The role of the 'invincible shield' 2: Risk taking behaviour, sexual partners and PrEP 3: PrEP role and other STIs

4.3.9 Reflexivity

IPA tends to use a cyclical approach to bracketing as it is recognised that researchers do not completely suspend their preconceptions (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018). However by attentive focus on the participant's words bracketing is more likely to occur as priority is given to the new information and preconceptions become apparent from this (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, pp.25,64). Therefore, reflexivity in IPA is of particular importance as the double hermeneutic and role of the researcher in interpreting the participants' sense making is a fundamental part of IPA data analysis.

Reflexivity can be explored in terms of the relationship between researcher and participant (Johnson and Long, 2015, p.34). I had been working with GBMSM in the PrEP clinics weekly since 2017 and although I had thought none of the participants were known to me I would have been unaware if I had spoken to them previously during a consultation. Being unknown to one another reduced the influences of emotional impacts for both on the findings, however there are potential power relationships regarding the interviews in this study (Hay-Smith *et al.*, 2016). In PrEP clinics the participant was asking for help from the nurse as an expert, however as an interviewing researcher I was requesting the help of the participant as an expert in their own experience. Similarly, as I was part of the researched world, role confusion can exist where participants could bring their experience of the clinic to the interview, whilst simultaneously I would have been influenced by clinical experience and professional obligations as a nurse (Gelling, 2015). This was broached by some participants who wanted confirmation that the interview was completely separate to their clinical records, however at the same time my nursing role engendered their trust in reassuring them in this regard. To avoid misplaced expectations or the interviews veering into a clinical consultation, I did not provide clinical expertise and refrained from reacting or offering advice (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p. 248). I was able to be guided by past study in counselling on the work of Carl Rogers to practice person centeredness, empathy and congruence (Thorne and Sanders, 2012) which fitted with the IPA approach (Smith, 2017). The utilisation of counselling skills such as active listening, prompting and the use of silence and reflection were helpful in striving towards empathy and congruence; although I felt conflicted with the questioning hermeneutic of IPA. Finally, I reflected on comparisons between myself and the participants, namely different genders and lack of shared experiences although similar socio-economic backgrounds (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.302). Nevertheless, I felt that although my nursing role had the potential to influence findings had I over-identified with participants or my role (Hay-Smith *et al.*, 2016), my a priori knowledge of the social context did help me to make sense of the participants' life-worlds.

4.3.10 Rigour and trustworthiness

Credibility explains the extent to which the study measures what it was actually intended to, and that the data expresses the reality of the lives of the participants (David and Sutton, 2011, p.86). Credibility in this study was achieved by utilising well established research methods, following a systematic framework, piloting the interviews and peer review to ensure that the research is congruent with the philosophical underpinnings (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.492; Polgar, 2019, p.187). Detail of decisions made around elements of the research process such as the sampling strategy and topic guide were provided for rigour as a priori knowledge and information can influence the a posteriori findings (Gentles *et al.*, 2015). Data analysis was co-analysed by the two university supervisors who have expertise in public health nursing and research methods to discuss the developing themes and to ensure that the interpretations were suitably justified by the data (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.502). This study also presented adverse and contradictory findings which refuted some of the themes (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.192). Potential issues were clarified beforehand, for example, potential participant response bias was addressed by the use of telephone interviews (Lacey, 2015, p.28).

An audit trail with a full record of all research activities was maintained to show that the research had been conducted with due care and outline the fundamental elements of the research practice. Examples of the audit trail include field notes, the coding process and rationale for arriving at the basis of a theme (David and Sutton, 2011, p.325) (see section 5.3.5). Inquirer bias was addressed using reflexivity as the researcher was part of the researched world and not going into the field as a blank slate (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.185). Researchers may have preconceptions and values about PrEP with regard to wider sociocultural and moral issues including cost, effects on sexual behaviours and that it could encourage unprotected sex (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.192; Auerbach and Hoppe, 2015). As a nurse, the lead researcher had to self-reflect critically to ensure that their experience and expertise did not lead to personal biases forming regarding patients brought into the research process. The power relationship between nurse researcher and participant was addressed by keeping to the topic guide whilst allowing for

emergent themes, not using leading questions, clarification and reflexivity as described in section 4.3.9 (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2017, p.177 and 208).

Cresswell and Cresswell (2018, p.191) explained how confirmability, or real objectivity is achieved using approaches such as triangulation and reflective commentary. Triangulation was achieved by comparing the different perspectives from participants within the individual interviews and comparison between the interviews to justify the themes and referring to the literature. Reflective commentary involved maintenance of a research diary to enable reflection and understanding of the meaning for the participant (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.504). Finally, an examination of the limitations of the study was included (Parahoo, 2014, p.120).

4.4 Chapter four summary

The methodology and study design for this research presented in this chapter were developed from the findings from the literature review in chapter two and the PrEP patient journey conceptual framework devised in chapter three; providing an explanation and justification for the design of this research. This chapter has detailed the strategy of inquiry and research methods supported by evidence and underpinned by the worldview of social constructionism. Thereafter, the decision to use IPA informed thematic analysis approach for this study was introduced, appraised and rationalised. The findings generated from the implementation of this study plan are presented in the following chapter.

Chapter five: Findings and themes

5.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the iterative IPA-informed thematic analysis of the qualitative findings generated during this study regarding the research aim of understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. Participant demographics are provided initially. Next, due to the idiographic nature of IPA, transcripts were analysed individually at first with participant experiences explored and interpreted utilising double hermeneutics. Next, transcripts were analysed across cases, identifying superordinate, subordinate and sub themes. These themes will be supported by explanatory text and participant quotations.

5.2 Participant demographics

The demographic characteristics of the twelve GBMSM participants in this study are presented in the table on the next page. All participants were taking PrEP as GBMSM who had requested PrEP but were not eligible were not included in this study as they would have low HIV risk and would not have had experience of taking NHS PrEP. Demographic information includes personal details such as age and relationship status which are relevant to personal rationale for and experiences of taking PrEP. Factors linked to deprivation such as education, employment, income and distance to the clinic (Population Health Scotland, 2020) were also included to provide further information to enable examination of variabilities and patterns of covariance and divergence within the group (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.50). For example, the participants without degrees and in the traditionally working-class professions such as joiner and postman lived in SIMD category one. None disclosed caring responsibilities or vulnerabilities, although one participant disclosed significant physical health problems and another poor mental health which he explained tended to isolate him from other people.

Table 5.6 Participant demographics

Name	SIMD	Age	Distance to clinic (miles)	Employment	Education	Income per £10,000	Length of time on PrEP	Sexuality	Relationship status	Dosing
Carl	2	31	3	Unemployed	MSc	<10	3 yrs	Gay	Bisexual	EBD
Connor	2	64	1	Healthcare, clinical pharmacist	Batchelors degree	40-50	3 yrs	Gay	Married to Roy	Daily
Ewan	2	54	5	Arts	Batchelors degree	Not given	9 mths	Gay	Single	EBD
Frank	1	58	3	Speciality joiner/truck driver	Highers	20-30	3 mths	Gay	Single	EBD
Greg	1	52	3	Postman	A levels	20-30	3.5 yrs	Gay	Single	EBD
Jamie	1	30	3	Healthcare, clinical nurse	BA	30-40	3.5 yrs	Gay	Single	Daily
Lawrence	1	55	4	Healthcare, non clinical health promotion	MSc	30-40	3 yrs	Gay	Husband + Regular Partner	Daily
Logan	1	34	4	Healthcare, clinical assistant	Batchelors degree	20-30	2 yrs	Gay	Single	EBD
Nate	1	34	8 (West HCPC)	Healthcare, clinical nurse	BSc and BA	30-40	2 yrs	Gay	Single	Daily
Roy	2	55	4	Retired	Batchelors degree	Not given	3 yrs	Gay	Married to Connor	Daily
Stewie	2	37	4	Unemployed	BSc	<10	2 yrs	Bisexual	Single	Daily
Tom	1	36	10 (North HCPC)	Communications	Not given	Not given	2 yrs	Gay	Single	Daily

5.3 Superordinate themes

5.3.1 Cultural competence and the role of the clinician

This superordinate and recurrent theme explores how the majority of participants in this study were not considering PrEP until their clinic consultation, after which they became engaged in taking it.

Participants described their initial awareness of PrEP and how they had heard about it, which links to the research objective (1) of their rationale for deciding to take PrEP as knowledge of it will be a barrier or facilitator to uptake. Some participants had heard of PrEP prior to attending the clinic as they had worked in a setting relating to healthcare. Some had heard of it vaguely 'on the grapevine' but were not aware that they were eligible for it. Other ways of hearing about PrEP initially by participants included partners and friends, work colleagues, the LGBT community, online, phone applications and newspapers. However, lack of knowledge of PrEP was a recurrent theme amongst participants in this study as many had heard of but not accessed it. For example, Ewan had heard of PrEP at work in healthcare but felt too 'uncertain' to start taking it:

'Uncertainty on all levels. Not sure that if I, I understood it correctly, the, what it was actually doing ... what it says it can do. The majority of my friends don't take it ... can you trust this, is it some kind of new-fangled thing that they might find out whatever' (Ewan, p.1, line 13)

Carl highlighted that this lack of knowledge around PrEP was actually commonplace amongst GBMSM and described 'ignorance' around what it did:

'They know that it (PrEP) exists but maybe they don't know all the details of how it works what it protects you and what it doesn't. I think still in the in the LGBT community there's still ignorance in terms of sexual health, not knowing' (Carl, p.3, line 18)

Lack of awareness of PrEP led to only three participants in this study attending the sexual health clinic specifically to request PrEP. The other participants had not requested PrEP but been informed at their consultation that they were eligible and after discussion had decided to start taking PrEP because 'it was there'.

'No' intentionally, er, but I remember I was down getting my 3 months check-up ... it was'nae like forced upon me, ... the nurse said have a chat about it you know but sex-wise and my preferences and she says to me it's something that you should think about ... so I says well I'm gonnae take it then, it was there' (Greg, p.1, line 23)

Frank, had never heard of PrEP before attending the sexual health clinic because he had symptoms and only became aware of PrEP when he was offered it at his clinic visit.

'The reason I went onto PrEP is during the lockdown I actually thought I had an STI, ... and apparently it wasn't an STI. So, at the time then during the conversation the consultant says maybe he says maybe the thing is if you if you start using PrEP.' (Frank, p.1, line 14)

When reflecting on why he may not have heard of PrEP before his clinic visit, Frank explained that he only met strangers at 'cruising areas'¹ which were 'impersonal' as there was no conversation between potential partners. Additionally, he was one of the few participants who did not attend sexual health services regularly or LGBT venues such as bars and clubs so was not part of the 'gay scene'. Therefore, he felt that he was one of the GBMSM who had missed out on obtaining sexual health information such as PrEP because he did not attend these places and groups.

'I'd never heard of it, no. I really just go cruising, so it's usually just it's strangers I meet up with ... there's no conversation ... its quite impersonal. You're there for a reason and that's it.' (Frank, p.2, line 1)

¹ 'Cruising areas' are public places which have a reputation for MSM meeting for anonymous sexual encounters (Frankis and Flowers, 2006)

Frank rarely had a sexual health screen and had not attended sexual health services for years. Not knowing what to expect at the clinic contributed to his anxiety and stress. Frank described worries about being asked personal questions by clinicians during the consultation. However, this concern was alleviated by supportive and knowledgeable staff.

'The first time I was in (clinic name), I didn't know what to expect but I must admit they were brilliant they put me at ease and every time that he asked a question they explained why they were asking it; anything he spoke about he explained in great detail, asked me if I understood and if I didn't he explained it even more'. (Frank, p.2, line 15)

A recurrent theme in this study was that participants praised the staff in the clinic:

'the staff that I have come across have been fantastic and very open and I think that also encourages folk that take PrEP to be a lot more open'. (Nate, p.8, line 9)

'the nurses they're fantastic....because they provide you with everything you need to know in a really really digestible way'. (Logan, p.12, line 25)

However, outside of sexual health services, participants explained that healthcare staff were generally not so knowledgeable about PrEP. Logan provided an experience of healthcare professionals in other settings who had not heard of PrEP:

'She was like what's PrEP, and this was ... a registered nurse within a hospital ... and the doctor came in and she was like have you heard of this? And he was like, well I've never heard of it ... so see if I was just a wee opportunistic closet gay that had this chance with the nurse to say, and she didn't know about it' (Logan, p.8, line 10)

Here, the lack of professional knowledge of PrEP had ensured that healthcare staff had missed the opportunity to suggest PrEP to an eligible patient. Participants responses about their experiences corresponded, concurring that awareness of PrEP in the NHS should be raised to the same level of awareness of HIV and AIDS and that PrEP required further advertising and promotion within healthcare.

5.3.2 Stigma, discrimination and awareness of PrEP

This superordinate and recurrent theme represents how participants felt that HIV stigma and discrimination prevented the NHS from promoting PrEP so GBMSM had subsequently promoted it to each other instead. This links to the research aim and objective (2) around barriers and facilitators to accessibility and acceptability PrEP in this study.

Respondents acknowledged that as awareness of PrEP outside of sexual health settings and the 'gay scene' was lacking, further advertising and promotion were required. Advertising PrEP at community events and organisations such as Gay Pride, adverts on mobile phone applications, pubs, clubs, colleges, universities and even schools and television were suggested by participants as solutions.

'at Pride ... going mainstream because everyone and their granny wants to jump on the back of Pride now. It should have been analysed and delivered in a positive uplifting way to combat that still echoing stigma against HIV' (Logan, p.11, line 21)

Frank recommended that health promotion staff target cruising areas in cities with leaflets and engage the men in conversation about HIV risk and PrEP.

"every city's got its it's well-known cruising spots and maybe get people who are from either the clinic or people involved ... to go out and about in the community and speaking to people in these areas" (Frank, p.9, line 2)

Participants felt that marketing PrEP similarly to other medications would appreciably combat the stigma and shame of HIV as instead of a 'huge fanfare' PrEP was 'shoved in the back door'.

'When it got rolled out ... every other mainstream drug it would have helped all these people, it should have come with a huge fanfare that everything else got and it just feels like shove it in the back door.' (Logan, p.8, line 17)

'You don't see PrEP advertised, unless you maybe go into the clinic for instance, it may be there but it's not advertised not gonnae say the TV, but there's something they're missing ... it's not widely known.' (Greg, p.9, line 1)

This lack of knowledge of PrEP was felt to be even more pronounced amongst people who were not GBMSM. Participants described many heterosexual friends or colleagues who had either never heard of PrEP or assumed that it was a 'gay drug' aimed only at GBMSM.

'it's the gay scene it's kind of more accepted whereas if it was the heterosexual side of things, I don't know whether they would be so accepting of it (PrEP).' (Connor, p.4, line 25)

'I'm not going to use that because it's for gay people.' (Logan, p.14, line 1)

Other participants highlighted the lack of awareness in relation to sexual health and PrEP information available outside the 'gay scene' in a different way:

'In the gay community I would say yes, but otherwise outwith that its sort of people who are sort of dipping their feet in the water don't know about it, younger ones, or as I say some guys that are married dabble. A lot of people aren't in the scene' (Greg, p.11, line 18)

Several participants described meeting a significant number of men married to women but having sex with men who were not aware of or accessing PrEP. These men were generally attempting to conceal their lifestyles and sexual encounters from their female partners and were 'never going to access PrEP'. Participants were concerned about HIV risk to the partners.

'it's not something that they would even consider so the men who have sex with men that I've had sex with, men who have other partners, married men, they're not going to access PrEP. They're never going to access PrEP.' (Lawrence, p.10, line 10)

'Married men out there as well they come online a lot if they're interested in this and that, and they've never heard of it as well. I would say they're very naïve to it because obviously they're trying to be in the closet ... a lot of them are like, what the hell's PrEP?' (Greg, p.6, line 16)

The lack of publicity around PrEP impeded not only PrEP awareness but also the fact that it is free from the NHS:

'a lot of people... have just not been aware that you could just get it for free' (Stewie, p.4, line 13)

'there are still people within 2021 in the UK that don't know that they can get a free prescription for this medication (PrEP)' (Logan, p.9, line 16)

Logan said that if he had seen PrEP mentioned in the media it was in a negative sense:

'Never mainstream, ... it will only be within a maybe sub thing that I'm watching it's been gay-made... about how like expensive it (PrEP) is in America and in Ireland ... anytime it is spoken about it's in a negative way ... so maybe don't touch it.' (Logan, p.9, line 26)

Nevertheless, a recurrent theme in this study was that many participants felt that PrEP medication had encouraged more conversation and negotiation between casual partners around sexual health as GBMSM would often ask if their potential partners were taking PrEP:

'We do tend to talk about sex things more often, and you know them, they're going to be a bottom, so they're going to be more concerned about transmission than I would be as a top as anyway. So, then they tend to be on PrEP and talk about it more.' (Stewie, p.3, line 28)

'If you see someone and you think oh yeah, I'd like to have some fun PrEP always comes into it whether I raise it or somebody else raises it. But it's always in the conversation' (Roy, p.4, line 2)

GBMSM who were taking PrEP often promoted it by encouraging other eligible men to take it which appeared to increase general awareness of PrEP amongst GBMSM.

This is a recurrent theme in this study.

'People we have spoke to, they have gone on it because we have spoke about it.' (Roy, p.6, line 6)

Lawrence had worked in healthcare and felt that he had a 'duty' to the health service to ensure the success of PrEP:

'There was also felt to be a community duty to be a success with this, (PrEP) that its appreciated' (Lawrence, p. 6, line 23)

5.3.3 PrEP replacing condoms for HIV prevention

This superordinate and recurrent theme explores how all participants in this study had replaced condoms for PrEP for HIV prevention and felt under pressure to have condomless sex. This links with the research aim and objective (3) of insight into sexual health behaviours of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in the light of PrEP.

Risk taking sexual behaviour amongst GBMSM can be explained by behaviours such as not using condoms, having anal rather than oral sex which carries a higher risk of STI's, more sexual partners, group sex or not asking partners if they have had a recent sexual health screen (see section 1.6). Participants felt that any behaviour changes regarding sexual risk-taking due to taking PrEP involved calculated risk and responsibility for their choices. Behaviour changes included not liking to use condoms for various reasons such as erectile dysfunction and lack of sensation.

'No one likes using condoms anyway, everyone hates it. They feel gross, and it's like sometimes it takes ages to get it on ... you're getting fickle erections because you're fiddling around with condoms ... you're in the moment, and like condoms are this weird manky slimy thing. It's not sexy.' (Stewie, p.4, line 1)

'I suppose it's that old saying that people don't like going in the bath with their socks on.' (Roy, p.2, line 29)

Consequently, all participants said that because they had started taking PrEP, their condom use had either greatly reduced or ceased which was a recurrent theme in this study. Most of the participants had stopped using condoms altogether because they felt that the risk of HIV was acceptably low with PrEP. The other participants who had

significantly reduced their condom use only used a condom if the partner had requested that they did or would stop using condoms a lot sooner with a new partner due to taking PrEP. Hence, participants agreed that condom users were in the minority amongst GBMSM taking PrEP:

'I just feel that you know if you feel by taking PrEP there's more opportunity to have bareback sex' (Roy, p.2, line 17)

'It makes logical sense doesn't it, with everybody not using condoms, since everyone hates them in the first place, the first opportunity to not die from taking them off, everyone is going to take it. In terms of society, I'd say it's made guys way more willing to have unprotected sex.' (Stewie, p.7, line 13)

Conversely, Tom described hearing about a man who had contracted HIV despite taking PrEP correctly, which had made him more likely to use a condom.

'People are talking about the legal things, what other safeguards are going to get put in place, what other kind of things can we do to protect ourselves' (Tom, p.3, line 10)

A recurrent theme in this study was that PrEP use instead of condoms had now become normalised amongst GBMSM for HIV prevention and PrEP was 'here for the masses'.

'I think at first when PrEP came here ... maybe had a bit of a negative approach ... sleeping around or people were dirty, or you know the stigma that comes with HIV in a sense but in a different way. I think it's now it's become the norm ... it's here now for the masses.' (Jamie, p.3, line 23)

'The condom users seem to be in the minority since PrEP came out ... if you want to use a condom and you're on PrEP what's the point' (Logan, p.3, line 22)

Indeed, PrEP use has become so acceptable and customary that some participants described how potential partners would not have sex with them if they were not on PrEP and that there was a stigma in not taking it.

'I think there's stigma for people who don't take it. Um, there has been comments in the past, that they have been asked prior to any intercourse, are you on PrEP, and the answer has been no, and the other person has said Well, we'll not be meeting up or we won't go home together etc. because they don't feel safe to go with this person who's not on that medication.' (Tom, p.6, line 2)

Consequently, some participants such as Roy had decided to take PrEP specifically to be 'included' to be sexually active with other GBMSM. He would have used condoms otherwise:

'Most people who wanted to have sex were not prepared to have sex unless you were prepared to do it without a condom. And at that point you kind of felt that you were eliminated because you weren't prepared to participate in that. So ... it was basically a decision that, to be inclusive ... so that you weren't left out.' (Roy, p.2, line 1)

Following on from this, Connor wondered if this development towards condomless sex with PrEP would put more GBMSM under pressure not to use condoms without PrEP:

'I had noticed before we went on it (PrEP) that more and more people were preferring not to use a condom which is something that we would have never done ... other people who are not on it whether they would then take the chance and have unprotected sex or whether they would ... tell them no or would you just go with the flow.' (Connor, p.5, line 20)

Greg highlighted this general reduction in condom use in a different way, explaining that he became angry with GBMSM who were having unprotected sex and not taking PrEP:

'I get a bit angry. Er if they're asking me for sex and its bareback and they're not on it (PrEP) that really pisses me off. I say no, no that's not right definitely not you shouldn't be doing that.' (Greg, p.10, line 15)

5.4 Subordinate theme 1: Socioeconomic status: health inequalities and PrEP

This subordinate theme relates to structural and individual inequalities due to deprivation which links to the research aim and objective (2) regarding barriers to availability, accessibility and acceptability of PrEP.

5.4.1 Sub theme: Health inequalities, vulnerabilities, culture and access to PrEP

Participants expressed their perceptions of the factors underpinning health inequalities and access to health services. Vulnerabilities, such as alcohol and substance use issues for example, were considered a key reason that would impede GBMSMs access to PrEP. Connor, Logan and Nate did not share personal experience of vulnerabilities but did have experience of working in healthcare with vulnerable adults. From their experience they perceived that GBMSMs with substance use issues may find it challenging to access services due to deprivation, homelessness or the nature of their chaotic lives impacting on uptake and adherence to PrEP:

‘They’re homeless ... they probably have no structure in their day to day lives, and if they are still using ... one day just blurs into the next so they’re not sure if they’ve taken it or not.’ (Connor, p.4, line 33)

Vulnerability also extended in relation to other groups and communities due to issues around acceptability, inclusion or cultural differences. Lawrence had experience of working with marginalised communities and highlighted that some specific cultural groups such as some refugees or travelling communities may face challenges in attending clinics to access PrEP. He provided his perception on these challenges, which included aspects of financial acceptability and accessibility of PrEP services.

‘For people with no recourse to public funding, there’s definitely an inclusion health aspect and there might be gaps in availability or accessibility and that’s where those are people whos’ rights are being overlooked’ (Lawrence, p.10, line 27)

‘The cultural determinant default in some populations were that ... you don’t go near your general practice because it’s not seen as safe and you have to queue up and you have to go to hospital’ (Lawrence, p.10, line 17)

A significant number of participants added that they had chosen to take PrEP because it was free and cost effective to the NHS.

'It's a good thing it's made available for people for free without having to pay for it or anything like that' (Frank, p.3, line 6)

Health inequalities were also linked to discussions around the efficiency of the medical model and concerns around this type of care not meeting patients' needs, particularly those from socioeconomic diverse backgrounds. PrEP was not a 'magical bullet'.

'The biomedical solution and that theory of magical thinking about it being a magical bullet when what happens is if you don't address the inequalities, (that cause HIV infection) people will be left behind' (Lawrence, p.9, line 18)

5.4.2 Sub theme: Health inequalities, education, information provision and access to PrEP

The qualitative findings in this study may demonstrate a relationship between educational attainment, deprivation quintile and knowledge and uptake of PrEP amongst the 12 participants. For example, Lawrence from SIMD quintile two who was educated to postgraduate degree level informed that all GBMSMs he had met were aware of PrEP, and almost all were taking it. This may highlight that being educated to Masters' degree level and living in SIMD quintile two may potentially affect his knowledge and awareness of sexual health issues and PrEP.

'So ... I'm middle aged, white affluent you know, intelligent, so the question also for PrEP I think is ... who is not finding this accessible?' (Lawrence, p.9, line 20)

Respondents from disadvantaged areas were considered in relation to 'working class' professions. Some participants from SIMD quintile one such as Greg said that they had been speaking to a significant number of other GBMSMs who were having condomless sex and were unaware of PrEP.

'I'll say well I'm on PrEP, are you, and then the person will say ... naively oh what's PrEP, and I you don't know about PrEP, ... because ... you're into bareback (condomless sex)' (Greg, p.5, line 1)

Sexual health information provision was discussed in relation to level of education and historical viewpoints and practices. Participants inferred that a lack of sexual education in schools compounded the way that sexual health information was shared which consequently impacted on HIV literacy. Logan, who was aged in his mid 30s, described the Section 28 legislation in place from 1988 to 2000 which meant that teachers could be convicted for providing sex education for GBMSMs. Therefore, GBMSMs were not 'allowed' to receive the same quality of sex education as their heterosexual counterparts and consequently the sexual health information provided was 'the blind leading the blind'.

'The whole Section 28 thing back in the day. Information wasn't the best and it wasn't regulated because it was done via like in a club or a pub or a dark room ... very much behind closed doors ... the blind leading the blind through something where you're not actually allowed to be educated on it within school ... because your teacher had the fear of going to jail. Your heterosexual counterparts would have had it regulated and taught in school' (Logan, p.3, line 4)

Frank's age was in his late 50s and he described how HIV information provision was also scarce and impeded by the lack of open societal discussion in comparison to the 1980s:

'It was just always STIs and chlamydia. I never really gave HIV a second thought. It doesn't really get the publicity it used to ... you couldn't turn on the TV or pick up a newspaper without there being a story about it people were terrified of it' (Frank, p.3, line 12).

Participants felt that historical scarce knowledge and a lack of open discussion impacted on young GBMSM's understandings of HIV. For example, Greg was in his early 50s and found that younger GBMSMs lacked knowledge around the AIDS epidemic in the 1980s and this, together with not being privy to HIV societal discussion/information, contributed to HIV health illiteracy. Consequently, younger GBMSMs were less likely to have heard of PrEP.

'A lot of these younger ones in their 20s and that at times are a bit naïve when it comes to like PrEP, a few of them are scared. Younger people don't know about it, I mean when I mention the (clinic name), what's that' (Greg, p.6, line 25)

Lack of knowledge had also created a sense of invincibility, particularly in younger GBMSMs as there was medication to treat HIV. Here, Roy and Connor as older GBMSM (aged late 50s and mid 60s) were reflecting on younger GBMSM:

'Younger people in general ... think they're invincible. you know I've got a whole life ahead of me, even if I catch something (HIV), there's still medication out there, I'm not going to die of it probably.' (Roy, p.6, line 23)

'The gay community is probably quite educated about it (PrEP) apart from ... the youngsters thinking they're indestructible.' (Connor, p.4 line 9)

Even Nate, who was in his mid 30s, expanded on this further, describing younger GBMSMs than himself as not only lacking in sexual health knowledge but being too immature to discuss the issues around HIV risk:

'The younger generation nowadays I don't think they pay much attention to the to the risks ... but obviously the education side of things, that maybe needs to be a bit more ramped up' (Frank, p.7, line 10)

'I just don't think there's that same seriousness around HIV and AIDS as what there was back then ... I just don't think it was spoken about as much now as possibly what it should be, especially the younger folk who don't necessarily understand fully exactly the sort of risks they are putting themselves under' (Nate, p.4, line 23)

Nate felt that young people obtained sexual health information from each other or online rather than school as information from the internet was a large part of their lives:

'I think social media, facebook, instagram, whatever else, um they probably get a lot of information from there' (Nate, p.5, line 2)

And engaging in sexual risk-taking behaviour:

'the young ones ... they're on bloody all these drugs now.' (Ewan, p.8, line 11)

Participants suggested that targeting schools, colleges and universities with sexual health information would be possible solutions.

'there's still a bit of stigma attached to it, but I think that younger people are more promiscuous than back in my timeline so I think maybe target schools colleges universities things like that so do talks, or just get pamphlets.' (Frank, p.7, line 13)

Again, participants described meeting some men who are married to women and concealing the fact that they had sex with men. This was not the personal experience of any participants in this study, however meant that these men were unlikely to attend sexual health services.

'I'm not really on the gay scene I know there's lots of people who for whatever reason say they're not gay, they're just bisexual or whatever, and those I've met lots of guys who are married, relationships with female partners, so for them they're not really want to be seen in these kind of places (sexual health clinics).' (Frank, p.4, line 27)

5.4.3 Sub theme: Health inequalities and organisational/clinic barriers to accessing PrEP medication

Organisational factors were prominent in the discussions relating to PrEP availability and accessibility due to the requirement for an appointment and consultation at the sexual health clinic every three months. To date, PrEP is only available from one sexual health clinic site in the Scottish city NHS health board. In some instances, respondents felt that GBMSM were 'penalised' when their unsociable working hours did not fit with the clinic opening times. Other reasons cited were being on zero hours contracts or in insecure employment and not being allowed time off for health appointments.

'I've got a lot of friends ... because of the shift pattern they do, they can't always get to the clinic it's not fair to people who are on that twilight hours in retail, hospitality, entertainment, and because of the hours they work they're getting penalised because they can't access these services.' (Tom, p.5, line 21)

Barriers to accessing sexual health services were also linked to the location of the sexual health clinic. GBMSM living at a greater geographical distance from the clinic without access to a car and dependent on public transport may find attending the clinic problematic:

'My friends ... can't get, access it ... because of the location of the centre and they're not able to commute. So, it is pretty central within the city centre but if you are in (West) or if you're in (Far West) it's difficult to get there on public transport because you have to get into the city centre and then get back out to the West End.' (Tom, p.6, line 13)

Stewie, who is currently unemployed, explained how after Covid-19 covid his local clinic had closed and the central clinic was further away and more difficult to attend:

'Getting hold of it is difficult, with needing to go to the (clinic name). I don't live near....before the pandemic there was a place down here...that was actually just...near my doctors...so that wasn't much of a difficulty' (Stewie, p.3, line 21)

It was agreed that even for those with access to a car, travelling to the clinic for the PrEP appointment could be problematic with issues such as traffic on the motorway and poor parking facilities. Participants suggested that PrEP being available from pharmacies as well as sexual health services would provide easier access, particularly if the person was running out of medication:

'It would be good if we could get it on repeat prescription at the pharmacy for example just to make it more accessible. ... I think in certain emergency circumstances if you run out and you can't get to the appointment ... there's maybe a way of getting maybe not a full tub but a certain amount just to survive you through' (Jamie, p.2, line 20)

Or accessing PrEP from the GP:

'Why is it not available within a GP who knows your medical history and has seen you possibly since you were born? They have all the facilities to do all the testing that the (clinic name) do anyway.' (Tom, p.5, line 21)

Connor disclosed that he was a pharmacist. He described colleagues as having a low awareness of PrEP but added that he personally would consider dispensing it from a community pharmacy:

'I don't think my colleagues could sit down and have a discussion with someone about the pros and cons of taking PrEP ... because they don't feel it's their responsibility. I would be quite happy ... I would have to see the test results that they were fine or to be doing the tests, yeah. The protocol for it.' (Connor, p.3, line 32)

5.5 Subordinate theme 2: Benefits and barriers to PrEP access

This subordinate theme relates to the research aim and objectives (2) and (1) of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation experiences of barriers and facilitators to accessibility and acceptability of PrEP and their rationale for taking it.

5.5.1 Sub theme: PrEP face-to-face appointments versus telephone and postal clinic appointments

Telephone and virtual appointments for PrEP are alternatives to attending the clinic for face-to-face consultations; and may help to address some of the issues around clinic accessibility faced by GBMSM described in the previous section such as geographical location and appointment times (section 5.4.3). However, patients taking PrEP are still required to complete the three-monthly sexual health screen and appropriate kidney function blood testing. The appointment is specific; patients cannot obtain PrEP at a routine check-up appointment, which was an issue for some participants. Prior to COVID-19, all PrEP appointments were face to face and some participants still preferred the personal contact of these consultations as they felt reassured by the direct contact with the clinician. Lawrence suggested that during these appointments it was easier to ask questions as interaction was better with some things best said in person and there was time for reflection. Condoms could also be picked up at the same time.

'The practitioner can read and engage ... face to face does provide a wee bit more reflection time and a wee bit more consideration of my circumstance. it gives me a slight assurance ... if I got a physical check in ... rather than just dispensing.' (Lawrence, p.3, line 22)

Roy preferred the convenience of face-to-face appointments in comparison to phone appointments:

'You get a text message, then you have to book it online then you have to wait for somebody to phone you, and then of course if you don't catch that phone call and then you've missed the next one ... a lot of numbers come through as 0800 ... I had to wait 10 days for the phone call. And then had to wait ... when they sent the stuff out ... we prefer going to the clinic. You know, get it all done at the one time.' (Roy, p.5, line 4)

He felt that the introduction of remote appointments was due to financial constraints:

'Cutbacks....When services start to go online like or by phone, what they're doing is they reduce the staff needed within the clinic. So the staff get redeployed I would rather they had the staff on.' (Roy, p.8, line 29)

During the COVID-19 pandemic, face-to-face appointments ceased. Other participants preferred the substitute telephone appointments for PrEP as they were anonymous, straightforward, faster and did not run over time, which had been an issue in the past.

'I think both ways are efficient but the phone consultation is a lot quicker and logistically that's probably better' (Carl, p.2, line 15)

Participants also discussed the use of postal kits to conduct the health screens, with the added service of PrEP medication being posted out. The following participant described challenges around obtaining blood for the required test.

'In terms of the actual STI check I prefer to go and get my blood taken because it's an absolute nightmare taking it myself. Me squeezing my finger over that vial for, like, 40 minutes, and like, totally trying to prick it and, like, er, yes, pain.' (Stewie, p.3, line 12)

Nevertheless, most described the convenience of having the medication posted out to them and the fact that they received a generous supply. For Nate, telephone and postal PrEP services were a facilitator to access and acceptability of PrEP.

'Just the convenience of here's the whole testing kit, on you go and do it, the post-box is literally at the bottom of my street, ... because I work 9 to 5 ... some people maybe struggled with the pinpricking themselves and whatever else but with having a nurse's background I find that dead easy' (Nate, p.3, line 10)

5.5.2 Sub theme: Sexual health service stigma and help seeking

Organisational barriers extended to the stigma which still exists for individuals around the acceptability of sexual health services. This is in addition to the HIV stigma discussed in section 5.3.2 and 5.5.3 and PrEP stigma in section 5.3.3. Lack of awareness of sexual health services was described as a barrier to PrEP access, particularly amongst younger GBMSM. Concern about confidentiality was also a consistent theme in this study with some participants describing registering at clinic reception as being a barrier to the acceptability of sexual health services for example.

'The reception that's where you pass your information on, they had seats about 4 feet away, ... you had to shout your name ... and I'm hard of hearing ... so I had to shout louder! My husband was there yesterday ... and he had to shout his name from the top of the stairs to reception. It can put people off'. (Roy, p.8, line 8)

Other respondents discussed the issue of confidentiality in relation to embarrassment and fear of being seen in the clinic and/or being identified and judged.

'Obviously a lot of people hear jokes and stories about these places ... if you're seen walking in, everybody knows the place oh they're going to say they're going in there obviously they must have something ... so anybody seen anywhere near the place was beelin'' (Frank, p.8, line 1)

'I've met people that have never been for a sexual health test in their life ... I just think that those people I know they just they feel dead embarrassed or scared to go in or in case maybe bump into someone know.' (Jamie, p.2, line 25)

The issue of having PrEP appointments within GBMSM only clinics resulted in some men feeling more comfortable being in the waiting room with other men, which they may have seen as a way to maintain confidentiality.

'All men together, generally gay and gay men right. People might feel more comfortable with that rather than going to a clinic with both sexes there and people there for different reasons.' (Roy, p.8, line 24)

In contrast, Logan felt that GBMSM only clinics were seen as less important compared to heterosexual health and felt like an 'afterthought':

'That's a bit rubbish, ... you can have this little space once a week in the heterosexual world so it still kind of feels disjointed ... shove it in there ... you're all herded into the one place, and it's really uncomfortable ... that in itself just feels like an afterthought' (Logan, p.10, line 30)

Confidentiality concerns were also highlighted in terms of families and partners becoming aware of GBMSM health status via medical records documentation. This was not an issue for any of the participants in this study but was for GBMSM they had met who were concealing their sexuality. A lack of awareness of the confidentiality of sexual health services was identified as a barrier to acceptability for these men.

'There's families and things like that involved with partners don't want to have anything in their medical records ... the other partner may accidentally find out about. Confidentiality is a big issue. If you've not actually used the facilities then you won't know about it if nobody's spoken to you or explained you what the place is all about' (Frank, p.5, line 2)

5.5.3 Sub theme: HIV stigma and generational differences

In addition to stigma around PrEP and sexual health (see sections 5.3.2 and 5.5.2), stigma and discrimination around sexuality and HIV can subsequently lead to health inequalities for GBMSMs. A recurrent theme in this study was that all participants agreed that HIV stigma was a consideration in relation to acceptability and accessibility of PrEP. Participants divided GBMSM into three age generations and explained that HIV stigma and sexual experience related differently to each. The older generations consisted of GBMSM who had lived through the AIDS epidemic (see section 1.7); the younger generations who had not; and those in between. Logan is aged in his mid 30s and feels 'in between'.

'When I see older generations, um I've got a couple of friends that say maybe I'll take that (PrEP) but still I'll always use a condom and I'll never not. Then you've got this younger generation that are like what is HIV?' (Logan, p.5, line 16)

Generational differences also influenced respondents' perceptions of HIV transmission. Those who had experienced the fear and stigma of the AIDS epidemic such as these participants were more likely to be concerned about the risk of HIV transmission.

'I just remember it being really like oh no, you don't touch them people, all the gays are dying' (Logan, p.4, line 29)

'It was really really scary how people were just dropping like flies' (Stewie, p.6, line 7)

Many GBMSMs had linked generational differences to fear and stigma, which influenced their sexual activity and behaviours. Lawrence is aged in his mid 50s:

'I was always quite phobic about anal sex. Such was the sort of stigma and the anxiety about it' (Lawrence, p.4, line 16)

Logan also reflected in depth on how the 'absolute petrifying' fear of HIV had affected sex and relationships amongst GBMSM in a different negative way; intersecting with the stigma of homosexuality and pushing sexual contact between men underground, affecting how they viewed sex and relationships.

'The stigma which then reinforces the absolute petrifying fear that you are going to catch this (HIV) just purely through having sex with someone so ... you couldn't really lose yourself in it ... it wasn't an authentic just having sex it was always partnered with that kind of little niggle of this could potentially provide you with a life sentence' (Logan, p.2, line 10)

'which then gives you this strange outlook on sex. You don't find gay guys saying I want to make love to you it's because sex partnered with fear ... you'll probably get better received as I want to fuck you ... It's a very hyper sexed community ... because it's pushed underground and your interaction has to be pretty quick and fast so you're just going to have that gratification then get out.' (Logan, p.5, line 12)

Generational differences also extended to HIV stigma and sexual orientation. The following excerpts highlight these differences in relation to heterosexual, gay and younger people. These respondents are in their 50s and 30s, so in their words, older and in between respectively; however none of the participants in this study defined themselves as young.

'I think straight people are more judgemental, especially if they are ill-informed, or this whole thing that gay men are much more promiscuous which is a load of bollocks.' (Roy, p.7, line 2)

Conversely, one participant felt that HIV stigma came from the gay community due to lack of education:

'It can be quite vicious, and I find that the majority of stigma's from the gay community and not from people outside it. especially with HIV things. That's just because people are not educated.' (Jamie, p.4, line 22)

Another felt that HIV stigma came from older rather than younger people:

'Some older people are stuck in their ways, shun gays. There is still even guys in their 50s that are very kinda like you know if he's gay I don't want to go near him ... the ones that are lower 30s, 20-odd, 30, 40, they don't bother their backside' (Greg, p.5, line 8)

In accordance with this generational theme, some participants agreed that HIV stigma still exists today, however others were unsure (see section 1.4). Ewan felt that older GBMSM may be resentful that PrEP was not available when they were younger:

'Some people have it (PrEP) like a get out of jail free card and it's almost that bitterness of thinking you should go what we went through ... so I think there is a wee bit of a stigma attached from the older generation towards the younger generation about using it (PrEP)' (Ewan, p.7, line 25)

Generational differences were also described with regard to the younger generation. For example, this group were having more unprotected sex with more partners in comparison to older GBMSM, partly due to the rise of internet dating. Connor is older aged in his early 60s and Logan aged in between:

'If you listen to the young guys maybe it has changed from when I was that age. But ... you've also got the rise of the internet. And easy access to sex basically whenever you want it. I don't know whether it's just society's changed as a whole er or it's just a lot easier for the youngsters to hook up nowadays.' (Connor, p.3, line 10)

'The younger ones being so kind of like obsessed, not obsessed but so kind of like entrenched with raw and bare back (condomless sex) and stuff like that because the fear (of HIV) for them, they didn't really have to deal with that' (Logan, p.4, line 13)

An example of this shift to reduced HIV stigma was the recent television series 'It's A Sin' about the AIDS epidemic set in the 1980s. A few participants spoke in positive terms about this, suggesting that it helped to combat HIV stigma as it did not 'other' GBMSM from the rest of the population.

'Its quite positive where that narrative has never been spun with HIV before and it's always been nasty, down, disgusting and other that; you have that mainstream that needs to be othered to keep us safe from it.' (Logan, p.4, line 30)

Another recurrent theme in this study was that all participants agreed that culturally, HIV stigma has lessened over the years and the general views in society around sexuality and HIV have changed over time to becoming more open and accepting of GBMSM. This leaves young GBMSM of today with less shame about their sexuality than had been experienced by those in the past. Frank is in his mid 60s and Jamie is the youngest participant in this study at age 30:

'In my younger days it still wasn't accepted there was still a lot of stigma attached if somebody was gay or bi ... there was a lot of kinda I wouldn't say shame, but people just didn't want the hassle but I think today is more accepting' (Frank, p.6, line 28)

'Nowadays it's everything's more open, you got nonbinary and things now you never used to have that. Maybe with that generation the stigmas going to I think that will kind of go away' (Jamie, p.4, line 29)

5.5.4 Sub theme: GBMSM Rationale for PrEP uptake and use

The rationale for taking PrEP is research objective (1) in this study and participants were clear about their rationale for taking PrEP medication. Respondents considered the main benefit/quality of PrEP to be reducing the chances of contracting HIV via unprotected sex, which was a recurrent theme in this study.

'Sex doesn't have to be partnered with this constant fear of impending doom'
(Logan, p.1, line 22)

Greg added that PrEP was also seen as a second line of defence, for example, protecting against HIV risk from unplanned episodes of unprotected sex or when condoms had broken or fallen off, therefore reducing the worry of contracting HIV.

'When you end up back somewhere drunken sort of night sort of thing and you knew the next day you slept with someone and never used anything and there was always that worry again ... but now that I'm on it (PrEP) I know I'm fine'
(Greg, p.10, line 7)

Further reasons to commence PrEP were an unrelated health scare or being diagnosed with a STI. Nate had started taking PrEP after PEPSE for an episode of unprotected sex that he had been concerned about.

'I just hadn't really done much sort of um research but after the PEP they had sort of recommended that um PrEP would be a viable option for myself' (Nate, p.1, line 18)

The worry of contracting HIV was extended further in terms of media coverage of a man who had become HIV positive despite taking PrEP correctly, which was cited by Tom as a concern about efficacy with condomless sex.

'That man, you know he's been on it since he was 16, 16 or 18, and has now tested (HIV) positive ... its brought up a lot of conversations about it within the gay community' (Tom, p.2, line 28)

The issue of PrEP quality and toxicity was frequently raised in this study. In the following quotes, respondents discuss their anxiety about taking a new medication and concerns about potential side effects, although for some participants the kidney function test provided reassurance.

'I was also a bit anxious, it was a new thing, a medication, so I don't know if I want to take, I was slightly reluctant about taking medication on daily basis, so I felt that, knowing that there's also a bit of toxicity and stuff' (Carl, p.1, line 20)

'I think people might be scared of what it will do to their body. I think the same with any medication that you can take I think some people might be a bit afraid of um you know what it will do to their insides.' (Jamie, p.5, line 4)

Although not a common theme, the issue of trust between partners was discussed as a barrier to taking PrEP. For example, participants discussed GBMSM they knew who only had unprotected sex with other men on PrEP so thought of themselves as protected by the partner. This would depend on trust that the partner was taking PrEP as he said he was:

'He hasn't bought into being a PrEP user himself but he recognises it and he describes it as safety by proxy' (Lawrence, p.7, line 7)

Trust was also discussed in relation to GBMSMs being under pressure from partners not to take PrEP because they were in a relationship. Jamie's partner argued if their relationship was monogamous then PrEP would not be required as there was negligible risk of HIV, however this was dependent on trust that his partner would be faithful:

'When you're in a relationship they, some people get a bit annoyed that you're still taking it, but I think I'm still going to go for my check-ups every 3 months I'm not going to not go just because I'm in a relationship.' (Jamie, p.7, line 26)

Many participants preferred to have sex with partners who were also taking PrEP although concerns arose as to whether the partner was actually taking it as they claimed.

'But you can never really tell if somebody's being 100% truthful' (Nate, p.4, line 9)

Greg explained that he would ask to see the partner's PrEP bottle or tablet as proof that they were taking it.

'Some people prove it as in showing me their self, I know what it's like the pill I know what the box looks like you know. There is idiots out there to be honest with you.' (Greg, p.10, line 25)

Some participants had friends who felt that their risk of HIV was too low to require PrEP. Some friends did not have unprotected sex very often, or they had insertive rather than receptive anal sex which carries less risk of HIV:

'They're like not sort of mad shaggers ... because they don't have loads of casual sex with loads of different people and because they're a top, um they don't necessarily feel like PrEP is needed.' (Stewie, p.1, line 21)

Medical problems such as kidney problems or interactions with other medications were cited by participants as reasons not to take PrEP that they had heard GBMSM speak of. Further reasons included disinterest or running out of it. Roy described a friend with poor HIV literacy:

'He thinks he's invincible sometimes um, oh, aye ... I'm surprised I've not got it (HIV) but I must have something you know antibodies or something like that to stop me getting it.' Just because he hasn't caught it.' (Roy, p.6, line 9)

5.6 Subordinate theme 3: GBMSM experience of taking PrEP medication

This subordinate theme relates to the research objective (2) of GBMSM who live in areas of high deprivation experiences of barriers and facilitators to uptake, adherence and continuation of PrEP.

5.6.1 Sub theme: Dosing schedules of PrEP medication

Participants described PrEP medication as 'convenient' as it can be stopped and started as required. Participants described how they had been able to stop PrEP medication at various points in time when they were not sexually active.

'I'm not really that active I don't go out and about that that often ... but if I do decide to go and do anything then I've the option of using the PrEP' (Frank, p.2, line 21)

Most participants said that they were not taking PrEP throughout lockdown for COVID-19 as they were not meeting anyone. Further reasons to stop included being unwell, being abroad and being in a long-term monogamous relationship.

'At the start of the first lockdown erm I kind of stopped taking it because I wasn't sure exactly what was happening, I wasn't sort of with anybody anyway' (Nate, p.1, line 10)

As described in chapter one section 1.6.1, PrEP can either be taken daily or 'event based' dosing (EBD) on demand when unprotected sex is anticipated. A half of the participants in this study were taking daily PrEP and the other half event-based PrEP. Therefore, the patient experience extended to participants who preferred daily PrEP as they met partners for sex randomly, so preferred to be always protected from HIV. In contrast, participants who were taking event-based PrEP preferred it because they knew when they would be going out and meeting partners so could prepare their medication beforehand. A few added that they were not having sex very often.

'Event based ... I prefer that. It works for me anyway. Well, (laughs) ... I'm not at it all the time so um, if it's planned you know I'll meet with a friend, let's say, then I know to take my 2 doses of tablets' (Greg, p.1, line 9)

Patient experience was also described in terms of the use of multiple medications. Frank was reluctant to take more by adding daily PrEP, so he chose event based:

'I thought do I really want to be start taking more medication like that when I already had some do I really want to be adding something else into the mix' (Frank, p.8, line 21)

5.6.2 Adherence to PrEP medication

Adherence to PrEP medication is part of research objective (2) of this study. A recurrent theme in this study was that all participants admitted that they sometimes forgot their PrEP medication. Barriers to adherence to PrEP included remembering to take it when starting it, a break from the routine and not liking to take pills. Tom distinctly sums up the problem with remembering his PrEP:

'There have been occasions where I've forgot to take it ... have I taken it, have I not taken it? ... but there's that thing like I've taken it, I'm like that, or have I actually taken it I can't remember. Is it because I can't remember I don't do it; I don't take it because I have taken it already.' (Tom, p.4, line 2)

The participants who took PrEP medication daily said that it was easier to remember than the complicated event-based way.

'If I'm doing the 2 1 1 situation I, you feel that the third day I might I think ... oh bloody hell, I forgot to take it. I always try to take it at the same time if I am taking it on the day so that I'm up in the morning, part of your routine.' (Ewan, p.5, line 19)

Some participants agreed that once PrEP had become part of their habit or routine, such as taking it after a meal or at work, it was easier to remember to take.

'I just schedule it daily with the other medication that I take its sometimes a bit more tricky with the event based I kind of have this habit it's kind of like you know it's like brushing teeth now, it's kind of a ritual.' (Carl, p.2, line 25)

Further facilitators to PrEP adherence were a dosette box and participants having a supply of tablets out of the house such as in a wallet or taking PrEP away on holiday with them. Some participants took PrEP at the same time as other daily medications which they found to be an aid to concordance. Some participants added that PrEP being available in a longer-term injection form would be a great aid to adherence.

'I think vaccines or injections would be perfect I think it's something we probably need ... you might get a vaccine then you might get a booster will be given once a year which would be a bit more easier for some people because I know for a fact that's there's people that probably forget to take it' (Jamie, p.2, line 17)

Further facilitators to the acceptability and accessibility of PrEP regarding adherence from sexual health services were that the service was free, the clarity of information in the PrEP leaflet and three-monthly appointment reminders by text.

5.7 Subordinate theme 4: Risk Compensation: GBMSM's perceptions of PrEP and health outcomes/safety

This section explores the experiences and perceptions of GBMSM taking PrEP and links to the aim and research objective (3) addressing any potential sexual behaviour change in the light of PrEP.

5.7.1 Sub theme: The role of the 'invincible shield'

Participants used phrases to describe PrEP such as 'invincible shield', 'safeguard', a 'safety net', 'guarantee', 'vaccine', 'life changing' and 'game changer' because it protects against HIV via unprotected sex. The resulting reduction in fear and stress around contracting HIV via sex enabled them to feel more relaxed and confident about their relationships and sexual health:

'PrEP is a real gamechanger ... it really made me feel a bit more confident ... some of that anxiety was definitely quelled ... it had been only with PrEP that I felt that ... one concern is to be eliminated.' (Lawrence, p.5, line 6)

'I don't think that people are like completely terrified of it (HIV) now in a way that like they might have been before ... the psychological effect of having a pill that you can take, that sort of is almost like a vaccine ... it's not doom, and you know you're not going to degrade before people's eyes in a matter of months.' (Stewie, p.6, line 10)

Carl suggested that he felt more confident in meeting potential partners generally because of PrEP:

'I think that I when I started taking PrEP I I felt I started feeling more confident er having sex and in general meeting people er not only having sex' (Carl, p.4, line 5)

Lawrence expanded on this by describing how the protection from HIV with PrEP whilst having condomless sex had increased intimacy with his partners.

‘Certainly, for my boyfriend and I, ... it really, took us to a different level of ... physical intimacy. In terms of my civil partner, I think in parallel it actually made us more emotionally intimate. ... it’s given me a sense of security and emotional stability and emotional intimacy that I don’t think I had prior to the intervention’ (Lawrence, p.4, line 5)

Other perceptions of PrEP were described as giving participants responsibility for their sexual health and a sense of agency. Participants also felt that the quality of PrEP would in the long term greatly reduce the transmission and incidence of HIV in the general population:

‘It would suppress the virus as much as it possibly can if more people were on it (PrEP). The same with the COVID vaccine’ (Tom, p.5, line 27)

‘It’s life changing, isn’t it? Really. You could say that’s what if people are educated towards it then there is absolutely no reason for anyone to you know contracting HIV, technically, from a sexual point of view ... why would you not take it ... it’s a bit of a no brainer.’ (Ewan, p.7, line 14)

Interestingly, some participants said that they were more likely to have sex with men who were HIV positive and had an undetectable viral load after they had decided to commence PrEP. Through learning about and taking PrEP they had found out more about HIV risk and had become aware that people with undetectable viral load do not transmit HIV through sexual contact.

‘When I started taking PrEP, I felt I started feeling more confident ... in meeting people who are undetectable. I think they have quite a fair amount of prejudice against them and ... if they’re they take care of their own health, if they’ve got the HIV under control and so on.’ (Carl, p.1, line 8)

5.7.2 Sub theme: Risk taking behaviour, sexual partners and PrEP

Sexual health risk taking behaviours other than condomless sex were also discussed. Some respondents suggested that there were no differences to their sexual risk taking other than a reduction in condom use due to PrEP:

'It's changed in the fact that I'm standing there feeling quite secure about feeling safe...it's an emotional kinda change more ... I don't think it's changed my sexual preferences or habits.' (Ewan, p.6, line 5)

Conversely, the other participants thought that taking PrEP had increased their risk-taking behaviour in sexual encounters such as increased numbers of partners. Participants described PrEP as providing a sense of freedom in terms of sex and partners:

'When the PrEP came out I was very much like um fell down that trap of kid in a candy shop, oh, obviously you can have lots of sex with lots of different people without using a condom because this is like this wonder drug' (Logan, p.1, line 12)

Participants developed this concept further, likening the feelings and implications to what they thought may be the sexual experiences of heterosexual people; or alternatively how they felt when 'coming out' as gay men.

'It was almost like coming out, so it was, do you know what I mean you have that kind of period of oh my god I feel amazing and here I am, I'm going to go out I'm going to date lots of people, have sex with lots of people' (Logan, p.2, line 21)

One participant thought that the number of sex parties had increased since the introduction of PrEP but was not sure there was a causal relationship. Other participants said that PrEP had enabled easier access to sex.

'I think my sexual behaviour has stayed the same ... occasionally people that I know that started taking PrEP they went they went a bit crazy at the beginning and they would have more risky sexual encounters, partners' (Carl, p.3, line 9)

'It's almost like the fear of contracting it (HIV) is no longer there in the same sort of force that it has been previously, so I definitely think people have relaxed their attitude towards sort of safer sex and whatever else, the number of partners that people have etc.' (Nate, p.6, line 28)

Participants felt that more tailored education and support around negotiating risk-taking behaviours with PrEP would help them to establish their sexual preferences and boundaries with partners:

'If you're going to give a child the keys to a Ferrari of course they're going to go out and potentially crash it. You're kind of then left to your own devices ... trial and error, figure it out. And then you turn inwards to your own community and again it's unregulated ... personal experience of this works for me, it might work for you.' (Logan, p.4, line 5)

Logan explained how HIV stigma and the fear of HIV could often exacerbate the sexual health risk taking behaviour of GBMSM. Hence, for some men the removal of the previous risk of HIV by taking PrEP could lead to even more extreme sexual health risk taking behaviours:

'Where its having lust partnered with fear um it's a straight psychotic;... and if you're not kind of having insight into it, it messes with your head and that messes with your relationships and then you might end up putting yourself in sort of risky situations or more and more kind of like kinkier or more dangerous situations because you're kinda desensitised to things. Vanilla sex isn't doing it for me so I need to kind of up the ante which creates the space for maybe more and further risky behaviour' (Logan, p.2, line 28)

5.7.3 Sub theme: PrEP role and other STIs

A recurrent theme in this study was that most participants thought that the incidence of other STI's such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea and syphilis had increased because condom use had decreased due to PrEP use. Some described personal experience of this.

'I basically found myself, being more prone to catching chlamydia, and that sort of thing, oh right ok, this is another line of defence this isn't a kinda free for all. This is not, like, a hall pass, just to be reckless and irresponsible.' (Logan, p.1, line 15)

A couple of participants felt that some GBMSM taking PrEP were concerned about the risk of other STI's, although would not actually use condoms to prevent transmission. The other participants agreed that GBMSM taking PrEP in general were not very worried about the other STI's because, unlike HIV, they were curable:

'It (PrEP) sort of created don't worry so much because we've always kind of dealt with the fear of that (HIV), so like contracting like chlamydia where you take 3 tablets was nothing your big player's (HIV) been taken out the game, everything else can be taken away with a jag or a tablet' (Logan, p.1, line 26)

'Hep C nowadays ... you can mainly treat that ... it's at the back of your mind, but you are conscious that on the whole they (STI's) can be treated these days.' (Connor, p.3, line 19)

Nate said that he had met a partner who thought that other STI's were even a 'badge of honour':

'Some people see sort of like having gonorrhoea or chlamydia almost as a badge of honour type thing ... they've got gonorrhoea this is their 3rd time and that they're quite happy ... yeah, ok I'm just going to be on antibiotics for x number of days and its ... going to be treatable it's going to be fine.' (Nate, p.6, line 13)

Greg explained how the PrEP induced feelings of being untouchable or 'immune' to other infections because of the 'invincibility' against HIV:

'Thinking you're immune to it so if you're still catching these wee STI's down the line I know it's not right you should be using condoms or whatever but like I suppose we're using PrEP now. It can get a bit, you know, nothing can touch me now' (Greg, p.3, line 2)

Indeed, some participants felt that ignorance of STIs amongst GBMSM in general was a problem.

'Obviously like PrEP's only sort of trying to prevent HIV I don't think there's much shared discussion about things like chlamydia, gonorrhoea' (Nate, p.6, line 11)

'It's good to have a flyer (about STIs) but 99% of people just throw them in the bin' (Jamie, p.6, line 8)

Other participants explained how the regular three-monthly sexual health screen requirement for obtaining PrEP provided reassurance around the other STI's for themselves but also the knowledge that partners taking PrEP were getting regular sexual health screens too:

'If the other person is comfortable with it I can have the discussion with them, are they on PrEP as well because if they're on PrEP I know that they get tested on a regular basis' (Connor, p.5, line 29)

Additionally, the fast turnaround for results and partner notification of a STI reduced the risk of passing the infection on:

'Some of the profiles on the dating websites the sex websites and they'll include your status, they'll include when you were last tested, they include do you use condoms, PrEP or both... much more openness ...it sends a bit of a signal of, a bit of managed responsibility perhaps but also that its ok to talk about that stuff whereas I think previously it could be quite taboo.' (Lawrence, p.8, line 2)

5.8 Chapter five summary

This study was carried out following the methodology outlined in the previous chapter four. The subsequent findings in this chapter have explored the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP in accordance with the research aim and objectives of this study. Three superordinate and four subordinate themes of the findings of this study were identified which reflected the themes from the literature review (chapter two) and some of the more general topics around sexual health and HIV from the introduction (chapter one).

Chapter six: Discussion and contribution to knowledge

6.1 Introduction

This chapter will further interpret and integrate the findings of this study in dialogue with the literature and the aim and objectives. The chapter aligns with the PrEP patient journey conceptual framework presented in chapter three. The new knowledge from the findings and themes is presented; exploring the experiences of availability, access, acceptability and continuation of PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation.

6.2 New PrEP patient journey conceptual framework

The new PrEP patient journey conceptual framework outlined in chapter three was devised by the researcher to underpin this study. This was developed from and improved on the Nunn *et al.* (2017) and Lau, Hung and Lee (2020) PrEP conceptual frameworks. It has been utilised to allow for focus on the integrative enquiry and data analysis and the key conceptual findings have been related to the theoretical foundation of the research, the literature review and the research aim and objectives. For ease of reference the new patient journey conceptual framework has been reproduced overleaf:

Figure 3.3: New PrEP patient journey conceptual framework underpinning this study

This chapter will discuss the themes identified from the findings in the previous chapter five together with the research aim and objectives. Text boxes at the end of each section will link the theme to the specific patient journey constructs in the conceptual framework together with a brief explanation of the relationship. Finally, the conceptual framework populated by the concepts identified from the findings will be portrayed in the subsequent section 6.8.

6.3 Superordinate themes

6.3.1 Cultural competence and the role of the clinician

This superordinate emergent theme relates to the research aim and objective (1) and (2) of rationale for and experiences of commencing PrEP and barriers and facilitators to accessing PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. Only three participants in this study had attended sexual health services specifically to request PrEP and the rest had attended for a sexual health screen. One participant had never heard of PrEP before attending sexual health services which is a clear barrier to uptake. The remainder had heard of PrEP from various sources but had not started taking it as they cited 'uncertainty' and 'ignorance' and lacked enough information to make a decision. A new finding in this study is that these participants had only decided to commence PrEP after recommendation from the clinic staff who explained that they were eligible and advocated taking it. There appears to be scanty evidence to support this to date. It is presumed that as awareness of PrEP increases over time amongst GBMSM, more will attend sexual health services specifically to ask for PrEP.

Although some participants in this study had been anxious prior to attending sexual health services due to not knowing what to expect and the prospect of being asked personal questions, all praised the clinicians at their consultation. Pauli, Martin and Greiling (2022) stressed that staff competence, interpersonal skills and empathy are very important, not only for patient wellbeing but to positively influence health behaviours. Conversely, several participants in this study described how they had regularly attended other areas of healthcare in Scotland outside of sexual health services in primary and secondary care and were disappointed that the healthcare professional they had seen had not heard of PrEP. Participants expressed concern that these were qualified clinical staff such as doctors and nurses who were unable to provide health promotion and information to people at risk of HIV. Conversely, Cooper *et al.* (2021) found that knowledge of PrEP in the USA amongst medical staff is widespread, however there appears to be scanty literature as to the level of knowledge of PrEP in the wider NHS in the UK. It is likely that the lack of promotion of PrEP in general would be a factor.

There also appears to be scanty research to date as to the significance of the clinician's recommendation of PrEP and impact of the patient relationship on PrEP acceptability. Applying the Health Belief Model outlined in chapter three highlights the importance of the skills and knowledge of clinicians in these consultations (Llewellyn *et al.*, 2019, p.113) in addressing HIV literacy and establishing the effectiveness of PrEP. The health belief model demonstrates how GBMSM are motivated to overcome the burden of accessing PrEP medication (section 5.4.3) and complicated concordance regimens (section 5.6.1) because they find it to be of worthwhile benefit.

Estcourt *et al.* (2023) and McDaid *et al.* (2021) highlighted the importance of cultural competency for best practice in addressing PrEP and HIV literacy respectively at sexual health services. Cultural competency has been defined in different ways. The essentialist view of learning about aspects of culture including beliefs and traditions of a particular group and applying them to practice has been criticised for not addressing power relationships (Gareneau and Peplin, 2004). Alternatively, the social constructivist perspective of cultural competence states that it is a relational process of partnership and shared meanings arising from the interactions between individuals, where the healthcare professional considers the patient's life and health holistically. Broader historical, social, political and economic factors such as deprivation are taken into account, allowing for focus on the prejudices that underlie social inequality (Garneau and Peplin, 2015). Cultural competence in nursing results in increased patient trust in healthcare, better concordance with treatment, improved patient satisfaction and better patient quality of life (Sharifi, Adib-Hajbagheri and Najafic, 2019).

The findings of this study demonstrate on individual, social and structural levels that cultural competence in working with GBMSM is essential for healthcare professionals regarding the successful implementation of PrEP. The staff in the clinic described in this study who were prescribing PrEP were either medical staff or very experienced nursing staff; the majority who were advanced practitioners (see section 1.6.2). The PrEP patient journey conceptual framework proposed in this study (see chapter three) demonstrates how healthcare staff are required to understand not only the numerous individual factors involved for GBMSM acceptability of PrEP in the framework, but also

the structural macro-level systemic factors such as deprivation, stigma, discrimination and barriers to accessing sexual health care services. Culturally competent healthcare staff possess the knowledge and skills for congruent, tailored consultations in HIV prevention where the patient relationship focusses not only on acceptability and continuation of PrEP but also patient empowerment so that GBMSM become authorities in their own healthcare. Critical reflective practice acts on an individual level by addressing power imbalances for GBMSM and enhancing the role of the nurse to challenge HIV stigma and address health inequalities by means of a social constructivist approach (Garneau and Peplin, 2015). This finding is in contrast to the patient experience of accessing PrEP in the USA, where many healthcare providers were uninformed about PrEP or felt uncomfortable discussing it; hence consultations were described as 'awkward' and 'condescending' by patients (Grimm and Schwartz, 2021, p.53).

Conceptual framework:

Availability – Lack of knowledge and wareness of HIV risk and PrEP by NHS clinical staff is an intermediate level barrier to availability of PrEP for GBMSM.

Acceptability – Culturally competent staff can tailor the consultation to the individual so that the service user can understand their HIV risk and make an informed decision regarding PrEP

Accessibility (non-discrimination) – On an intermediate level, culturally competent staff can address individual level aspects of deprivation regarding accessibility of PrEP for GBMSM, **fostering agency.**

6.3.2 Stigma, discrimination and awareness of PrEP

This superordinate emergent theme relates to the research aim and objective (2) of barriers and facilitators to PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. The findings in study highlight that lack of awareness is a significant barrier to accessing PrEP medication. Participants in this study questioned why they had learned initially about PrEP from either sexual health staff or their peers rather than via a national public health campaign. It was felt that PrEP was a huge step forward in HIV prevention which was being kept hidden away from the public as PrEP had not been marketed similarly to other 'mainstream' medications. Participants in this study compared the level of investment in the promotion of PrEP to the COVID-19 vaccine and summarised that the disparity was a continuation of existing HIV stigma and discrimination towards GBMSM. All agreed that further advertising and promotion of PrEP both within and outside of the NHS was required so that PrEP awareness was equivalent to awareness of HIV.

Furthermore, participants in this study described how the lack of promotion around PrEP led to many GBMSM assuming that they had to pay for the medication themselves. This is a potential problem as Gilson, Clutterbuck and Chen (2018) found that over 70% of men at high risk of HIV in Scotland would be unable or unwilling to self-fund PrEP if it was not available on the NHS; a particular issue for those in poverty. Another participant criticised the implementation of PrEP further for a lack of community engagement where all of the complex underlying biological, societal and environmental factors were not considered. A lack of community engagement has been found to cause stigma and an increase in STI's in sexual health interventions in the past (Allen-Scott, Hatfield and McIntyre, 2014).

Consequently, a new finding in this study is that due to the absence of a national campaign promoting PrEP, many GBMSM taking PrEP are promoting it themselves by encouraging other eligible men to commence it in an attempt to increase awareness and understanding of PrEP amongst potential partners, and in general. Participants in this study said that GBMSM taking PrEP had a good knowledge of the eligibility criteria and were able to recommend PrEP to others by sharing their experiences of

taking it. This followed the Martin (2017) Word of Mouth model in health care discussed in chapter three (section 3.2), where patients draw on health information from others such as friends (Pauli, Martin and Greiling, 2022).

Participants in this study described how these conversations with potential partners about PrEP were also allowing for more discussion and negotiation about wider sexual health issues in general such as condom use and HIV testing and that these extra conversations may not have happened prior to PrEP. This new finding in this study may be significant as if it becomes a general trend as these discussions may raise awareness of PrEP and HIV literacy. Estcourt *et al.* (2021) explained how the decision to not provide a mass media campaign for PrEP in Scotland was to avoid demand exceeding capacity in clinic. Decisions were taken to supply NHS PrEP via sexual health services only with no added finance for the additional service provision required (Young, 2021, p.66). Yet Young (2021, p.65) argued that the actual reason for this decision was to avoid anticipated negative media coverage in Scotland. When PrEP had been proposed in England in 2016 the media responded with homophobic rhetoric suggesting that PrEP was only a lifestyle drug to encourage risky sex for undeserving gay men. Grimm and Schwartz (2021, p.49) explained how GBMSM at risk of HIV are a stigmatised population, and restricting the promotion of PrEP avoided the possibility of controversy. However, dealing with this potential homophobia affecting their healthcare has compelled GBMSM to act and advocate for themselves to raise awareness of PrEP and address their own healthcare needs; reflecting experiences that had transpired during the AIDS epidemic in previous years (see section 1.4).

Nevertheless, when information about PrEP is disseminated by word of mouth the information is passed on by individuals who are not trained healthcare providers, leading to an increased risk of inaccuracy, misinterpretation or reinterpretation. Consequently, participants in this study added that they would prefer more support from clinic staff in terms of information, counselling and discussion about how to negotiate relationships, sexual health and the risk of STIs with PrEP. This study also finds evidence that although GBMSM taking PrEP are promoting it to others, this word of mouth is not reaching the entire population of GBMSM in Scotland. Participants in this study explained that people who were not part of the commercial 'gay scene' or

did not attend sexual health services regularly were less likely to be aware of PrEP. For example, GBMSM who met partners at cruising areas or did not attend LGBT venues, bars and clubs missed out on sexual health information, which leads to inequality within this population. This included men with a non-gay identity. Several participants expressed significant concerns about the HIV risk of a number of men that they had met who were having unprotected sex with casual male partners and had not heard of or accessed PrEP but were also married to women or had a long-term female partner who was unaware of their lifestyle (see section 5.4.3).

This is reflected in the literature. Men who identify as bisexual or heterosexual are less likely to access sexual health services and men married to women sometimes led clandestine sexual lives which were separate to the rest of their relationships (Coia *et al.*, 2014). It is thought that these men were unlikely to identify with gay culture or be involved in HIV prevention work. Consequently, they may not have much perception of their risk of HIV from their sexual behaviours. Being involved in the commercial 'gay scene' in Scotland improves health literacy and access to testing for GBMSM as historically it has been a centre for the delivery of sexual health interventions (Frankis *et al.*, 2016; Young and McDaid, 2014). Following on from this, Dalrymple *et al.* (2019) and O'Donnell *et al.* (2019) noted that men who had sex with men and a non-gay identity were more likely to be older and less likely to test for HIV, which fits with the increased public acceptance of same sex partnerships over time described by participants in this study. This theme fits with availability and acceptability of PrEP at structural, intermediate and individual levels in the conceptual framework for GBMSM.

Conceptual framework:

Availability - of PrEP was limited by lack of promotion and community engagement at structural level and intermediate levels.

Accessibility – Lack of promotion of PrEP and community engagement adds to perceptions of discrimination and increases HIV stigma at a structural level. PrEP encourages conversations around sexual health. Individual GBMSM with agency are promoting it to others, however men with a non-gay identity/not part of the 'gay scene' still miss out hearing about PrEP

6.3.3 PrEP replacing condoms for HIV prevention

This superordinate emergent theme relates to research objective (3) exploring sexual behaviour changes in the light of PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. All participants in this study stopped or significantly reduced their condom use because they had started taking PrEP medication and the risk of HIV with PrEP was so low that condoms were not required. Participants added that they would also be much less likely to use a condom if their partner was also taking PrEP, if they were drunk or if they knew their partner before having sex. Only one participant commented that he would be more anxious about condom use after finding out about a recent PrEP failure. Reasons for not using condoms included lack of sensation and erectile dysfunction (see section 5.3.3).

This finding in this study challenges much of the initial literature around PrEP which suggested that GBMSM do not change their condom use or risk-taking behaviours due to PrEP. For example, Hosek *et al.* (2017) found no significant difference in condom use between GBMSM taking and not taking PrEP, even suggesting that PrEP increased condom use. However, later studies such as Oldenburg *et al.* (2017) and Traeger *et al.* (2018) advised that PrEP use may be linked to an increase in condomless anal sex amongst GBMSM and their partners. Hughes *et al.* (2018) concurred, finding that condom use with PrEP was not straightforward but dependent on a number of other evolving cognitive and emotional influences regarding decision

making which were inherently social. Reasons given by the participants in this study for not using condoms concur with the literature (McCormack *et al.*, 2016) including increased sensation, condoms weren't discussed, participants were under the influence of drugs/alcohol or didn't use condoms with their regular partners but did with others.

On a wider scale, participants in this study felt that condom use had greatly reduced amongst GBMSM taking PrEP in Scotland and many would only use condoms if the partner had asked them to. Participants explained that PrEP use had now become so normalised amongst GBMSM in Scotland that condoms were not required as PrEP had replaced condoms for HIV prevention. This normalisation of condomless sex due to the efficacy of PrEP for HIV prevention can be viewed through the lens of NPT (see chapter three) where patients make sense of PrEP, understand its quality and legitimacy and actively enrol themselves in supporting it (Bracher and May, 2019, p.171).

Yet on review of the findings in this study, this normalisation effect appears to have intensified to such a level where GBMSM are now describing feeling under pressure to take PrEP and stop using condoms to be able to remain sexually active. Many participants in this study were slightly older and had always practiced safe sex so feeling pressured into not using condoms was abnormal to them. Indeed, most participants in this study preferred to have sex with partners who were also taking PrEP and some participants would not have sex with a partner who was not taking PrEP. This position appears to be generalisable to the wider population of GBMSM in Scotland as participants also described potential partners refusing to have sex with them unless they were taking PrEP. Consequently, some participants in this study had felt forced to start PrEP when they would have otherwise used condoms for HIV prevention, which is also a new finding in this study (see section 5.3.3). This led to a further discussion around PrEP stigma where participants described a positive stigma relating to PrEP in Scotland because the person taking it was not likely to have HIV and a negative stigma attached to not taking it. There appears to be scanty evidence in the literature around GBMSM refusing to have sex with those not taking PrEP, however the literature is varied in terms of PrEP stigma. Young and McDaid (2014),

Sowicz *et al.* (2014) and Golub, Gamarel and Surace (2017) had suggested a negative social stigma attached to PrEP, in that people using it were thought to be promiscuous and irresponsible or HIV positive and lying about it. Conversely, Ellorin *et al.* (2017) and Auerbach and Hoppe (2015) found that much of the stigma around PrEP to be positive because PrEP offers a way to safeguard health while preserving intimacy in relationships and that being 'HIV negative and on PrEP' was seen as desirable. Moving forward, participants in this study expressed the concern that this general trend towards condomless sex due to PrEP would cause repercussions for those GBMSM not taking PrEP, who would also face pressure not to use a condom. In a time of reduced anxiety around HIV with PrEP, sexual health messaging faces an increasing challenge regarding the promotion of condom use. Consequently, groups with a lower uptake of PrEP such as those with lower socio-economic status, bisexual or younger GBMSM may face increasing HIV risk.

Conceptual framework:

Acceptability – There is now a negative stigma attached to not taking PrEP at an intermediate social level. Individual GBMSM are feeling under pressure to take PrEP instead of using condoms for HIV prevention to be sexually active.

Quality - Such is the efficacy PrEP that it appears to be normalised in replacing condoms for HIV prevention for GBMSM. However, an overall increase in and norm of condomless sex amongst the GBMSM population may affect individual HIV risk, particularly for vulnerable GBMSM.

6.4 Subordinate Theme 1: Socioeconomic status: Health inequalities and PrEP

6.4.1 Health inequalities, culture and vulnerabilities

Participants in this study observed that GBMSMs who were vulnerable were less likely to access sexual health services to obtain PrEP. Vulnerabilities and cultural differences can create barriers for individuals accessing PrEP which links to the research aim and objectives (1) and (2) in this study. Vulnerability was described in terms of issues such as addictions; where alcohol dependence and substance use were often related to deprivation in terms of chaotic lifestyles and homelessness. It was considered that alcohol and drug problems led to sexual health being a low priority for these individuals which was compounded by a lack of resources and organisational barriers to accessing the clinic. The literature relating to PrEP access for vulnerable GBMSM is scanty, however Blashill *et al.* (2019) in the USA noted that depression, alcohol/drug use and experiences of violence negatively impact on uptake of PrEP. Similarly, intravenous drug users in the UK population who are at risk of HIV have a very low uptake of PrEP (Nakasone *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, research addressing barriers to healthcare in general report vulnerability and substance use as potential reasons as outlined in chapter one section 1.8. Practical barriers to attendance at sexual health services can include insecure housing, lack of money and transport, not remembering which interventions had occurred at past visits and the substantial burden involved in the ongoing buying of, taking and withdrawing from drugs (Edelman *et al.*, 2013; MacAfee *et al.*, 2020). Poverty and insecure housing have also been identified as barriers to uptake of PrEP in the literature (Burns *et al.*, 2021; Dehlin *et al.* 2019).

Participants in this study suggested that specific groups of people such as some refugees or travelling communities may not attend sexual health services or access PrEP due to barriers around inclusion, accessibility and acceptability. For example, one participant explained that for some African cultures there was no custom of attending clinics for healthcare because it was not seen as safe; people tended to go to hospitals instead. In England black African and Caribbean women have a very low uptake of PrEP despite HIV risk, due to lack of awareness, HIV stigma and institutional racism (Nakasone *et al.*, 2020). Participants also pointed out that GBMSM from

overseas may be less likely to be aware that they could access free PrEP from the NHS. Kaczkowski and Swartout (2019) found that young refugees tended to lack money and transport and, particularly men, had poor health literacy around STIs and experienced shame in relation to their sexual health. Additionally, GBMSM from some religions and cultures can experience varying amounts of homophobia and can often find that their religion and culture is in conflict with their sexuality (Jaspal *et al.*, 2019) (see chapter one section 1.7). Intersectionality demonstrates how these vulnerabilities and cultural differences, or different social categories, impact upon one another to augment inequalities within sexual health (Frankis *et al.*, 2016). Individuals with specific social and health needs such as vulnerabilities related to deprivation can experience marginalisation, causing barriers to uptake of PrEP. This inequality links to most of the constructs of the patient journey in the conceptual framework on individual, social and structural levels. Work is required to engage these groups to identify barriers, promote PrEP acceptability and increase accessibility so individuals are not excluded from PrEP services.

Conceptual framework:

Availability – A lack of community engagement has prevented uptake of PrEP for some marginalised/culturally different communities of GBMSM where specific needs have not been addressed. Individuals also lack awareness that NHS PrEP is free.

Acceptability – Individual cultural differences can affect the acceptability of PrEP for some GBMSM. Those GBMSM with vulnerabilities related to deprivation such as drugs/alcohol can experience a lack of agency as a barrier to uptake of PrEP.

Accessibility (physical/economic) – Vulnerable GBMSM or groups such as refugees may face financial and logistical challenges to accessing PrEP clinics.

Accessibility (non-discriminatory) – Intersectionality demonstrates how GBMSM can experience inequality and barriers to accessing PrEP on individual, intermediate and structural levels.

6.4.2 Health inequalities, education and HIV literacy

It is well known that education in general impacts on future life chances and that deprivation is a key determinant of health inequalities (Scottish Government National Statistics, 2021; Audit Scotland, 2012). With regard to the research aim and objective (2) of barriers to PrEP, the qualitative data from this study suggested that there could be a potential relationship between deprivation category, educational attainment and uptake of PrEP. Those participants who lived in SIMD quintile one without degrees said that they themselves and their potential partners reported less awareness of PrEP. In comparison, participants living in the slightly more affluent SIMD quintile two who were educated to degree or postgraduate level and working in professional occupations were generally aware of PrEP, together with their potential partners. These individual participant findings are not transferable to the wider population, however Burns *et al.* (2021) and Blashill *et al.* (2019) concurred that socioeconomic circumstances such as poverty level, unemployment, income and inequality all negatively affect PrEP acceptability and access for GBMSM. Similarly, Garcia and Saw (2019) in the USA and Jaspal *et al.* (2019) found that GBMSM with a lower income and less educational qualifications had significantly less HIV literacy and were consequently less likely to access PrEP (See section 2.5.2 and section 1.8). Following on from this, participants in this study identified that an important factor in accessing PrEP was that it is free of charge (Lorenc *et al.*, 2020; Sowicz *et al.*, 2014; Golub *et al.*, 2013).

Similarly, sex education in school was a common theme in this study with regard to barriers to PrEP. Participants perceived that inadequate sex education contributed to a lack of knowledge around sexual health and HIV literacy which consequently led to inequalities around PrEP accessibility for GBMSM. Some older respondents reflected on their socio-cultural experience of the HIV/AIDS epidemic in the 1980s and the gay and HIV stigma of the time, which had impacted on their education. It had been illegal for schools in the UK to include gay sexuality in the curriculum, so participants explained how they had obtained inaccurate information 'behind closed doors' instead. Participants in this study concurred with Patterson *et al.* (2020), who suggested that sex education in schools today is still inadequate and bounded by social class, power

and politics, so often failing to provide the practical information necessary to mitigate risks of STIs, leading to poor sexual health and HIV literacy for young GBMSM.

Conceptual framework:

Availability – Lack of education on social and individual levels is a barrier to sexual health knowledge, HIV literacy and uptake of PrEP with regard to deprivation for GBMSM.

Acceptability – Poor sex education can shape HIV stigma for GBMSM, leading to internalised homophobia, discrimination and health disparities. Lower levels of education have been associated with less HIV literacy and distrust of PrEP.

Accessibility (non-discrimination) – Education in sexual health is required to increase HIV literacy which will promote PrEP accessibility for GBMSM.

6.4.3 Health inequalities and organisational/clinic barriers to accessing PrEP medication

This sub theme explores the research aim and objective (2) of barriers to uptake of PrEP for GBMSM in this study. Participants described several barriers that they had to negotiate to access PrEP services including the number of visits required, location and appointment times of sexual health clinics. Those who lived in more remote or rural areas were at a disadvantage, particularly if they did not have access to a car as availability and cost of public transport was a significant difficulty. This finding around transport reflects previous research in Scotland (Flowers *et al.*, 2013; Flowers, Duncan and Knussen, 2003) and in the USA (Rogers *et al.* 2023). Low income has also been found to be a barrier to attending PrEP clinics in the USA (Burns *et al.*, 2021; Blashill *et al.*, 2019; Garcia and Saw, 2019). Participants explained that because there was only one clinic dispensing PrEP in the city's West End, GBMSM living more remotely in the next town or further outside the city centre faced a long journey. Even those with a car complained of logistical problems such as being stuck in traffic on the motorway and missing appointments. Furthermore, the frequency and timing of clinics

did not necessarily suit some GBMSM who were employed by means of today's unsociable working hours, zero hours contracts or who were in insecure employment such as the 'gig economy' (Scottish Parliament Health and Sport Committee, 2015). Many working in sectors such as retail, hospitality or entertainment had poor working terms and conditions and were not allowed time off for medical appointments by their employer.

However, the identification socio-economic status specifically as a barrier to accessing sexual health clinics to obtain PrEP for Scottish GBMSM is a new finding in this study. Being able to access PrEP from G.P.'s and pharmacies or outlying clinics were suggested by participants as solutions to these problems. The HIV Commission (2020) are currently campaigning for PrEP in England to be available from venues outside of sexual health clinics such as community pharmacies, which is thought to be feasible (Kennedy *et al.*, 2022; Crowley, Cullen and O'Donnell, 2020) and similar provision has been recommended for Scotland (Estcourt *et al.*, 2023). This theme fits to the accessibility construct of the conceptual framework at structural, intermediate and individual levels. NHS healthcare should be physically and economically within reach for all parts of the population (Scottish government, 2020; WHO, 2017), however the fact that PrEP is not universally accessible to all GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation has clear implications for a rights-based approach to sexual health.

Conceptual framework:

Accessibility (physical/economic) – PrEP is provided by only one sexual health clinic in the city and is not accessible to all GBMSM due to barriers related to deprivation. On structural and intermediate levels, accessibility of PrEP is dependent on service provision in terms of service type, location and appointment times and on individual factors such as mobility, support, vulnerability and ability to manage the costs of getting to the clinic.

6.5 Subordinate Theme 2: Facilitators and Barriers to PrEP access

6.5.1 PrEP face-to-face appointments versus telephone and postal clinic appointments

This sub theme addresses the research aim and objective (2) by exploring types of clinic appointment as barriers or facilitators to accessibility of PrEP. During the COVID-19 pandemic many health services in Scotland were being run remotely (British Medical Association, 2022). Prior to the pandemic PrEP appointments had been face to face but these were replaced by a telephone consulting service in order to reduce the potential spread of COVID-19. These remote consultations involved some STI testing using home kits with the kit and the PrEP medication being posted to the patient. Some participants in this study preferred these remote appointments as they were straightforward, faster, efficient and having testing kits and medication posted out to them was convenient. Remote appointments also overcome the appointment scheduling issues and geographical barriers to attending clinic mentioned in the previous section, negating the need to travel. Furthermore, remote appointments avoid any potential embarrassment of being seen in the clinic waiting room. Kincaid *et al.* (2021) added that remote and online consultations amongst GBMSM can provide autonomy and control and be thought of as less intrusive than face to face appointments.

Despite these advantages to remote consultations, many participants in this study preferred the original face-to-face PrEP clinic appointments because they could complete the consultation and pick up the medication in one appointment. They felt 'reassured' by the direct contact with the clinician and described how face to face contact enabled disclosure of personal information, time for reflection and the ability to ask questions. This study finds evidence that face-to-face care is important and remote care should be seen as complementary rather than a replacement to ensure acceptability for patients. It is also important to be mindful of digital exclusion when providing remote PrEP services to avoid exacerbating health inequalities.

Conceptual framework:

Accessibility (physical/economic) – On a structural level, policy decisions regarding PrEP service provision and location will affect the suitability of appointment type for individual GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation.

Accessibility (non-discrimination) – On an intermediate clinic level, decisions regarding time, type and location of the PrEP clinic appointment will affect individual suitability subject to circumstances and preferences.

6.5.2 Sexual health service stigma, HIV stigma and help seeking

This sub theme addresses the stigma related to attending sexual health services and HIV stigma which both relate to the research aim and objective (2) of barriers to uptake of PrEP. This is experienced by GBMSM in addition to the stigma surrounding PrEP (section 6.3.3). Concerns about confidentiality were reported to be a significant barrier to attending sexual health services to obtain PrEP for GBMSM, with some participants being afraid of being seen in the clinic waiting room by someone they knew and being judged by other patients and staff. This is widely documented in the literature (Lea *et al.*, 2019; O'Donnell *et al.*, 2019; Flowers *et al.*, 2013). Participants in this study described the problem being exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic due to social distancing from the receptionist in the waiting room. Some participants in this study felt more comfortable in a male-only waiting room, however a minority thought that GBMSM only services felt ad hoc and 'like an afterthought' in comparison to heterosexual sexual health. The Scottish Government (Population Health Directorate (Scotland), 2021) seek to promote sexual health services and normalise access to address stigma and embarrassment, however the negative view of sexual health and clinics in society today remains a problem.

Notably, some participants described how some GBMSM with a non-gay identity 'will never' access services specifically targeted at GBMSM which include PrEP. Participants explained that for some of these men, being married to women and concealing the fact that they had sex with men meant that they were unlikely to access

sexual health services due to concerns around families and partners finding out and many not being aware that sexual health services are confidential. Many of these men were thought by participants to have low HIV literacy (see section 5.5.2). This is supported in the literature (Dalrymple *et al.*, 2019).

For the GBMSM participants in this study, HIV stigma was a recurrent theme influencing sexual health and access to PrEP. All had experienced external homophobia in some form and described how internalised homophobia led to many GBMSM not feeling at ease with their sexuality and lowering self-esteem. Consequently, some men did not feel comfortable talking about their sexual experiences which prevented them seeking out sexual health services (Estcourt *et al.*, 2023; Flowers *et al.*, 2013). In the literature, stigma and shame around being a gay or bisexual man and internalised homophobia have been widely documented (Flowers *et al.*, 2013; Official Statistics (Scotland), 2017) (see section 1.4). Coia *et al.* (2014) noted that GBMSM who report low self-esteem and/or loneliness found it more difficult to negotiate what they wanted from casual partners or in relationships due to the lack of self-confidence, ability or assertiveness. Some did not define their own limits, concerns or desires regarding sexual practices and took risks to fulfil a requirement for intimacy. Others were influenced by peers or cultural coercion to try to be more sexually exploratory and unrestrained, leading to riskier sex (Coia *et al.*, 2014). This can be intensified by poor mental health and intimate partner violence, exacerbating inequalities for GBMSM taking PrEP (Miltz *et al.*, 2019a; 2019b).

Participants in this study divided GBMSM into three age generations of older, middle aged and younger; and explained that HIV stigma and sexual experience related differently to each. Older GBMSM had experienced effects of the criminalisation of homosexuality in the UK prior to legal reform in 1967 and the devastating impact the AIDS epidemic (Ezhova *et al.*, 2020; Dalrymple *et al.*, 2019) (see section 1.4). Participants in this study explained how historically outlawing their sexuality had pushed sexual contact between men 'underground', skewing their outlook on sex and relationships and leading to sexual risk-taking behaviours. One participant explained how some GBMSM's viewpoints became confused, with encounters pared down to casual sexual gratification because there had been no permission for loving

relationships. Older participants in this study described how the AIDS epidemic had led to such a fear of HIV transmission that it had limited their sex lives in terms of intimacy as sex had been partnered with fear and dread of the risk of an untreatable infection.

Conversely, participants in this study felt that young GBMSM experienced less shame about their sexuality compared to older men because they had not lived through these experiences. Participants felt that Scottish culture today has 'mellowed' over time to a more accepting position of LGBT people. Additionally, younger GBMSM have poorer sexual health knowledge and HIV literacy and less concern about contracting STI's and HIV due to perceptions of effective treatments. Participants in this study felt that these factors contributed to a high level of condomless anal sex amongst young GBMSM; who could be 'naïve', 'immature' and not take their risk of HIV seriously. Concerns about confidentiality in sexual health clinics were also felt to be a particular barrier to access for young GBMSM; and participants recommended targeting schools, colleges and universities with information around sexual health and HIV. These findings are reflected in the literature (see section 6.4.2). Young GBMSM are more likely to be poorly informed about HIV risk, less likely to test for STIs and HIV and experience particular problems accessing sexual health services (Dalrymple *et al.*, 2019; Cassidy *et al.*, 2018; Coia *et al.*, 2014) (see section 1.4). These factors, together with inconsistent sex education, indicate challenges to HIV literacy for this population of young GBMSM in Scotland (Public Health Scotland, 2017). Consequently, they are less likely to access PrEP (Public Health Scotland, 2019).

HIV stigma and sexual health service stigma are barriers to uptake of PrEP for GBMSM linking to most of the constructs on the conceptual framework at structural, intermediate and individual levels:

Conceptual framework:

Availability – HIV stigma affects public health policy with regard to PrEP on a structural level and also affects GBMSM on social and individual levels, for example educational and employment opportunities. Stigma regarding sexual health services is present on social and individual levels as a barrier to PrEP availability.

Acceptability – HIV stigma influences culture and society and can result in external and internalised homophobia and discrimination for GBMSM, affecting individual risk taking behaviours, self-esteem and relationships. There is still shame attached to attending sexual health services in society.

Accessibility (non-discrimination) - HIV stigma is a barrier to PrEP for GBMSM who may have poor HIV literacy or not feel comfortable disclosing their sexuality. Concerns around confidentiality in sexual health services should be addressed. HIV and sexual health service stigmas are particular barriers to accessing PrEP for young GBMSM and those with a non-gay identity.

6.5.3 Rationale for PrEP uptake and use

Rationale for taking PrEP links to the aim and is research objective (1) in this study. All participants agreed that they had decided to commence taking PrEP medication because it reduces the chances of contracting HIV via unprotected sex (McCormack *et al.*, 2016). Many participants did not like to use condoms because of lack of sensation or intimacy and the technicalities of using them such as losing erections and problems with fit. Others did generally use condoms, but PrEP offered a second line of defence such as protecting against HIV risk from unplanned episodes of unprotected sex when drinking alcohol. This reduction in anxiety around contracting HIV with PrEP enabled participants to relax and enjoy their sexual experiences with less fear than in the past. These reasons for condomless sex are reflected in the literature in chapter two (Hughes *et al.*, 2018; McCormack *et al.*, 2016). Nutland *et al.* (2016) and Golub *et al.* (2013) concurred with the findings in this study that PrEP use can increase sexual pleasure, intimacy and opportunity and decrease the stress, fear and anxiety of contracting HIV, thus positively affecting mental health and wellbeing.

Participants in this study described several reasons in their experience as to why GBMSM who were at risk of HIV had decided not to take PrEP. Participants explained that poor HIV literacy was a significant factor and that many GBMSM they met did not think that they were at risk of HIV from their sexual behaviour despite having condomless anal sex with partners of unknown HIV status. These men had either not considered their HIV risk or had demonstrated flawed risk perception in thinking their HIV risk lower than it was. This is reflected in the literature (Frankis *et al.*, 2016). Young and McDaid (2014) added that some GBMSM believe they did not require PrEP as they used other methods of HIV prevention such as avoiding 'high-risk' sexual acts or using withdrawal during sex. A recent study by Grimshaw *et al.* (2021) examined 50 people who acquired HIV in Scotland and not taken PrEP, identifying that many of these individuals had not attended sexual health services or had an HIV test because they had not considered themselves at risk of HIV. Participants in this study added that further concerns regarding the quality of PrEP medication were around safety, particularly as it had been approved quite recently. Some participants did not like to take any medications or were concerned about unforeseen pharmacodynamic effects.

This is reflected in the literature in several studies, particularly with regard to taking medication in the long term, and can be linked to poor education (Garcia and Saw, 2019; Sowicz *et al.*, 2014; Golub *et al.*, 2013). Side effects to PrEP can also be a barrier to uptake and this is also well documented in the literature (Garcia and Saw, 2019; Golub *et al.*, 2013); however, none of the participants in this study had experienced any side effects. One participant in this study was concerned about the efficacy of PrEP after reading in the media about a man who had contracted HIV despite taking PrEP correctly and similar concerns about efficacy are reflected in the literature (Young, Flowers and McDaid, 2015; Sowicz *et al.*, 2014; Golub *et al.*, 2013). Finally, participants in this study explained that running out of PrEP was a significant barrier to continuation. Participants explained that accessing and taking PrEP entailed a sizeable burden, not only in terms of concordance but the requirement for the three-monthly visit to the clinic for the STI check and monitoring. This was pertinent because many common medications can be obtained locally on prescription from the GP with a long-term supply. This burden of the regimen of accessing and taking PrEP being

a barrier to acceptability and continuation is reflected in the literature (Rogers *et al.*, 2023).

The rationale for taking PrEP for GBMSM is linked to the availability, acceptability and quality constructs on the conceptual framework at structural, intermediate and individual levels.

Conceptual framework:

Availability – On structural and intermediate levels, the lack of communication and promotion of PrEP has led to a lack of awareness of PrEP amongst NHS staff and individual GBMSM. Poor education and HIV literacy are barriers to PrEP availability for GBMSM related to deprivation.

Acceptability – A lack of education, community engagement and stigma around sexual health, HIV and PrEP are barriers to acceptability of PrEP for GBMSM. Some may not realise their risk of HIV. The burden of accessing and taking PrEP due to the limited facilities dispensing PrEP is a barrier to PrEP acceptability and continuation for some.

Quality – GBMSM rationale for taking PrEP is due to the established efficacy in HIV prevention, associated with safety and reduced anxiety around HIV.

6.6 Subordinate Theme 3: GBMSM experience of taking PrEP

This section addresses the research objective (2) of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation experiences of taking and adherence to PrEP. Participants described PrEP medication as useful as it can be taken as required when sexually active. Many participants stopped PrEP during lockdown for COVID-19 because they were not able to go out and meet sexual partners. Other reasons for stopping PrEP had been due to being unwell, being abroad, working long hours and not going out or being in a long-term monogamous relationship. PrEP was restarted when the situation had changed. Harberer (2016) noted that PrEP is not meant to be taken continuously but as required when people may be at risk of HIV.

As described in chapter two section 2.6, PrEP can either be taken daily or 'event based' on demand when unprotected sex is anticipated (Molina *et al.*, 2015). Many participants in this study alternated between daily and event-based dosing regimens. The participants who preferred daily PrEP tended to meet their partners randomly and were unlikely to be anticipating sex so preferred to always be protected from HIV. The participants who preferred event-based PrEP knew when they would be going out and potentially having sex so could start their PrEP beforehand. Other reasons for taking 'event based' PrEP were not being very sexually active and taking other medications at the same time so preferring to take less medication overall.

Adherence to PrEP was also discussed in accordance with research objective (2). All participants in this study admitted that they sometimes forgot their PrEP medication, which they did not always disclose to clinic staff. Participants reported that barriers to adherence to PrEP were remembering to take it particularly when starting it, a break from routine such as not being at work, being away from home, running out of it and not liking to take pills. Substance use was another barrier to remembering PrEP. Participants concurred that the more complicated event-based PrEP regimen was more difficult to remember to take than daily PrEP. Facilitators to PrEP adherence for participants in this study were taking it as part of a habit or routine such as after a meal or when brushing teeth, taking it with other daily medications, dosette boxes and having a supply of tablets out of the house such as in a wallet. Further facilitators to

the continuation and adherence of PrEP were support from clinicians, the clarity of information in the PrEP leaflet and three-monthly clinic appointment reminders by text. Adherence to PrEP is essential for efficacy as the GBMSM in Scotland who have contracted HIV despite being prescribed PrEP are likely to have done so due to non-adherence (Public Health Scotland, 2019). Studies in the literature vary widely as to levels of adherence to PrEP from 80-90% to 20% (Montgomery *et al.*, 2016; Liu *et al.*, 2014; Hosek *et al.*, 2017) (see section 2.6). Sowicz *et al.* (2014) found that PrEP adherence was also shaped by the patients' perception of their risk of contracting HIV, which was often different to their actual risk. Regarding event-based PrEP, the findings in this study contest those in Molina *et al.* (2015) who found no difference in adherence between daily and event-based PrEP. However, Parsons *et al.* (2015) concurred with the findings in this study that adherence is lower with event-based PrEP as concord is required between anticipated and actual sexual behaviour. The literature regarding adherence to PrEP for GBMSM regarding aspects of deprivation is limited, however the findings from this study are in accordance with Shuper *et al.* (2022), who highlighted the extent and significance of alcohol, drugs and mental health conditions.

Consequently, participants in this study argued that PrEP being available in a longer-term injection form would be a very beneficial aid to adherence. Indeed, NICE (2022) has recently published guidance for injectable HIV treatment which will clearly negate barriers to adherence to oral PrEP such as forgetting tablets and ensure a therapeutic dose (Landovitz *et al.*, 2021). Long-acting medications are useful for people who struggle with concordance to oral medications and will also be useful for vulnerable groups such as injecting drug users or those wishing to conceal the fact that they are taking PrEP. In summary, the findings from this study are in concordance with the literature in the main in explaining barriers and facilitators to adherence to PrEP for GBMSM (Shuper *et al.*, 2022; Taylor *et al.*, 2014). Nevertheless, the importance of support from clinicians, the information in the PrEP leaflet and text reminders are new findings in this study. These findings link to the accessibility (non-discrimination) and quality sections of the conceptual framework.

Conceptual framework:

Acceptability (non-discrimination) - The different options of when and how to take PrEP can promote acceptability for GBMSM to suit on an individual level. Clinician support from an intermediate level is important to address individual barriers and facilitators to adherence to PrEP for GBMSM including aspects of deprivation such as alcohol/drugs and mental health. Clinicians can promote individual problem solving skills and provide leaflets, set up text reminders, etc.

Quality – Improved adherence will increase the efficacy of PrEP. The introduction of long acting medication formulations will be useful in this regard.

6.7 Subordinate Theme 4: Risk Compensation: GBMSM perceptions of PrEP and health outcomes/safety

6.7.1 The role of the ‘invincible shield’

Participants in this study used phrases describing PrEP as protection such as ‘invincible shield’, ‘safeguard’, a ‘safety net’, ‘guarantee’, ‘vaccine’, ‘life changing’ and ‘game changer’ because of its protection and efficacy in reducing the risk of contracting HIV via unprotected sex. This links to the research aim in this study and objective (1) experiences and rationale for uptake of PrEP. As described previously, participants had explained how PrEP results in less fear and stress around contracting HIV, empowering them to feel more relaxed and confident about their relationships and sexual health (see section 5.7.1). Participants also explained how the safety of having condomless sex with PrEP had increased intimacy with their partners and enabled them to become closer emotionally in relationships. Furthermore, participants in this study felt that PrEP had given them responsibility for their sexual health and a sense of agency; and that in the long-term PrEP would greatly reduce the incidence of HIV. These findings are reflected in the literature with GBMSM in England describing PrEP as ‘gift from the Gods,’ ‘life-changing’ and that they were ‘ridiculously lucky’ as PrEP would eradicate HIV (Lorenc *et al.*, 2020; Hughes *et al.*, 2018).

Conceptual framework:

Quality - The efficacy of PrEP reduces anxiety around HIV engendering better sex and relationships and is motivation for continuation of PrEP

6.7.2 Risk taking behaviour, sexual partners and PrEP

Participants in this study discussed the issue of trust between partners as another factor in their decision making in assessing HIV risk and whether to take PrEP. This sub theme relates to research objectives (1) and (3) of rationale for taking PrEP and changes to sexual health behaviours in the light of PrEP. Some participants in this study were concerned that the potential partner was actually taking PrEP as he said he was and asked to see the PrEP bottle or tablet before having sex. Participants explained how they were more likely to trust 'regular' partners known to them such as friends or long-term casual partners as they had an idea of their sexual behaviours, expected that they would have good adherence to PrEP and would be more likely to inform them if they were a contact of an STI. Furthermore, participants explained how they could be under pressure from a partner to stop PrEP because they had decided to be in a monogamous relationship, however, stopping PrEP relied on trusting the partner to be faithful and not bring HIV into the relationship. In the literature prior to PrEP rollout, Young, Flowers and McDaid (2015) had identified the concern that PrEP would reduce the requirement for a sexual agreement. Sexual agreements enable GBMSM couples to define clear expectancies about sex and sexual behaviour, manage their risk of HIV and STIs and establish boundaries and trust. Nevertheless, Coia *et al.* (2014) found that in reality, it is common for many GBMSM not to talk about sex or HIV status with potential partners prior to sex. Instead, many assumptions are made as to the potential partner's HIV status, with the prevalent belief amongst men that if someone is living with HIV, they will automatically disclose it to others (Coia *et al.*, 2014).

Trust amongst GBMSMs also related to long term relationships, with condomless sex a sign indicating monogamy, commitment and intimacy. However, participants explained how PrEP use had impacted on some couples in closed relationships, with the introduction of PrEP leading to an agreement to include other casual or regular sexual partners into the relationship. This appears to be a new finding in this study. Although the literature describes many GBMSM in relationships having agreements about concurrent partners or open relationships there appears to be scanty research around PrEP use instigating additional partners into relationships (Coia *et al.*, 2014).

Interestingly, some participants in this study said that they were more likely to have sex with men who were HIV positive and had an undetectable viral load after commencing PrEP as they had a better understanding of HIV transmission. Similar findings have been identified amongst PrEP users in England (Gafos *et al.*, 2019).

Participants in this study also considered whether the introduction of PrEP had affected other sexual health risk taking behaviours such as numbers of partners, frequency and type of sex and establishing when the potential partner had last had a sexual health screen. A half of the participants in this study said that PrEP had made no difference to their sexual health behaviours other than reducing their condom use. The other half said that taking PrEP had increased their risk-taking behaviour in sexual encounters due to a sense of freedom with regard to sex. They described this as feeling heterosexual or in terms of 'coming out' or like 'a kid in a candy shop' where they were able to have sex with as many different people as they liked as PrEP had removed the fear of HIV. For some of these participants this increased sexual risk-taking behaviour was temporary; but for others these behaviours continued. Interestingly, one participant in this study noted that removing the risk of HIV with PrEP could lead to even more extreme sexual health risk taking behaviours for some GBMSM as they became 'desensitised' and looked to replace the risk during sex. This appears to be a new finding in this study. This was described by Allen-Scott, Hatfield and McIntyre (2014) as an unintended 'boomerang effect', where the prevention of an extreme event counterproductively leads to another extreme event. This has been seen in other health interventions, for example where attempts to prevent obesity have led to anorexia (Allen-Scott, Hatfield and McIntyre, 2014). Participants felt that more tailored education and support around negotiating PrEP and risk-taking behaviours with partners would address this issue.

The findings in this study again contest much of the initial research around PrEP which suggested that there was limited or no change to sexual risk-taking behaviour due to PrEP (McCormack *et al.*, 2016). Nevertheless, studies in the literature have identified a higher number of sexual partners due to PrEP (Oldenburg *et al.*, 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2016; Baeten *et al.*, 2012). Gafos *et al.* (2019) found in their English study that PrEP use was associated with GBMSM increasingly taking part in receptive anal sex, drug

taking and not asking their partner if they had been tested for HIV. Additionally, socio-economic status remains a consideration as GBMSM living in poverty are more likely to exhibit risky sexual health behaviours due to power imbalances and economic dependence (Closson *et al.*, 2018). Mental health and wellbeing are also linked to sexual health behaviours, and GBMSM taking PrEP can experience high levels of intimate partner violence and depression, exacerbating inequalities (Miltz *et al.*, 2019a; 2019b). This is linked to accessibility of PrEP in the conceptual framework.

Conceptual framework:

Acceptability – Individual relationships and trust between partners is a significant factor for GBMSM affecting HIV risk compensation and acceptability of PrEP

Accessibility (non-discrimination) - PrEP may be associated with an increase in risk taking sexual behaviours such as an increase in the number of partners. Deprivation is a consideration on individual and intermediate levels here as financial, social or health considerations can cause power imbalances in relationships between GBMSM, exacerbating inequalities and HIV risk.

6.7.3 PrEP role and other STIs

This sub theme is linked to research objective (3) in this study exploring insight into sexual health behaviours in the light of PrEP. Most participants in this study felt that as GBMSM were largely replacing condoms with PrEP for HIV prevention this would reduce the risk of HIV but increase the risk of the other STI's such as chlamydia, gonorrhoea and syphilis. Several participants described personal experience of contracting new bacterial STIs due to condomless sex with PrEP, and all thought that the incidence of STI's excluding HIV had increased accordingly. This viewpoint appears to result from their personal experience as the literature tends to dispute a relationship between PrEP use and an increase in the incidence of other STI's (Public Health Scotland, 2019; Reyniers *et al.*, 2017; McCormack *et al.*, 2016). Nevertheless,

Traeger *et al.* (2018) noted that an absence of control data in observational studies makes attributing changes in sexual behaviour to PrEP use alone problematic, with unmeasured or unanalysed confounders potentially biasing results. Some participants in this study had employed risk reduction strategies after contracting an STI such as fewer partners or going back to using condoms more often and some had not. Nevertheless, no participants were prepared to return to consistent condom use to prevent other STI's. All took responsibility for this decision and said that although they were aware they should be using condoms, all had decided to risk another STI instead, together with varying degrees of concern. From their experience participants explained that an STI would be quickly diagnosed and treated at the routine three-month sexual health screen and all felt that bacterial STI's were 'nothing' as they were very easily cured with a 'jag or tablet'. Many participants were aware of antibiotic resistance, particularly those who worked in healthcare, but the feeling appeared to be that this risk was very remote and unlikely and would not affect them. Participants in this study added that the feeling of immunity to HIV that PrEP provided influenced how they felt about other STI's in that they felt 'immune' from those as well. This is a new finding in this study. Lorenc *et al.* (2020) in England concurred that other STI's were 'inevitable' with PrEP. Balan *et al.* (2019) in New York added that the regular testing with PrEP and previous negative test results had led to a sense of a low risk of infection, with STI treatments thought to be fast, simple and effective amongst GBMSM taking PrEP.

Participants in this study agreed that ignorance around STIs was still prevalent amongst many GBMSM in Scotland because STI's were rarely discussed outside of the sexual health and 'gay scene' settings. However, the emergence of antibiotic resistant strains of gonorrhoea in particular are becoming a significant public health concern and an increase in the incidence of other STI's at a population level will have implications for both individuals and NHS services (Public Health Scotland, 2017). This would be another potential and unintended 'boomerang effect' of PrEP (Allen-Scott, Hatfield and McIntyre, 2014). Therefore, the demonstration in the findings of this study that these participants are prepared to take personal responsibility for their sexual health suggests that further health promotion around the risk of antibiotic resistance and possibility of untreatable infections may be effective. Health promotion

can stress the reassurance of negative test results and promote consideration of how GBMSM are going to protect themselves and their partners moving forward. This links to PrEP accessibility on the conceptual framework.

Conceptual framework:

Accessibility (non-discrimination) - A potential increase in STI's due to a reduction in condom use will also affect PrEP acceptability (opportunity cost) and quality on individual, intermediate and structural levels. Health promotion is required to endorse antibiotic stewardship and prevent the possibility of untreatable STIs.

6.8 Revisit new PrEP patient journey conceptual framework

This section revisits the PrEP patient journey conceptual framework for this study as outlined in chapter three and section 6.2, presenting the framework together with the concepts identified throughout this chapter six.

Figure 6.4 New PrEP patient journey conceptual framework with concepts

The conceptual framework for this study is able to capture the patient journey by depicting the individual's movement through the five constructs. Here, PrEP is available from the NHS, the individual becomes aware of it and considers it, attends the clinic for a consultation and finally becomes actively engaged in continuing to take it. During this physical and emotional journey, the patient experience is at the centre of the framework where they are in contact with the health service at a consecutive series of 'touch points' across episodes of care (Davies *et al.*, 2022). Behaviours, feelings, motivations and attitudes are captured at individual, social and structural levels to incorporate the economic, political, cultural and social determinants of health.

The success of PrEP in Scotland has seen the annual incidence of HIV fall by 75% for GBMSM taking PrEP in 2021 with additional population-level protection against HIV (Estcourt, *et al.*, 2021). One participant in this study described himself as 'middle aged, affluent and white' and receiving PrEP, however an intersectional approach demonstrates how others at risk of HIV with lower socio-economic status in this study may be less likely to do so. This PrEP patient journey conceptual framework contributes to new knowledge by illustrating the structural, intermediate and individual level barriers and facilitators involved in the uptake of PrEP for GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation. The super-ordinate themes in the findings and conceptual framework in this study highlight the value of culturally competent clinical healthcare staff in providing PrEP and their importance as a resource and model for good practice, and the normalisation of PrEP in replacing condoms for HIV prevention. However, HIV stigma and decisions around the promotion of PrEP in Scotland have prompted perceptions of discrimination amongst GBMSM and distinct barriers to acceptability and accessibility of PrEP experienced particularly by young and bisexual GBMSM, highlighting implications in terms of HIV risk and further health inequalities. The subordinate themes in the findings and conceptual framework in this study follow the research aim and objectives for this study, demonstrating how deprivation in terms of income, employment, education, health and access to services (Public Health Scotland, 2020) are experienced by GBMSM in terms of rationale, barriers, adherence and behaviour change relating to uptake of PrEP.

The findings from this study incorporated into the conceptual framework confirm that the biomedical intervention of PrEP alone does not respond to the multifaceted sexual health needs of GBMSM in Scotland, which has implications for a rights-based approach to healthcare (Young, 2021, p.68; WHO, 2017). Parker and Aggleton (2003) highlighted the manner in which HIV stigma and discrimination reinforce and reproduce existing inequalities of deprivation, sexuality, class, gender and race. Attention is required to tackle the healthcare system's failure to acknowledge the socio-structural factors that impact on GBMSM healthcare needs with regard to PrEP services and awareness campaigns. Addressing the broader political economy of social exclusion will challenge the deeper social, political and economic causes of HIV stigma and discrimination (Parker and Aggleton, 2003). Community engagement is

required to co-create multi-dimensional programs of intervention which include structural level factors such as deprivation to address health service equity, inequalities and barriers to acceptability and accessibility of for PrEP. The use of the new PrEP patient journey conceptual framework highlights that at present, the quality of PrEP has been established and it is available; however it is not necessarily acceptable or accessible to all at risk of HIV. The use of the 'marketing mix' tool in the framework provides corresponding areas of focus that can be used in strategic decision making to overcome the barriers to healthcare identified and meet patient need.

6.9 Summary of chapter six

This chapter has focused on the integrative IPA-informed thematic data analysis and clarification of the study findings in dialogue with the existing literature to critically appraise the research aim of understanding the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. The creation of the new PrEP patient journey conceptual framework has provided focus and structure for the findings of this study; presenting the findings and themes as new contribution to existing knowledge. Critical exploration of the findings suggest that disparities in awareness, acceptability and accessibility of PrEP remain along traditional indicators of inequality and socio-economic status. This study finds that GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation can face challenges on individual, social and structural levels in terms of uptake of PrEP.

Chapter seven: Conclusions

This chapter presents the strengths and limitations of this study, reflections on the study design and information on how reflexivity was achieved, together with recommendations for policy, practice and further research. Finally, the conclusion returns to the research aim and objectives and summarises the outcome and significance of the study.

7.1 Strengths and limitations

This section considers strengths and limitations of the study design. Firstly, the sample is derived from those attending sexual health clinics which may not be reflective of a wider population of all GBMSM in Scotland because those eligible for PrEP but do not attend sexual health clinics were not included. GBMSM who are buying PrEP were also not included. However, GBMSM who may be at risk of HIV but do not attend sexual health services are a hidden population, particularly if they are not involved in the 'gay scene'. It can be argued that the use of purposive sampling in this study is a strength as the participants were themselves already having conversations about PrEP with other men they encountered including discussions around why people were not taking it. Although the information was filtered through the viewpoints of these interviewees (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018, p.193), it can be argued that these participants are ideally placed to reach this hidden population.

Secondly, a limitation of the use of SIMD quintiles are that they provide a measure of deprived areas, not deprived individuals (Public Health Scotland, 2020). Hence, as was noted in this study, not all people living in lower SIMD quintiles are materially disadvantaged and vice versa. Many participants in this study were educated to degree level or higher and were employed in traditionally professional occupations. Nevertheless, SIMD quintiles were thought to be a comprehensive and useful tool to identify relative deprivation as they include 32 indicators such as resources and opportunities in addition to income. Furthermore, SIMD is used by the Scottish Government to target health interventions so was considered the most appropriate tool to measure deprivation in this case (Public Health Scotland, 2020).

Finally, this thesis relied on qualitative data alone. The inclusion of quantitative data and a mixed methods study may have provided further insight where statistical analysis and interpretation of data may indicate or disprove a relationship between PrEP awareness and uptake and deprivation for GBMSM. This requires further study.

7.2 Reflections on the study design

The next two sections will be discussed in the first person for clarity as they concern my impact as the lead researcher. Firstly, I was satisfied that ethical principles, rigour and trustworthiness were adhered to in this study (Polit and Beck, 2020, p.121; David and Sutton, 2011, p.42). For example, confidentiality, informed consent and data protection were achieved via compliance with the details specified by the ethics committee and there were no breaches of confidentiality (Gelling, 2015, p.155). The participants in this study did not have any questions or express that they had any concerns regarding the study design. Therefore, I am satisfied that all gave informed consent. Similarly, respondents did not appear anxious or distressed during the interviews. However, to be sure that this risk was mitigated I explained that support was available; although this was not required. Respondents remained anonymous to me as a health care worker. An unintended advantage of the decision to use telephone interviews for this study added an element of safety to data collection for both participant and myself as not meeting in person removed potential transmission of COVID-19. Furthermore, as the interviews took place during lockdown restrictions, many participants were not working and unable to go out therefore were available and keen to be interviewed to be able to talk to someone.

With regards to reflection on the impact of the methodological choices in this study, semi-structured interviews provided a quantity and richness of data and 'thick description' which led to in-depth views and participants' accounts. My decision to transcribe interviews as they occurred also proved to be fortunate as new themes such as HIV stigma were raised by participants which were included as questions in the latter interviews. The use of the IPA informed thematic framework for data analysis developed in this study followed that of Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2022, p.82), and this iterative process is a characteristic of IPA (Smith, 2017). After data collection, I

was certain that IPA informed thematic analysis had been the correct approach for this study. Smith, Flowers and Larkin (2022, p.143) explained how IPA is often used in sexual health research as it challenges understandings based around the 'othering' of people and medicalising behaviours. During the interviews, these concepts were advanced directly by the participants themselves as important considerations although they had not been part of the initial interview topic guide. Furthermore, IPA captures 'the particular' rather than the nomothetic (Smith, Flowers and Larkin, 2022, p.30) which is appropriate with regard to PrEP medication as deciding to take it is more of a personal choice due to situation-specific factors, which may not be the case for many other medications. Regarding data analysis within this study, I thought of participant experience as being the outcome of variables such as personal beliefs, values, past experience, attitudes and knowledge. These factors underpinned the process of interpretation by each participant and although each interpretation was different due to differing experiences and beliefs, there were also similarities which indicated common and/or shared experience. Therefore, the assumption can be made that participants' experiences will have commonality with other GBMSM who are eligible for PrEP with lower socio-economic status.

A valid interpretation of the study findings was achieved by the adoption of well-established and structured research methods. As outlined in section 4.3.10, the use of practices such as peer review, a pilot interview and regular meetings with my supervisors ensured rigour and trustworthiness. Appendix 16 provides an example of data analysis confirmation by my supervisors.

7.3 Reflexivity and reflections on the research process

Reflexivity was achieved by being conscious of my potential prejudices and personal values which may bias the participants and influence the findings, particularly as I am part of the researched world. Firstly, I had to be mindful that I was working as a researcher rather than a nurse and that the participants were not in a nurse-patient relationship, hence the importance of remaining neutral. The use of field notes, a personal journal and discussions with my supervisors promoted reflexivity and offered an audit trail. I met with my supervisors regularly and these supervision sessions

provided the chance to for reflection on the development and execution of this study and to learn from the experiences of others in how to avoid potential bias. An example of this was to be careful not include my own suggestions for sexual health service redesign but only those raised by the participants. I feel that I was successful in minimising potential researcher bias as participants did not give the same responses to similar questions as they tended to during PrEP consultations in clinic. An example would be medication concordance; in clinic it was extremely rare in my experience for any patient to admit forgetting PrEP however in the interviews participants disclosed that forgetting PrEP medication was commonplace amongst themselves and other users. I had been concerned that the participants' awareness that I was a sexual health nurse may have introduced an element of potential bias as they did not criticise the staff; however, they did criticise the service.

Throughout the course and progression of this thesis, I am conscious of my personal position within it as a sexual health nurse working in PrEP clinics and someone with strong political views on inequality and am mindful of the influence that position may have on the research. An advantage of this position is that I already had a good understanding of many of the aspects of HIV and PrEP medication and was familiar with working with GBMSM and comfortable with frank discussions of sex. Conversely, I was disadvantaged in that I commenced this research with an a priori assumption that I had a complete understanding of PrEP and why GBMSM may use it, and also that socioeconomic status would have an influence on PrEP uptake because deprivation has already been found to be the one key determinant of health inequalities (Audit Scotland, 2012).

The depth of the qualitative data analysis based on IPA allowed me to hear the extent and complexity of the life experiences and interpretations of the participants and their significance. These a posteriori findings challenged my initial view from my experience in clinic that I thought I knew the personal perspectives of the patients. Instead, I felt privileged to be provided with an insight into the lives of these participants and was able to understand for example the complexity around how HIV stigma and risk had shaped how they viewed themselves within society and the different ways of how they made sense of these influences to be able to manage sex and their relationships.

Finally, now data collection is complete, dissemination is important for the voices of the participants in this study to be heard. I have been successful at conference with three poster presentations regarding this study, one of which was awarded third prize. I will also disseminate the findings of this study via publication in relevant peer reviewed journals in sexual health. This will contribute to new knowledge by informing PrEP roll out in other countries and in Scotland benefit patients by identifying some of the problems around NHS service provision, providing information around the barriers to uptake of PrEP for these GBMSM and other individuals who may be at high risk of HIV.

7.4 Recommendations

7.4.1 Implications for practice

Recommendation 1. Sexual health clinics - locations

PrEP should become available from other sexual health clinic locations in addition to the city centre to improve ease of access for people living more remotely, for example the outlying clinics.

Recommendation 2. Sexual health clinics - appointments

PrEP appointments should be at a range of times to suit those who work unsociable hours. A choice between face to face and remote telephone appointments with postal kits is preferable. A choice between appointments in men only or mixed gender spaces is desirable.

Recommendation 3. Sexual health clinics confidentiality

Sexual health clinics should address the lack of confidentiality at clinic reception where people in the waiting room can hear patients' names as concerns about confidentiality are a barrier to access for some.

Recommendation 4. Sexual health clinics risk taking

Longer appointment times are required for the clinician to provide tailored education and support around negotiating PrEP and risk-taking sexual behaviours, such as awareness and associated implications of acquiring other STIs.

Recommendation 5. Long-acting PrEP

Initiate long-acting formulations of PrEP medication such as injections to promote concordance generally; particularly useful for populations such as people who inject drugs.

7.4.2 Implications for policy

Recommendation 1. PrEP availability

Develop provision so that PrEP is accessible from a range of services to improve ease of access such as G.P. surgeries on prescription and pharmacies.

Recommendation 2. Raise awareness of HIV

Raise HIV awareness and consequently HIV literacy in the Scottish population in general to reach younger and bisexual GBMSM. HIV should be addressed during sex education in schools and at colleges and universities.

Recommendation 3. Raise awareness of sexual health services

Promote NHS sexual health services to increase awareness of the services available and address barriers to access. This information should include the clinic location, what the service provides and that sexual health services are free and confidential.

Recommendation 4. Raise awareness of PrEP

PrEP should be promoted in the same way as other medications to raise awareness. The campaign should target cruising areas, community events such as Gay Pride, adverts on mobile phone apps and in pubs, clubs, colleges, universities and schools.

Recommendation 5. Community engagement

Commence community engagement and participation to address social and community challenges to PrEP awareness and uptake.

Recommendation 6. Wider NHS engagement

Raise awareness of PrEP in the wider NHS so that healthcare professionals outside of sexual health are aware of PrEP and are able to advise patients at risk of HIV.

7.4.3 Implications for research

Recommendation 1. Further study

Further study is required as to ascertain whether living in areas of remoteness or rurality may be a barrier for GBMSM considering PrEP.

Recommendation 2. Quantitative study

Quantitative study is required to accept or reject the hypothesis that PrEP uptake is related to deprivation and/or education.

Recommendation 3. Further quantitative study

STI incidence and prevalence should be monitored to ascertain potential impact of PrEP use on STI rates.

Recommendation 4. Further qualitative study

Further study is required to identify potential expected and unexpected outcomes of PrEP including effects on other HIV prevention methods and sexual health behaviours.

7.5 Conclusions

Whilst researching and writing this thesis, the number of GBMSM accessing PrEP in Scotland has increased and the available knowledge and literature regarding PrEP has become more extensive (Estcourt *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, in this concluding chapter it is important to return to the original research aim and objectives of this study to ensure they have been met. The aim of the research was to understand the experiences of GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation in Scotland who are taking NHS PrEP. The research objectives are: 1) exploration of the rationale for and experiences of accessing and utilising PrEP; 2) understanding of the barriers and facilitators to uptake and adherence to PrEP and 3) gaining insight into sexual health behaviours due to PrEP for this population. These are reflected in the Patient Journey conceptual framework (section 6.8).

- 1) The rationale for taking PrEP amongst GBMSM living in areas of high deprivation was found to be due to the efficacy of PrEP for HIV prevention, leading to reduced anxiety around HIV and better sex and relationships. The fact PrEP is free of charge is also important. However, this study provides new evidence that the decision to defer awareness campaigns of PrEP has added to the lack of awareness of PrEP for many GBMSM such as those who were not part of the 'gay scene' and also amongst staff in the wider NHS. This was seen as in addition to already existing HIV stigma and discrimination and, together with poor education and HIV literacy in relation to deprivation, has introduced barriers to availability of PrEP for GBMSM.
- 2) Critical appraisal of the findings in this study also provides new evidence of physical and socioeconomic barriers to accessibility of PrEP for GBMSM living in SIMD quintiles one and two and/or those with lower income and educational attainment, suggesting a relationship between deprivation category and acceptability and accessibility of PrEP in Scotland. This study has also contributed new knowledge by identifying the effect of HIV stigma on the awareness and acceptability of PrEP, which influences sexual health seeking, HIV testing and sexual risk-taking behaviours. HIV stigma has affected

particularly younger GBMSM and those with a non-gay identity, who were less likely to attend sexual health services and access PrEP. Many contributory factors were identified, such as deprivation, substandard sex education, inconsistent perceptions of HIV risk, low HIV literacy and concerns about confidentiality in clinics. In terms of experiences of service provision, GBMSM in this study highlight the significance of cultural competence of sexual healthcare staff for successful PrEP implementation in Scotland. Holistic consideration of factors that affect an individual's health and attitudes such as deprivation, stigma and inequality, and the capability to identify shared meanings with the patient have enhanced patient adherence, empowerment and agency regarding HIV prevention and PrEP. The clinicians identified in this study provide an important resource for modelling best practice in patient care regarding PrEP provision.

- 3) In the absence of PrEP awareness campaigns, the findings in this study demonstrate the development of PrEP where GBMSM taking it are raising awareness and encouraging others to incorporate it into everyday use. This study highlights an emerging shift where PrEP is replacing condoms for HIV prevention and men are refusing to have sex with potential partners who are not taking PrEP; consequently, GBMSM are experiencing pressure to stop using condoms and commence PrEP instead specifically to be sexually active. This unintended consequence of PrEP pressures GBMSM towards condomless sex, an upturn in sexual health risk taking behaviours for some and accommodation regarding the risk of other STI's. This study suggests that condomless sex may be increasing amongst GBMSM overall yet those living in areas of higher deprivation are less likely to be aware of and access PrEP. This could potentially further exacerbate health inequalities for GBMSM with lower socioeconomic status and have implications for increased HIV prevalence in this population.

This study has been successful in meeting the research aim and objectives as above. However, deprivation is multi-faceted and whilst participants in this study provided their experiences of deprivation in terms of income, employment, health and access

to services; other aspects of deprivation such as crime and housing (Public Health Scotland, 2020) were not addressed. Further study is required to also explore GBMSM experiences of PrEP in relation to crime such as intimate partner violence and housing in terms of poor or insecure housing as a cause for health inequalities. Furthermore, literature from the USA such as Dehlin *et al.* (2019) and Burns *et al.* (2021) suggested area level deprivation as a barrier to PrEP, and this requires study with regard to the UK.

This thesis provides insight and a contribution to existing knowledge with a new understanding of the lived experience of GBMSM with lower socio-economic status regarding uptake of PrEP medication. It can be argued that the findings in this study are transferrable to similar populations at risk of HIV, helping to inform other practitioners working in the field and the further rollout of PrEP. The use of the PrEP patient journey conceptual framework includes the WHO (2017) AAAQ rights-based approach to healthcare to ensure that PrEP services are following the Scottish government standards for healthcare provision (Population Health Directorate, (Scotland), 2021). By demonstrating and encompassing the complex interlocking of political, biomedical, social and cultural forces with diverse meanings and values that exist within PrEP, the framework identifies corresponding areas of focus to address the barriers to healthcare and meet patient need.

Appendix 1: Eligibility criteria for PrEP in Scotland

Age 16 +AND			
Resident in Scotland AND			
HIV negative AND			
ONE OR MORE OF:			
a current sexual health partner, irrespective of gender, of people who are HIV positive and have a detectable viral load OR	a GBMSM or transgender woman with a documented bacterial rectal STI in the last 12 months OR	a GBMSM or transgender woman reporting condomless penetrative anal sex with 2 or more partners in the last 12 months, and likely to do so again in the next 3 months OR	an equivalent high risk of HIV acquisition as agreed with another specialist clinician

(Brady *et al.*, 2019)

Appendix 2: Historical and current pathways of care for HIV and AIDS

YEAR	TREATMENT AND TESTING	OUTCOME
1982	No treatment for HIV/AIDS ¹	Hospitalisation and death ¹
1987	U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) license ELISA test, the first commercial blood test to detect HIV antibodies then Western blot commercial test for HIV antibodies ² First antiretroviral drug, AZT/Zidovudine, approved by FDA to treat HIV after successful clinical trial. AZT blocks action of HIV enzyme reverse transcriptase, stopping the virus from replicating in cells ²	Distinction between HIV and AIDS established; increased accuracy of testing ² Slows down the course of AIDS, delaying death. Is recommended for pregnant women with HIV in USA and transmission to foetuses reduces from 25% to 8% ²
1995	FDA approval of Saquinavir, or Highly Active Antiretroviral Therapy (HAART), a combination of drugs working as protease inhibitor; forming defective HIV which cannot infect new cells ²	Revolutionary new extremely effective medication, reducing AIDS related deaths and hospitalization by 60 to 80%. AIDS no longer thought of as 'death sentence' ²
2006	Male circumcision found to reduce HIV transmission and subsequently recommended by WHO and UNAIDS ³	Risk of female-to-male HIV transmission reduced by 60% ³
2012	FDA approved PrEP in the USA ³ New treatment guidelines launched by WHO recommended early initiation of antiretroviral treatment as soon as possible after diagnosis regardless of CD4 count, or Treatment as Prevention of HIV, or TasP ³	Varying levels of effectiveness dependent on setting ³ Risk of HIV transmission reduced by 96% among sero discordant couples ³
2017	Prevention Access Campaign launch of anti-stigma information campaign 'Undetectable = Untransmittable' (U=U) ³ .	HIV positive people who adhere to treatment with undetectable viral load cannot transmit HIV ³

(C.D.C., 1981¹; Hughes, Barber and Nelson, 2008²; UNAIDS, 2017³).

Appendix 3: Keywords, delineators and truncation used in literature search

Core keyword	All keywords used
PrEP	'PrEP' OR 'Pre-exposure prophylaxis' OR 'Pre exposure prophylaxis' OR 'Preexposure prophylaxis'
	AND
GBMSM	'GBMSM*' OR 'MSM*' OR 'men who have sex with men' OR 'homosexual*' OR 'gay*' OR 'bisexual*' OR 'LGBT*'
	AND
Deprivation	'Deprivation' OR 'deprived' OR 'socio economic' OR 'socio-economic' OR 'socioeconomic' OR 'low income' OR 'low-income' OR 'poor' OR 'poverty' OR 'inequalit*'

Appendix 4: PRISMA screening process and reviewed studies

Appendix 5: Characteristics of studies included in thesis literature review

Author	Design	Sample	Country	Aim	Results/Findings	Limitations
Dehlin <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Quantitative Regression analysis of phone line data	150 GB MSM	USA	Examine why Black MSM are not engaged in PrEP care cascade	MORE AND THEME GBMSM living in areas higher poverty are less likely to initiate PrEP	Missing data Participants referred internally
Burns <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Computer self survey Logistic regression analysis	142 GB MSM	USA	Examine how structural factors affect PrEP uptake in poor neighbourhoods	Neighbourhood poverty rates, unstable housing & incarceration affect PrEP uptake	Purposive sample Postcodes used to define neighbourhoods
Blashill <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Computer self survey Logistic regression analysis	151 GB MSM	USA	Examine why Latino MSM are not engaged in PrEP care cascade	Structural barriers affect awareness of PrEP & psychosocial barriers affect adherence	Cross-sectional study Low power
Garcia and Saw (2019)	Computer self survey Multiple regression analysis	154 GB MSM	USA	Explore barriers to PrEP for Latino GBMSM	Low socio economic status and HIV stigma negatively affect PrEP uptake	Convenience sample Low power
Jaspal <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Cross sectional survey	191 GB MSM	England	Examine impact of income & education on HIV literacy/PrEP	Lower-level education & income less likely to use PrEP	Opportunity sample Partially anticipated behaviour
Golub <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Cross sectional survey	177 GB MSM	USA	Identify barriers & facilitators to PrEP uptake and adherence	Cost, safety, efficacy, location of service & stigma identified	Sampling & powering unclear
Taylor <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Focus groups Descriptive design	39 GB MSM	USA	Identify barriers and facilitators to PrEP adherence	Facilitators: routines, reminders. Barriers: mental health, drugs, alcohol	Confidentiality Difference in sampling methods

Shuper <i>et al.</i> (2022)	5 focus groups	35 GB MSM	Canada	Explore if alcohol/drugs or depression affects PrEP adherence	The severity of the factor affects adherence to PrEP	Convenience sample Excludes vulnerable people who cant attend clinic
Hughes <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Telephone interviews Grounded theory	32 GB MSM	USA	Identify role of PrEP re sexual health behaviours	Reduction in sexual risk taking behaviour, increase in STIs	Recruited from another study
McCormack <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Double blind RCT	545 GB MSM	England	Efficacy of PrEP in real world setting	Efficacy: 86% No change to STI rates with PrEP	Quasi experiment Self-reporting bias
Rogers <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Interviews from longitudinal study	19 GB MSM	USA	Explore barriers to retention in PrEP care	Barriers: finance, transport, appt times, poor HIV literacy, misinformation	Generalisability

Appendix 6: CASP tool quality assessment of PrEP evidence

RCTs

Study	Randomisation	Allocation concealment	Groups similar at baseline	Eligibility criteria specified	Blinding	Attrition high	Analysis by group	Quality rating
McCormack <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Yes	Unclear	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Fair

Cross sectional studies

Study	Sampling	Confounders addressed	Analysis defined	Outcomes defined	Discussion	Risk of bias	Precision/Quality
Dehlin <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Convenience	Yes – some missing data	Yes	Yes	Yes	Some	Fair/Good
Burns <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Purposive	Yes – not able to infer causality	Yes	Yes	Yes	Less	Good
Blashill <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Convenience	Yes – not able to infer causality	Yes	Yes	Yes	Less	Good
Garcia and Saw (2019)	Convenience	Not given	Yes	Yes	Yes	Less	Good
Jaspal <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Opportunity	Yes – not able to infer causality	Yes	Yes	Yes	Less	Good
Golub <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Unclear, non probability	no comparison to adherence of other medication	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Fair

Qualitative studies

Study	Sampling	Ethics	Methodology	Recruitment	Discussion	Risk of bias	Credibility of findings/Quality
Shuper <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Convenience	Yes	5 focus groups Thematic analysis	From 2 x PrEP clinics	Yes	Some	Good
Rogers <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Purposive from longitudinal study	Yes	Individual interviews Thematic analysis	From larger PrEP study	Yes	Less	Good
Taylor <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Purposive/Convenience	Yes	4 focus groups Descriptive design	From PrEP study/community	Yes		Good
Hughes <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Purposive	Yes	Individual interviews Grounded theory	From PrEP study	Yes	Yes	Good

Appendix 7: Informal local approval email

Email from Clinical Director

From: MCGOUGH, Pauline (NHS [REDACTED])
Sent: 17 April 2018 15:48
To: ROONEY, Elizabeth ([REDACTED])
Subject: RE: prof doc research on PrEP

This sounds really interesting and well worth doing – I would support the use of NaSH for this purpose. Go to Martin S with what you need once your plans are a little more advanced thanks P

Pauline McGough FFSRH FRCOG

Consultant in sexual and reproductive health

Clinical Director

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Please note I have reduced my hours and have clinical commitments on Mondays and Fridays. Please don't expect responses to emails on those days.

PA Frances Doherty

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Appendix 8: Local research enquiry process form

Research enquiry process

We welcome research at and aim to make the process as easy as possible. If you would like to conduct research within or with clients, please complete this short form and email it to Lorraine Forster, Nurse Consultant, via email address @research@ggc.scot.nhs.uk along with any protocols/proposals, so that the suitability of for the project can be assessed.

The form and protocol will be assessed by

- An appropriate clinical lead for the area, for assessment of suitability in the field and with the client base
- Research Governance Group

If we believe that the research is of interest we will nominate a member of the clinical team to act as your local collaborator (if you have not already identified one prior to submitting your enquiry). If we do not feel that this research is appropriate we will let you know without delay. All requests will have a response within 4 weeks.

Research Enquiry process version 3 May 2017

	<p>recommendations for best practice regarding PrEP provision. This will benefit both the [redacted] clinic and service users, with the dissemination of the findings raising the profile of the [redacted] and complementing the service review. Barriers to PrEP provision can be addressed and facilitators identified, with the findings providing a greater understanding of PrEP uptake and retention and enabling improvements to the service for clients and staff.</p>
<p>What are the potential risks to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • health, safety and wellbeing of researchers and research participants? • the organisation? 	<p>There should be no detriment to the participants; however if a participant does become upset the lead researcher is well qualified to undertake support and signposting to professional help as she is an experienced senior nurse. Subjects will not include those in a dependent relationship. Participants will not be over researched as the lead researcher will check with each participant that they are not taking part in other studies at the same time.</p> <p>There should be no risk to the lead researcher, particularly with the use of telephone interviewing.</p> <p>There should be no risk to the organisation.</p>
<p>Are there any ethical issues? Will you be applying to an ethics committee? If not, have you ascertained that your study does not require it?</p>	<p>Favourable ethical opinion will be sought from the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee and an appropriate REC before patients are entered into this study as outlined in The Research Governance Framework for Health and Social Care (Department of Health, 2005). Written approval to carry out the study will be sought from the head of service at the [redacted].</p> <p>Clients will only be allowed to enter the study once they have</p>

[redacted] Research Enquiry process version 3 May 2017

	<p>provided written informed consent. Verbal and written information prior to interviews will inform participants that they may decline to answer questions and withdraw at any point from the study until a week after the interview without giving a reason and that their medical care will not be affected.</p> <p>The CI will be responsible for updating the Ethics committee of any new information related to the study.</p> <p>Data will be stored securely on paper and in electronic form on a secure NHS computer according to the Data Protection Act (1998). Only the lead researcher and her UWS supervisors will have access to this. Confidentiality will be maintained throughout the study by using study numbers only to identify participants. Other participant information data stored and linked separately. Pseudonyms will be used for quotations when the work is published or presented. Data will be destroyed after five years as per University of the West of Scotland policy.</p>
<p>What would be required of [redacted] in terms of sites/clinics involved, staff workload and time, room space, storage, equipment, etc?</p>	<p>It will be requested that the [redacted] staff member consulting the prospective participants already identified prior to attending the PrEP clinic will pass the patient information sheet and consent form to the client. The study will be carried out in the researchers own time and the costs of the computer, phone calls, and information leaflets will be met using the researchers' personal resources.</p>
<p>What legal requirements govern the research?</p>	<p>The study will be carried out in accordance with the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki (1964) and its revisions (Tokyo [1975], Venice [1983], Hong Kong [1989], South Africa [1996] and</p>

[redacted] Research Enquiry process version 3 May 2017

	Edinburgh [2000]).
When do you anticipate the study would start and finish?	It is expected that the Phase 1 Data collection section of the study will take place in April/May 2020. It is expected that that recruitment for Phase 2 Interviews will commence in June/July 2020 and continue for three months.
How will the findings be disseminated?	This study is taking place as part of a Professional Doctorate qualification at the University of the West of Scotland. The findings from this study will be disseminated in the form of a written thesis, submission for publication in peer reviewed journals and presentations internally and externally to [redacted]
What is the agreement relating to intellectual property, publication and authorship?	The University of the West of Scotland will have primary ownership of intellectual property, publication, and authorship. A summary of the interviews can be provided on request.
How will [redacted] be recognised?	[redacted] will be recognized as an invaluable collaborator in this study in the final publication. The [redacted] logo will be included on all study documentation.
Have you identified a collaborator from the [redacted] team? If yes please provide details	Dr Louise Melvin

Researchers running projects in [redacted] will have the option of publicising their work on the [redacted] website within the research pages of the professional microsite (current research projects at [redacted]). It is likely that ethical approval will be needed for research materials uploaded on to the website, similar to what is required for participant information materials. To submit research publicity materials for approval for display on the website, go to [http://www.\[redacted\].org/professionals/sandyford-digital-media-request-form/](http://www.[redacted].org/professionals/sandyford-digital-media-request-form/)

[redacted] Research Enquiry process version 3 May 2017

Appendix 8: Formal local approval letter

NHS

PRIVATE & CONFIDENTIAL

Ms Elizabeth Rooney

Advanced Nurse Practitioner

Sexual Health Services

Our ref: LM//RF

Date: 15th April 2020

Dear Ms Rooney

Re: Great PrEPArations: Beyond the risk of HIV. A qualitative study of the experience of men who have sex with men living in areas of high deprivation who are taking pre-exposure prophylaxis to HIV medication (PrEP)

I am pleased to inform you that the Research Governance Group has approved your study being undertaken in the service, subject to Ethics Committee and NHS Research and Development approval.

Yours sincerely

Appendix 9: Formal University of the West of Scotland ethical approval letter

29/07/2020 (Dr Gordon Mackay, ethics co-chair)

Dear Elizabeth Rooney,

Your application 5188: Great PrEParations: beyond the risk of HIV. A qualitative study of gay and bisexual men's lived experience of taking Pre-exposure Prophylaxis to HIV medication (PrEP) in the West of Scotland, submission 10529, has been approved by the Health and Life Sciences SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr Gary Boyd

Appendix 10: Formal NHS Board ethical approval letter

Scotland, UK

Ms Elizabeth Rooney

NHS [redacted] Board Approval

Dear Ms Elizabeth Rooney

Study Title:	Great PrEPArations: beyond the risk of HIV. A qualitative study of the experience of men who have sex with men living in areas of high deprivation who are taking Pre-exposure Prophylaxis to HIV medication (PrEP)
Principal Investigator:	Ms Elizabeth Rooney
[redacted] HB site	[redacted]
Sponsor	[redacted]
R&I reference:	[redacted]
REC reference:	[redacted]
Protocol no: (including version and date)	[redacted]

I am pleased to confirm that [redacted] Health Board is now able to grant Approval for the above study.

Conditions of Approval

1. For Clinical Trials as defined by the Medicines for Human Use Clinical Trial Regulations, 2004
 - a. During the life span of the study [redacted] HB requires the following information relating to this site
 - i. Notification of any potential serious breaches.
 - ii. Notification of any regulatory inspections.

It is your responsibility to ensure that all staff involved in the study at this site have the appropriate GCP training according to the [redacted] HB GCP policy (www.nhs.gov.uk/content/default.asp?page=s1411), evidence of such training to be filed in the site file. Researchers must follow NHS [redacted] local policies, including incident reporting.

2. For all studies the following information is required during their lifespan.
 - a. First study participant should be recruited within 30 days of approval date.
 - b. Recruitment Numbers on a monthly basis
 - c. Any change to local research team staff should be notified to R&I team

- d. Any amendments – Substantial or Non Substantial
- e. Notification of Trial/study end including final recruitment figures
- f. Final Report & Copies of Publications/Abstracts
- g. You must work in accordance with the current NHS GG&C COVID19 guidelines and principles.

Please add this approval to your study file as this letter may be subject to audit and monitoring.

Your personal information will be held on a secure national web-based NHS database.

I wish you every success with this research study

Yours sincerely,

Kayleigh McKenna
Senior Research Administrator

Appendix 11: Participant information sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Title: Great PrEPArations: beyond the risk of HIV. A qualitative study of the experience of men who have sex with men living in areas of high deprivation who are taking Pre-exposure Prophylaxis to HIV medication (PrEP)

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please don't hesitate to get in touch or to ask Elizabeth Rooney or her supervisor Dr Fiona Smith if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

1. What is the purpose of the study?

This study is being conducted in part fulfilment of a Professional Doctorate in Nursing exploring the experience of men who have sex with men who are taking PrEP and ensuring that sexual health services meet their needs.

2. Why have I been invited?

We are inviting people over 18 years of age who are taking PrEP prescribed by the NHS. Your views and opinions around PrEP care and delivery will be valuable in shaping the evidence collated for the study.

3. Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. Even if you decide to take part you are still free to withdraw consent at any time without giving a reason and your medical care will not be affected.

4. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be given this information sheet to read and two copies of the consent form for this study when you attend for your PrEP clinic appointment. If you are interested in participating in this study please let the clinician at your appointment know. If you agree, contact details of your first name, phone number and/or email will be passed on to the lead researcher. Then, at least 24 hours later, the lead researcher will contact you to answer any questions you may have and if you still agree to participate, arrange a date and time convenient to yourself for a single telephone interview. We will request that you complete the consent forms, keep one and post the other back to us using the SAE. If you prefer, a consent form can be emailed to you and you can complete it and email it back to us. The lead researcher will then phone you to complete the interview lasting an hour to 90 minutes. The interview will include basic demographic questions and elicit your views and experiences of accessing and taking PrEP medication. If you don't want to answer a question just say so and the interviewer will move on to the next one. All information will be kept confidential unless you tell us something that suggests you or others are at risk of harm, in which case standard safeguarding procedures will be followed. The interview will be audio recorded and the audio recording will be turned into a written document by the lead researcher then all recordings will be

immediately destroyed. Quotations from interviews will be used but they will be allocated a pseudonym by the lead researcher so you will not be identifiable from them. If you so wish, copies of the themes raised from the transcripts will be sent to you for verification and you can request a copy of the results of this study.

5. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no benefits to you individually, however by taking part your views may identify what works, what doesn't work and why and the study can identify recommendations for improving delivery of PrEP.

6. What are the possible disadvantages of taking part?

There are no identifiable risks to you in taking part in this study. However if you feel uncomfortable about any topics raised in the interview, please let the researcher know and the interview can be stopped until you feel able to continue or it can be terminated. The interviewer can support you and direct you to organisations that can help you should you feel the need. There is no reimbursement for taking part.

7. Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

Yes. In the UK all research using patient data must follow the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation, EU, 2018) rules and the law called the Data Protection Act. Universities and the NHS are funded from taxes and they are expected to do research as part of their job. They still need to be able to prove that they need to use patient data for the research. In legal terms this means that they use patient data as part of 'a task in the public interest'. If they could do the research without using patient data they would not be allowed to get your data. Researchers must show that their research takes account of the views of patients and ordinary members of the public. They must also show how they protect the privacy of the people who take part. An NHS research ethics committee checks this before the research starts. You will be identified by a pseudonym and any information about you will have your name and contact details removed so that you cannot be recognised from it. Only the lead researcher will have access to participants' identification details. Storage of your personal data will be in accordance with the Data Protection Act (2018). All information will be held securely in line with University of the West of Scotland policy in a locked cabinet in a locked room at UWS. Study notes will be destroyed five years after the study is completed in line with University regulations.

8. What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the study will be used in a dissertation which will be submitted in part fulfilment of the Professional Doctorate in Nursing at the University of the West of Scotland. This may inform recommendations to research funding bodies and grant applicants. They may also be published in scientific journals and presented at scientific meetings. You will not be identified in any report or publication.

9. Who is organising and funding the research?

The study is being undertaken by Elizabeth Rooney in part of fulfilment of the Professional Doctorate in Nursing at the University of the West of Scotland. Her academic supervisor is Dr Fiona Smith. The course is part funded by NHS [redacted] Primary Care Division and the Royal College of Nursing. The study has no commercial sponsorship.

10. Who has reviewed the study?

The scientific content of the research has been reviewed by the academic supervisors, NHS [redacted] and the University of the West of Scotland Research Ethics Committee.

11. Contact for Further Information

Elizabeth Rooney, Advanced Nurse Practitioner, NHS [redacted]

email: [REDACTED]

or Dr Fiona Smith, Lecturer (Adult Health), School of Health & Life Sciences,
Room A718, Barbour Building, University of the West of Scotland, High Street Paisley PA1 2BE

For concerns regarding the conduct of the research project please contact Sarah Scrivens, University Ethics Committee, ethics@uws.ac.uk, 0141 848 3351 or East of England - Essex Research Ethics Committee, email: Essex.REC@hra.nhs.uk

Appendix 13: Interview topic guide

Topic Guide for Interview

Title of Project: Great PrEPArations: beyond the risk of HIV. A qualitative study of the experience of men who have sex with men living in areas of high deprivation who are taking Pre-exposure Prophylaxis to HIV medication (PrEP)

Name of Researcher: Elizabeth Rooney

Introductory statement:

I am going to ask you some questions exploring your viewpoints and your experience of accessing and taking PrEP medication. The interview will be audio recorded but all information will be kept confidential unless you tell us something that suggests you or others are at risk of harm, in which case standard safeguarding procedures will be followed.. If there are any questions you do not want to answer just tell me and we can move on to the next one. If you do not understand a question just ask me to explain it to you. Remember you do not have to take part and can change your mind at anytime, including during the interview and your care will not be affected. If you feel uncomfortable about any topics raised in the interview, please let the me know and the interview can be stopped and support offered.

Patient demographics: Highest educational qualification/Income/Job title

How did you hear about PrEP?

Why did you decide to start taking PrEP? Did you ask for it or was it offered to you? Stopping it?

Can you tell me about your experience of PrEP in general? What is it like?

What was your experience of accessing it?

What do you think of PrEP?

Prompts: Good and bad points Why? Broader effects in the gay scene/society?

What about other men you know? Does anyone else take it?

Prompts: your peer group, experience, knowledge, access, stigma etc.

How do you remember to take it?

Has your sex life changed with PrEP?

Prompts: In terms of condoms? Partners? Negotiations?

Any other comments

Version 2 Topic Guide 4/12/20 Rooney/Appendix 3

Appendix 15: Example of data analysis themes generation informed by IPA

Knowledge of PrEP at initiation

This category is contextual and concerns what had actually happened when participants made the decision to start taking PrEP. Their rationale for starting PrEP (such as PrEP reducing the risk of HIV), or their concerns (such as toxicity or not wanting to take tablets) are addressed separately.

(Related to the a priori knowledge in Question 1 of the interview topic guide: How had you heard about PrEP? Why did you decide to start taking PrEP? Prompt: Did they ask for it or was it offered to them? Etc.)

Descriptive comments across the cases	No. of participants
Had they heard of PrEP before coming into the clinic	
<i>I'd never heard of PrEP</i>	1
<i>I'd heard of PrEP but hadn't decided to start it</i>	7 Recurrent (super ordinate theme?)
<i>I came to the clinic specifically for PrEP</i>	3
For those who had heard of PrEP, where had they heard of it	
<i>On the grapevine</i>	2
<i>Work colleagues as I work in healthcare</i>	4
<i>Work colleagues and I don't work in healthcare</i>	1
<i>Partner(s)</i>	2
<i>Friend(s)</i>	3
<i>LGBT community</i>	1
<i>Online websites</i>	5
<i>Online dating mobile phone apps</i>	1
<i>Tabloids/newspaper</i>	2
<i>I was moving on to PrEP from PEPSE</i>	1
<i>I was on the English PrEP trial</i>	1
For those that had heard of PrEP, why had they not started it	
<i>Only occasionally had sex, didn't think I was eligible</i>	1

<i>Didn't know enough about it/uncertainty about efficacy/how it worked</i>	3
<i>Hadn't really considered it</i>	2
<i>Didn't know I could get it in this clinic</i>	1
Why they then changed their minds to decide to start taking PrEP	
<i>PrEP explained to me by healthcare staff, they recommended it and I agreed</i>	7 Recurrent (super ordinate theme)
For those who asked for PrEP in clinic, why was this	
<i>No one would have sex with me if I wasn't taking it</i>	2
<i>Partner started it</i>	1
For those who hadn't asked for PrEP, why were they in clinic	
<i>Routine sexual health screen</i>	6
<i>I had symptoms</i>	1
<i>Went from PEPSE to PrEP</i>	1
Who do they know of/think may not have heard of PrEP	
<i>GBMSM married to women</i>	4
<i>Homeless/traveller/refugee/different ethnic groups</i>	1
<i>Heterosexual people and lesbians see it as only for gay men</i>	3
<i>Young people as they have poor HIV literacy</i>	3
<i>Experience of NHS staff outside of sexual health having not heard of PrEP</i>	3
<i>GBMSM who go to cruising areas as there's no conversation</i>	1
<i>GBMSM not on the gay scene</i>	2

Exploratory comments

Descriptive comments are shown in maroon above

Linguistic comments are shown in blue italics below

Conceptual comments are shown in green underlined below

Theme generation

Theme: Barriers to PrEP uptake - no knowledge of PrEP

Amongst GBMSM:

*the younger ones that don't know and are naïve (to PrEP)
I can't believe that there's still gay people that I come across that don't know what it is
married men out there they've never heard of it
if nobody's explained you then you're not going to know
what the hell's prep?
it's not widely known about.*

Repercussions of the decision not to promote PrEP – those not on the 'gay scene' or met partners cruising where there was no conversation – or young or bisexual GBMSM – inequalities – HIV literacy – sex education – generational differences – concerns about confidentiality for married men – people who don't attend sexual health services – GBMSM who attend sexual health services will be offered PrEP – GBMSM with friends/partners on PrEP will hear of it – will leave a section of the population who will not – participants spoke about PrEP being on some GBMSM's online profiles – many don't meet online – if they do why have they not seen a mention of PrEP online? – GBMSM on PrEP feel it is important to tell others about it/encourage them to start it – word of mouth

Amongst healthcare professionals:

*oh, that's quite good never heard of it and had to go and look it up (heard in hospital)
you're clearly going to come across some gay patients
I was really like oh my god, seriously, she'd never heard of prep (of the nurse in hospital)
If I was just a wee opportunistic closet gay that had this chance with the nurse to say, and she didn't know about it*

PrEP not promoted in wider NHS – staff training – cultural competence – patient care – health promotion – missed opportunities – sexual health services are very separate to rest of NHS services – separate building, staff don't work with staff from other areas – very isolated – specialist - public health policy? – is sexual health still a Cinderella service – stigma even in NHS - why

Theme: Barriers to PrEP uptake: insufficient knowledge of PrEP

How people who have heard of PrEP were not taking it:

*limited prior knowledge of it
would have had a critical eye to it
Heard mention of it, not in general conversation*

*some people that have not been aware that you could just get it for free
it wasn't something that was stored in my mind and questioned it was just something
that just passed through
it wasn't really something people talked about
uncertainty on all levels
Pretty unconvinced
some kind of new-fangled thing
not sure if I understood it correctly, what it was actually doing,
worried about it being, doing what it says it can do,
not 100% sure how prep worked
I just thought you would be taking prep but still walking around with chlamydia or
syphilis*

heterosexual community... they assume that it's just for the gay community

*the decision not to promote PrEP – minimal information and knowledge of PrEP –
these GBMSM are not even in the pre contemplative phase of the behaviour
change model they are not considering PrEP at all despite having heard of it –
none of them even looked into it – just passed everyone by – vague – what knowledge
they did have appeared negative – suspicious – no faith in it – no curiosity?*

Theme: Facilitators to PrEP uptake – knowledge:

*friends and family I've got that are positive I've been kind of brought up educated
participated in that prep impact trial, (then moved city) went for regular screening and
found out about the availability of prep
after the pep they had recommended that prep would be a viable option*

And those taking PrEP only to be sexually active:

*People who wanted to have sex were not prepared to have sex unless you were
prepared to do it without a condom.
So without PrEP you were eliminated
to be inclusive
go on prep so that you weren't left out.
we kind of felt excluded.*

*GBMSM here are not starting PrEP because of the reduced risk of HIV they are
starting it to be able to have a sex life – stigma in not taking PrEP – condom use
stopping – due to PrEP and lower risk of HIV so not required any more – normalisation
of PrEP – normalisation of condomless sex – what about GBMSM who aren't taking
PrEP and condoms? – under pressure – the participant who started PrEP because of
his partner was "recruited" by his partner, who was just back from the USA and had
seen PrEP there*

Theme: cultural competence of the nurse

*they provide you with everything you need to know in a digestible way
know exactly what they're talking about
like unsung heroes
are amazing, passionate, non-judgemental
he explained to me what it was and I thought well fair enough so
every time he asked a question they explained why they were asking it
in great detail, asked me if I understood and if I didn't he explained it even more
I was put at ease straightaway
And they don't hold back on the questions!
it was'nae like forced upon me,
it's something that you should think about*

super ordinate theme – attend clinic for a different reason, usually sexual health screen – limited or no knowledge of PrEP and no intentions to take it – leave clinic with PrEP or appointment to start it – why? – cultural competence of staff – knowledge – training – attitude – patient relationship – health promotion – information provision – safe prescribing – patient centred care – would participants have started PrEP otherwise? – how important are the staff – is it just because someone has posited the idea of PrEP? – or is it just that **PrEP is a great quality medication** – WHO AAAQ – fits with theme rationale for taking PrEP – as one participant said it's a 'no-brainer' – and as with word of mouth, how much would anyone explaining PrEP encourage someone to take it – and how much is the knowledge and expertise of the healthcare professional

Excerpts from lead researcher reflexive diary:

Reflection on participant description of PrEP implementation:

These participants experiences of PrEP implementation reflect my own as a clinician. I had not heard mention of PrEP, then it appeared out of the blue at the same time as the HPV vaccine for GBMSM. There was one training session on it then were told to start prescribing it. There were a lot of unaddressed concerns and unanswered questions about potential problems and interactions with other medical conditions etc. and people prescribing outside their competence. There were also a lot of concerns about consultation times – GBMSM consultations are already long involving HPV vaccine, hepatitis testing and vaccine, HIV literacy, PEPSE, risk reduction and condoms and STI testing of additional sites and now PrEP – all in 30mins! Staff were moved from other clinics to cover – It all appeared to happen in a fast, ad hoc manner with no additional financial or staff resources with a kind of 'start it and deal with problems as they arise' message. Having said that, in general research and treatments do change quickly and the push is to make them available to patients safely but in a timely manner.

Reflection on the participants comments about the clinic staff

I was surprised at the significance of this theme around participants appearing to start PrEP due to their consultation with the clinician. However the staff that were prescribing PrEP in the clinics were all very experienced – mostly doctors and

advanced practitioners – who were educated to at least PG Cert level, prescribers, been working in sexual health and GU for years, and all although had different consultation styles would have been experienced and competent. Fast forward to after implementation (and some adverse events and datixes) the PrEP clinics I think were running very efficiently and well. I don't think that anyone pushed PrEP onto patients – it was seen as in line with other treatments and STI prevention - but the message would have been you are eligible for this medication as there is a risk of HIV, this will greatly reduce your risk of HIV, we can give it to you, you should consider it.

Appendix 16: Example of confirmability of data analysis by supervisor

Education	Employment	PrEP Medication rationale/uptake	PrEP Medication duration	PrEP/HIV and historical perceptions/beliefs	PrEP Knowledge	PrEP Access
Postgraduate – Participant 4	Professional – Participant 4	-condoms less popular Uptake -rapid -participant 4	3-4 years – participant 4	Stigma similar to HIV, you are sleeping around or dirty or a slut -PrEP shaming -HIV in LGBT -Lack of education -Hiv pos people resent prep didn't exist at the time and encourage people to take it	General communications Vague reference in PrEP population Online applications (which ones) Tabloids	Sandyford at routine sexual health screening English Clinical Trial
					Lack of PrEP knowledge Younger people not heard of it Exclusion LGBT – why? -ignorance Exclusion Medical/hospital Exclusion wider community - why?	

PrEP and Normalisation	PrEP Medication concordance	PrEP non-concordance	PrEP Facilitators	These need coding
Everyone is taking it Grapevine No stigma – norm	-Safety and protection -Harm minimisation if both partners use PrEP -Screening benefits Reassured re toxicity by routine kidney function tests -Maturity (age) -Ease of use -Convenient Practical/behavioural in line with other meds/ritual/habits	-Depending on sexual activity -Lack of multiple partners toxicity -side effects -Intestinal - Contraindications of medication -Expense Apathy -Not bothered -Shyness -type and length of relationship (Part 4) The burden of treatment -daily pill requirement	-Pharmacy access -Vaccine - Online/phone is much quicker and easier logistically, simple -Sexual health screening alongside PrEP medication -larger supply - PrEP posting - HIV education in schools -friends	Other stis are curable so not worried Little knowledge of other stis people bin flyers and don't talk Other people are worried about stis Partners talk about prep and ask if each other is on it Pressure to come off prep if in a relationship

	-Social link/aspect HIV community - Other health problems making you consider your health more seriously Informed and educated -long term relationship (Part 4)	-hate taking pills -run out - forgetting, taking ebd not daily - geographical access - pragmatic -bloods only from Sandyford - Appointments - postal kit but pain & bleeding for long time trying to get blood test -embarrassment people/experience of sexual health screening -scared - work commitments - Pandemic. - Timeliness in attending clinics Side effects -intestinal -		People asking for it from partners to sell in England Sexual behaviour has remained the same Some people had more risky sexual encounters and more partners at the start - thought they had invincible shield - then people got other stis and calmed down Has less worry about having upsi with people hiv pos undetectable viral load More confident having sex
Current perceptions				

Young people less stigma, non binary etc., more open				

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